

PH.D. IN ASTRONOMY, ASTROPHYSICS
AND SPACE SCIENCE

CYCLE XXXIII

MODELLING OF BLACK HOLE WINDS
FROM THE HORIZON UP TO GALAXY SCALES

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A.Y. 2020/2021

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*Dedicated to Giulio Regeni,
Patrick Zaki and all my colleagues.
Solidarity forever, solidarity for all.*

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1. AGN: phenomenology and physics

1.1 General overview

Active Galactic Nuclei are among the most energetic sources observed in the Universe. They are powered by accretion onto the supermassive black holes (SMBHs) harboured at the centre of almost every galaxy, and their energy output is so high that they can easily outshine the luminosity of their host galaxy. Accretion is by far the most efficient energy conversion process, and actually represents one of the main channels for SMBHs to grow their mass during the galaxy lifetime. Thanks to this, AGN represents the most powerful non-explosive astrophysical source and enables us to study in detail the extreme physical processes governing matter and energy flows and their role in the galaxy evolution.

The AGN radiative output spans the entire electromagnetic spectrum, from the radio up to the γ -ray band, with a wealth of different spectral features. All the systems appear to share some basic properties, such as i) extremely high luminosity, ii) small emitting regions in all bands, as suggested by the extreme observed variability, iii) highly broadened and blueshifted absorption and emission features, especially in the optical, UV and X-ray bands (see below). On the other hand, differences are observed from source to source in many energy band, thus casting a doubt on whether all AGN types are essentially the same objects. Nowadays, a general, unifying picture of the AGN physics has emerged, which is able to account for the shared properties and the observed peculiarities (Antonucci, 1993; Urry, & Padovani, 1995). The leading actors shaping the AGN properties and observational appearance can be reduced to a very small number: orientation, accretion rate, the presence and (eventually) the strength of jets. One of the simplest and most popular sketch of an AGN structure is presented in Fig. 1.1, while a typical AGN spectral energy distribution (SED) is presented in Fig. 1.2.

AGN shows an axisymmetric structure, with the SMBH at the centre. Being one of the simplest compact objects, a SMBH can be simply described through its mass M and spin. M can be constrained with a relative confidence and it is usually found to lie in the $10^6 - 10^9 M_\odot$ range, where M_\odot is the solar mass, while the spin can only be indirectly estimated and, at the moment, there seems to be no favourite or peculiar values. The accretion process takes place on the equatorial plane, where the infalling matter is in form of a rapidly-rotating disc, since it needs to lose its galactic-scale angular momentum. This accretion disc can, in principle, extend

Figure 1.1: Conceptual view of an Active Galactic Nucleus. Bottom and top panel refer to radio-quiet and radio-loud objects, respectively. Different components and sight lines are indicated. Adapted from Beckmann & Shrader (2012).

Figure 1.2: A sketch of an AGN SED. Black solid curve represents the total SED, while the different components are represented with coloured curves. The far ultra-violet band is absorbed by the host galaxy, therefore it is labelled as "largely unobservable". In the radio band, both RL and RQ profiles are represented. For comparison, a starburst galaxy SED is also shown with light gray curve. From Harrison et al. (2014)

up to the innermost stable circular orbit (*ISCO*) of the SMBH; therefore, a significant fraction of the SMBH gravitational potential is converted into thermal energy, i.e. (mostly) radiation. The conversion efficiency η between infalling matter and energy is around 0.10 (Davis & Laor, 2011), making accretion the most efficient engine in the Universe, orders of magnitude more than fusion and fission processes.

This energy output directly dominates the X-ray and UV emission in AGNs. In the UV a "big blue bump" component is observed, given by the multicolor blackbody emission from the disc, peaking at temperatures around $10^5 K$. The X-ray band is shaped by a so-called "corona", i.e. a hot ($T \approx 10^9 K$), tenuous atmosphere embedding the SMBH and the innermost part of disc, that reprocesses the UV seed photons giving rise to a power-law spectrum with a cut-off corresponding to the temperature of the electrons in the corona (Elvis et al., 1994; Koratkar & Blaes, 1999; Vasudevan & Fabian, 2007).

Moving outward, the accretion disc is expected to cool, and after the so-called "dust sublimation radius", at scales of the order of $\approx 1 pc$, theoretical and observational evidences suggest a transition to a less dense, cold and dusty "torus". This component has a typical thermal emission spectrum peaking in the IR range. The height of the torus with respect to the disc plane is of the order of its radial distance from the black hole ($\frac{H}{R} \approx 1$). This way, all the sightlines from the SMBH with an altitude less than $45deg$ are bound to intersect the torus. Conversely, this implies that the line of sight (LOS) of an external observer will also cross the torus if its inclination is $< 45deg$ from the disc plane. All the LOS lying at $> 45deg$ from the disc plane, instead, will see the bare nucleus, with no traces of the torus absorption.

This picture corresponds to the basic difference between so-called Type-II AGNs, for which absorption deeply affects the observed SED especially in the soft X-ray-to-optical range, and Type-I, where absorption is negligible or, at least, subdominant. In Figure 1.1, lower half, other two components, namely the Broad Line Region (BLR) and Narrow Line Region (NLR), are indicated. The former identifies rapidly rotating gas (with velocities $10^3 - 10^4 km/s$) emitting in the optical/UV band, which is observed in Type-I but not in Type-II AGNs. Again, this difference can be explained thanks to orientation effects, since the short distances from the SMBH required to reproduce the fast rotational velocities are well within the typical torus scale. Conversely, emission lines from the NLR are characterised by a lower width, parametrised through the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM), which is usually $< 10^3 km/s$. Therefore, NLR is located at higher distances, and they can be observed independently both in Type-I and Type-II AGNs (Richards et al., 2002; Kuraszkiewicz et al., 2004; Shen et al., 2011; Vietri et al., 2018, 2020). This picture is also confirmed by the gas electronic density in the two cases: BLR have $n \approx 10^{10} cm^{-3}$, while in NLR $n = 10^6 - 10^8 cm^{-3}$ (Peterson, 1997; Netzer, 2013). Studies of the absorption in the X-ray band in Type-I and -II AGNs confirm this basic scheme (Dadina, 2008).

Accretion rate onto the SMBH is the second main "ingredient" and results in an overall "scaling" of the AGN properties, such as its luminosity and the strength and velocity of the optical, UV and X-rays absorption and emission features (see review by Giustini & Proga, 2019 and references therein). In the basic picture, as implicitly assumed until now, the accretion flow is structured into a geometrically thin, optically thick disc (Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973; Novikov & Thorne, 1973) with a very high radiative efficiency, producing a very bright UV and X spectra. This scenario is valid for a broad range of accretion rates and represents a good description of the AGN for the aims of the present work. However, for $\dot{m} \leq 10^{-2}$, where \dot{m} indicates the accreting matter onto the SMBH normalised to the Eddington value, the disc becomes radiatively inefficient and, as a consequence, optical-UV emission is strongly reduced. Typical η drops to 0.01 (Sądowski & Gaspari, 2017). In the extreme limit $\dot{m} < 10^{-6}$ the AGN can be considered as quiescent/inactive, such as for our own Galactic centre, Sgr A* . At the opposite end, for $\dot{m} \gg 1$, the onset of advective cooling (besides the radiative cooling) reduce η to some percent (Sądowski & Narayan, 2016; Jiang et al., 2019), but the overall physical structure of the disc is similar to the thin disc case.

We report in Fig. 1.3 (left panel) the fraction f_{obs} of Compton-thin obscured AGNs (absorbing column $10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2} \leq N_H \leq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) as a function of the accretion rate, for a large hard X-ray selected sample (Ricci et al., 2017). The accretion rate is expressed as $\lambda_{Edd} = L_{bol}/L_{Edd}$, where $\lambda_{Edd} = L_{bol}/L_{Edd}$ is the ratio between the bolometric and the Eddington luminosities and is a proxy of \dot{m} . f_{obs} is the highest for $\lambda_{Edd} = 10^{-4} - 10^{-2}$ and drops suddenly for $\lambda_{Edd} \geq 10^{-2}$. This value corresponds to the "effective" Eddington limit for a dusty gas, and indicates that the accretion luminosity is able to sweep out the gas around the AGN and to significantly impact its observational properties. Moreover, f_{obs} shows a decrease for $L_{bol}/L_{Edd} < 10^{-4}$ too, which can be explained by a quiescent state of the AGN in which both the infalling and the outflowing gas are considerably reduced. On the other hand, the fraction of Compton-thick obscured sources ($N_H > 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) is independent from λ_{Edd} , suggesting a two-phase scenario for the accretion region (see right panel). A compact, almost luminosity-independent component is responsible for the Compton-thick absorption and corresponds to the innermost, optically thick part of the accretion disc. Compton-thin absorption, instead, originates from the disc surface layers, where optically thin gas may be linked to a puffed up photosphere or outflow.

Finally, the presence of a relativistic jet also plays a major role in shaping the AGN and its observational properties. According to the most popular scenario, jets are launched by extracting angular momentum from the SMBH ergosphere (Blandford & Znajek, 1977), reaching a very high speed, up to 99 % of the speed of light. They exhibit a high degree of collimation and can extend up to galactic scales. Synchrotron emission from the jet dominates the radio band, and can contribute significantly also to the X-ray band. In the most extreme cases, when the jet

Figure 1.3: Left panel: fraction of Compton-thin ($10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2} \leq N_H \leq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) obscured sources as a function of the accretion rate λ_{Edd} , for a sample of hard X-ray selected sources. Shaded area represents the standard deviation from the average value. Vertical dashed line corresponds to the "effective" Eddington limit for dusty gas. Right panel: cartoon showing the geometry of Compton-thick and -thin absorbing regions (dark and light gray, respectively) for low and high Eddington ratios (left and right, respectively). Adapted from Ricci et al. (2017).

is pointed towards the observer (so-called blazar AGNs), the relativistic beaming concentrates most of its emission along the LOS and the jet profile can dominate the whole SED. In this case a broad double peak, due to synchrotron radiation, spans the entire electromagnetic domain from the radio up to the Gamma band (see Fig. 1.2). The fraction of AGNs with a relativistic jet is a minority among the broad AGN population, between 1% and 10% (see Padovani et al., 2017 and references therein). The formation and the strength of a jet are not firmly established theoretically. However, they seem to be predominant for radiatively inefficient accretion flows, especially at $\dot{m} \leq 10^{-2}$ and, perhaps, $\dot{m} \gg 1$ (see Giustini & Proga, 2019). Moreover, a high SMBH spin seems to favour the jet launching (Tchekhovskoy et al., 2011; Tchekhovskoy, 2015; Narayan et al., 2014).

To summarise, we briefly describe the AGN classes reported in Fig. 1.1 according to the three fundamental properties discussed above: orientation, accretion rate (luminosity) and jet activity.

- Type-I and type-II sources are classified according to the FWHM of their broad and narrow emission lines. High inclination objects (type-I) are unobscured by the torus, therefore they clearly display both broad and narrow emission lines, whereas in low inclination objects (type-II) broad lines are obscured.
- Moderate luminosity objects are referred to as Seyfert galaxies ($L_{bol} \approx 10^{40} - 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) and represent the dominating population at low- z . Quasars (or QSOs) are the high-

luminosity and, usually, high- z counterparts of Seyferts, with $L_{bol} \geq 10^{46} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. They also show values of \dot{m} close to 1, while Seyfert have \dot{m} between 0.01 and 0.5 (see e.g. Tombesi et al., 2010).

- The jet strength is usually parametrised through the radio flux F_{radio} : AGNs with $\frac{F_{radio}}{F_{opt}} > 10$ are generally defined as radio-loud (RL), otherwise they are radio-quiet (RQ; upper and lower half of Figure 1.1, respectively). Broad Line and Narrow Line Radio Galaxies are the counterpart of RQ Type-I and -II, and the same holds for RL and RQ quasars. Finally, blazars are dominated by the relativistically beamed jet emission throughout the SED.

1.2 The Accretion Disc - Corona Paradigm

1.2.1 Accretion modes

Accretion disc is the "central engine" of the AGN. The gravitational energy, once converted into radiation, is responsible practically for the whole AGN SED, either in the form of direct, thermal radiation (as for the UV part) or reprocessed at different distances and different wavelengths.

The first accretion model for AGNs has been put forward by Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) (see Novikov & Thorne, 1973 for a general relativistic treatment). The accreting flow is structured into a geometrically thin, optically thick disc, with a roughly Keplerian rotational velocity profile. The main cooling channel is thermal radiation, therefore the mass-to-energy conversion efficiency η is the highest possible. For a disc extending up to the ISCO, η is equal to 0.057 for a non-rotating (Schwarzschild) black hole and 0.42 for a maximally rotating (Kerr) one with a corotating disc.

Gas needs to lose its angular momentum l , accumulated during its galaxy-long journey, to descend at close distance to the SMBH and, finally, get accreted. In order to transfer l out of the disc, Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) focused on the viscosity between adjacent layers of the accretion disc, due to their different rotational velocity. Since the inner layer is faster than the outer one, viscosity allows to transfer momentum from the former to the latter. Since both layer are rotating, this results in a net transfer of angular momentum outward. From a microscopical point of view they explained the viscosity in terms of inner gas turbulence, with the kinematic viscosity coefficient $\nu_* \approx l_0 v_0$, where l_0, v_0 are the turbulence correlation length and mean speed, respectively. Then, assuming that the velocity can not exceed the sound speed, $v_0 < c_s$, and that the typical turbulence size should be within the disc height, $l_0 < H$, the coefficient can be rewritten as:

$$\nu_* = \alpha H c_s \quad (1.1)$$

where α is a dimensionless coefficient, assumed by Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) to be a constant and

Figure 1.4: MRI dynamics. Left side: Evolution of the vertical magnetic field lines. Panels are in (r, z) coordinates and correspond to increasing times from the start of the simulations (indicated in the bottom right of every panel, in units of number of orbits). Right side: magnetic field lines (solid curves) and velocity vectors (arrows) in the (r, z) plane within the disc. Adapted from Balbus & Hawley (1998).

comprised between 0 and 1. This way, the viscous stress tensor (defined as in Landau, Lifshitz, Hydrodynamics book) reads as $T_{r\phi} = \rho v_* r \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial r}$, where the dependence from the rotational velocity profile manifests in the derivative term.

It is not yet clear what kind of physical process is needed to reproduce the value of α derived from the observations (King et al., 2007). Particularly, one of the possibility is represented by the Magneto Rotational Instability (MRI), originally discussed by Velikhov (1959); Chandrasekhar (1960) and adapted to the context of accretion by Balbus & Hawley (1991) (see also the review by Balbus & Hawley, 1998). It is a self-enhancing perturbation generated by close, magnetically-connected particles rotating in the disc. If one of them has, say, slightly higher velocity v_1 with respect to the rotational velocity v_{rot} at its given radius, it will adjust to a different equilibrium configuration at higher r . Conservation of l implies that v_1 decreases. Viceversa, if a second particle has slightly lower v_2 than the equilibrium one, it will fall at lower radius, where it will experience an increase of v_2 . The magnetic field line connecting them will be stretched and, as in the case of a viscous stress, it will transfer momentum outside, i.e. from the closer to the farther particle. This way, the latter will again have $v_1 > v_{rot}$, and the former $v_2 < v_{rot}$, so they will further displace outward and inward, respectively. This mechanism is self-reinforcing and is bound to grow with exponentially, even tough is damped by higher-order perturbations before

the stability of the accretion disc is harmed (see review by Abramowicz & Fragile, 2013 and references therein). In Fig. 1.4, left panel, we show the trend of the magnetic field lines inside the disc as a function of time, and in the right we show a section of the disc, where two simultaneous outflow and inflow streams trace the transfer of l outward and the drifting of accreting gas at inward, respectively.

Finally, it is interesting to highlight the maximum temperature for thin discs, which roughly goes as (see e.g. Spruit, 2010):

$$T_{max}(K) \approx 6 \cdot 10^7 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{r_i^3 M_{BH}^\odot} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (1.2)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass inflow rate \dot{M}_{acc} normalised to the Eddington rate $\dot{M}_{Edd} = \frac{L_{Edd}}{\eta c^2}$ (where we put $\eta = 0.1$ for simplicity), r_i the innermost disc radius in units of Schwarzschild radius $r_S = 2GM_{BH}/c^2$ and M_{BH}^\odot the black hole mass in solar units. This temperature can be translated into a typical photon thermal energy of:

$$E_{ph}(keV) \approx 5 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{r_i^3 M_{BH}^\odot} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (1.3)$$

indicating the peak of the big blue bump. For $M_{BH} = 10^6 - 10^8 M_\odot$, $\dot{m} = 1$, $r_i = 1$, we obtain $E_{ph} = 0.2 - 0.05 keV$, indicating that the main radiative contribution for AGN-sized SMBH lies in the UV band indeed.

This so-called thin disc scenario (since radiation is able to keep gas pressure low enough so that $H \ll R$, i.e. its altitude is small compared to the radius) is valid for a broad range of accretion rates and represents a good description of the accretion system for the aims of the present work. However, as anticipated in Section 1.1, it must be revised in case of extremely low or high accretion rates.

In the low-accretion end, $\dot{m} \leq 10^{-2}$, the disc is not efficiently cooled via radiation and the structure resembles that of an ADAF (advection-dominated accretion flow). As a consequence of the low irradiation, the gas temperature and, most importantly, pressure become very high, with a few important consequences on the structure of the disc. First of all, gas pressure puffs up the disc and the vertical altitude H becomes comparable with the radial coordinate R . Thermal pressure in the radial direction alters the rotational velocity profile, leading to sub-Keplerian velocities and higher radial velocities with respect to the thin disc solution. As a consequence of the shorter accretion timescale and the higher H , the gas density is low, and so it has high cooling time and it is optically thin, therefore $\eta \approx 0.01$. Typical gas temperatures are of the order of $T \approx 10^{10} K$. We refer to the review by Narayan & McClintock (2008) for an interesting introduction on

Figure 1.5: Transition between ADAF and thin disc solutions. From bottom to top \dot{m} increases and, as a consequence, radiative cooling is enhanced, driving the change in the disc structure. QS indicates the quiescent state, HS the hard state (where the disc is extremely hot and the accretion gas density is low), IS the intermediate state and, finally, TS is the thermal state, corresponding to the geometrically thin disc. From Narayan & McClintock (2008).

ADAF discs, from which Fig. 1.5 is taken. It shows different disc configurations, from an almost quiescent state (bottom) where $\dot{m} < 10^{-3}$ to two intermediate states ($\dot{m} \approx 10^{-3} - 10^{-1.5}$ and $\dot{m} \approx 10^{-1.5} - 10^{-1}$, respectively) and, finally, a fully thin disc for $\dot{m} \geq 10^{-1}$ (top). The radiatively inefficient, geometrically thick section (ADAF-like) is represented with ellipses, with the intensity of the hatching indicating the gas density (increasing from bottom to top). The temperature is inversely proportional to the radius, so the inner region is hotter and with higher gas pressure, while at large radii the disc transitions to a geometrically thin configuration. The ADAF-like region reduces with increasing \dot{m} , since the increasing gas density enhances radiative cooling.

The assumption of efficient radiative cooling breaks up for high mass inflows, too, ($\dot{m} > 1$) and the disc is better described by a "slim disc" solution (Abramowicz et al., 1988; Beloborodov, 1998). The energy generated during the accretion is so high that it can not be channeled through radiation alone, and advection plays again an important role. This interplay between radiation and advection is similar to the one in the interior of stars, where sun-like ones relies on radiation to dissipate the internal heat, while lower and higher mass stars have predominantly convective cores (see e.g. Kippenhahn et al., 2012). Interestingly, while in stellar theory the different regimes are driven by the mass of the star, in accretion disc theory the driving factor is the

inflowing mass \dot{m} .

Figure 1.6: Radiative efficiency η (left) and luminosity (in Eddington units, right) for a slim disc as a function of \dot{m} . Different lines refer to different spin values a . Blue points correspond to numerical solutions and the continuous curves to analytic fits. From Madau et al. (2014)

Figure 1.7: Transition between thin and slim disc. Left panel: ratio between the energy transported through advection and radiation as a function of radius r in gravitational units. Different curves refer to different \dot{m} and spin values a , as indicated. The *ISCO* is represented with a vertical line. Right panel: Emitted flux (both through advection and radiation) as a function of r . Line style as in the left panel. From Abramowicz & Fragile (2013)

From a mathematical point of view, slim disc is a generalisation of the thin disc solution, since it allows both radiative and advective cooling and does not assume a Keplerian rotational profile. In the low \dot{m} limit it converges to a thin disc configuration, while for super-Eddington

Figure 1.8: Composite quasar spectrum calculated from a sample of 2200 quasars at $0.04 \leq z \leq 4.79$ from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. Dashed and dotted lines refer to power-law fits of the UV and optical bands, respectively. From Vanden Berk et al. (2001)

accretion the disc is geometrically thicker (with a maximum H/R ratio of about 0.3) and the advection reduces the radiative efficiency η to ≈ 0.01 . Specifically, a significant part of the energy is not liberated at all, and gets accreted directly onto the SMBH. We show in Fig. 1.6, left panel, η as a function of \dot{m} according to the slim disc model discussed in Madau et al. (2014), from where the Figure is taken. Different lines correspond to different spin values a . In the low accretion limit, we find the constant η values derived above for the thin disc model, where the inner boundary is set at the ISCO. For $\dot{m} > 1$, instead, the efficiency drops and reaches 0.01 for $\dot{m} = 10$. Viceversa, in the right panel we see that the luminosity linearly grows until $\dot{m} = 1$, after which it saturates asymptotically.

The disc structure is detailed in Fig. 1.7. Left panel shows the advective energy flux f_{adv} normalised to the electromagnetic flux, as a function of the radius (in units of r_G) and for different \dot{m} and spin values. For $\dot{m} = 0.01$ the disc is in the thin limit and $f_{adv} \approx 0$, while for increasing mass flux f_{adv} also increases, indicating that most of the energy is channeled into advection. Right panel shows the electromagnetic flux as a function of r . While for $\dot{m} \leq 0.1$ the emission is confined to the ISCO, for higher mass fluxes it extends up to the event horizon, and a significant fraction of energy is directly accreted onto the SMBH.

As discussed above, the peak of disc emission is in the far ultraviolet region (the so-called Big Blue Bump), which is strongly absorbed by the host galaxy ISM. However, observations show a general agreement with the accretion disc models discussed above (Vanden Berk et al.,

2020; Campitiello et al., 2020). We show in Fig. 1.8 a stacked UV spectrum of 2200 quasars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (from Vanden Berk et al., 2001).

1.2.2 The X-ray corona: heating and emission mechanisms

Joint UV - X-ray analysis (see e.g. Nandra et al., 2000; Petrucci et al., 2013 and references therein) support the accretion disc - corona interplay, where the latter component is responsible for the Comptonisation of seed UV photons from the disc, originating the X-ray spectrum. This process takes part in the innermost part of the accretion disc. Current estimates, using spectroscopy (especially on lensed AGNs) and time variability, puts an upper limit at $10 r_G$ from the SMBH. Within this region, UV radiation emitted from the accretion disc is reprocessed by an overlooking "corona" of hot gas, with typical temperatures kT of the order of one to some $100keV$ (Fabian et al., 2017; Lanzuisi et al., 2019). This hot atmosphere, named after the Sun corona, is probably energised and maintained through some kind of instability in the accretion flow and its magnetic field. Particularly, magnetic reconnection events could liberate enough energy to steadily sustain the corona (Haardt & Maraschi, 1991).

Once emitted from the disc surface, UV photons will interact with the hot electrons in the corona and get up-scattered through inverse Compton. Following simple energy conservations arguments and assuming a thermal distribution for the electrons around a mean value $\Theta = kT_e/m_e c^2$, it is possible to calculate the photon energy gain as $\epsilon_{out} = (1 + 4\Theta)\epsilon_{in}$. Obviously, from an energy conservation point of view, the photon gains energy from the interaction until $\epsilon_{out} \lesssim \epsilon_n$, where ϵ_n is the average (thermal) electron energy. This condition can be written also as $\epsilon_{out} \lesssim 3\Theta$. The probability of a photon-electron interaction is, of course, proportional to the gas optical depth $\tau = \sigma_T nR$, i.e. the Thompson cross-section time the electron number density and the mean free path. After the first interaction, a fraction τ of the scattered photon will interact again with the gas, and so on until $\epsilon_{out} \approx \epsilon_n$. This "iterative" process leads to a power-law profile, i.e. the flux of emitted photons (in units of counts per second per keV) from the corona as a function of their energy ϵ is $f(\epsilon) \propto \epsilon^{-\Gamma}$. Γ is called the "photon index", and it is linked to the spectral index α (flux of energy as a function of the photon energy, units of erg per second per keV) as $\alpha = \Gamma - 1$. We show in Fig. 1.9, left panel, the power-law spectrum given by the superimposed thermal (blackbody) emission of the multiple scattered photon populations.

This process is interrupted when photons and electrons have comparable average energies, so there is no net gain by one over the other. This leads to a cutoff in the power-law spectrum that can be modelled with an exponential rollover at energies over $50 - 100keV$ (see e.g. Dadina, 2008; Fabian et al., 2015; Middei et al., 2020).

We show in Fig. 1.9, right panel, a comparison between a power-law spectrum with expo-

Figure 1.9: Left panel: The superposition of multiple scattered photon populations, giving rise to a power-law profile. Right panel: comparison between a power-law spectrum and a self-consistent computed Comptonised spectrum. From Done (2010).

nential cutoff (green line) and a more accurate, relativistic-corrected spectrum, obtained with the numerical code COMPPS (see Done, 2010 for the details). The latter goes to zero below the parent photon population energy, which has been fixed to $kT = 0.6 \text{ keV}$, and shows a small bump corresponding to the non-interacting (non upscattered) fraction of seed photons. Differences in the high energy cutoff are also visible.

Figure 1.10: Γ as a function of z for different observational samples (see legend). For the $z > 6$ and $z > 6.5$ points the number of detected photons per observation (counts) is indicated. Error bars are at 68% c.l.. From Vito et al. (2019).

Figure 1.11: An example of X-ray spectrum with the typical observed components (see text). From Risaliti & Elvis (2004)

Interestingly, the accretion disc - hot Corona system does not evolve strongly from low redshift up to $z > 6$. We show in Fig. 1.10 the observed values of the photon index Γ for a wide range of redshift bins, assembled using several samples from the literature. Γ lies in a narrow range around 2 up to $z \sim 7$, notwithstanding the higher noise due to the low flux observations at the highest distances.

Starting from this simple picture, further reflection paths of the up-scattered photons may lead to further spectral components. As an example, we show in Fig. 1.11 some of the features typically observed in an AGN X-ray spectrum. The power-law component is shown in fuchsia, modified by a so-called warm absorber at energies $\approx 1 \text{ keV}$. This term indicates a layer of mildly ionised gas with column densities in the range $10^{20} - 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and velocities up to 10^3 km s^{-1} , observed in almost 50% of the AGNs regardless of their luminosity (Piconcelli et al., 2005). We will describe them in detail in Sect. 1.3. Since reprocessed radiation from the corona is re-emitted almost isotropically, on average half of it will be reflected onto the disc. The reflected spectrum is a convolution of the incident spectrum with the amplitude of the major radiative processes on the reflection plane. Particularly, photoelectric absorption is responsible for the cutoff at energies below $\approx 3 - 4 \text{ keV}$ and leads to a peak at around 30 keV . Reflection may also lead to some fluorescent emission lines from the disc. Due to its relatively high cosmic abundance, the most prominent is formed by neutral or ionised *Fe* at around $6-7 \text{ keV}$ (red line).

Figure 1.12: α_{OX} as a function of $L(2500\text{\AA})$ for different AGN samples from the literature (see legend). Red points in the right end indicate the WISSH hyperluminous sample (Bischetti et al., 2017). Adapted from Martocchia et al. (2017).

If the emission occurs close to the SMBH, its profile will be strongly distorted both because of the rapid disc rotation and of the general relativistic effects.

Finally, cyan line indicates the so-called soft-excess in the soft X-ray band (up to 1-2 keV). A widely accepted explanation for this feature is still missing; however, several studies suggest that it may originate from warm Comptonisation of nuclear-scale gas (Porquet et al., 2004, see also discussion in Done, 2010).

We caution that this picture is far from being firmly established. The small dimension of the X-ray emitting region in AGNs make impossible to resolve it observationally. The wealth of spectral features is entirely encoded along the line of sight, so the same spectrum can often be interpreted as the superimposition of different absorbing and reflecting layers (see discussion in Nardini et al., 2016).

The dynamical behaviour of the accretion discs and the corona reflects in the relationship between the UV and X-ray observed luminosities. In this regard, it is of particular interest the trend of the X-ray to UV luminosity ratio α_{OX} . This quantity is defined as:

$$\alpha_{OX} = \log \frac{L(\nu_X)}{L(\nu_{UV})} / \log \frac{\nu_X}{\nu_{UV}} = 0.384 \log \frac{L(2keV)}{L(2500\text{\AA})} \quad (1.4)$$

where $2keV$, 2500\AA ($= 5eV$) are usually chosen as the representative frequencies for the X-ray and UV band luminosities, respectively (Vignali et al., 2003; Just et al., 2007; Lusso et al., 2010). The α_{OX} coefficient can be considered as the slope of a straight line connecting the 2500\AA and $2keV$ luminosities. It is found to be anticorrelated with $L(2500\text{\AA})$ over a broad range (see Fig. 1.12), indicating that for increasing accretion rate the X-ray production is reduced. Several

hypothesis have been put forth to explain this trend (see discussion in Martocchia et al., 2017 and references therein). One possibility is that the evolution from radiation- to advection-driven accretion disc also affects the strength of the Comptonising X-ray corona, resulting in an under-production of X-ray photons at high accretion rates. In this sense, an extreme possibility could be that envisaged by Proga (2005), i.e. that at high luminosity/accretion rates the UV flux is capable to drive an outflow towards the coronal region, making it cooler and denser and then reducing its X-ray production rate. Interestingly, from an observational point of view, some of the highest detected $L(UV)$ AGNs are X-ray weak (Nardini et al., 2019), i.e. their $L(X)$ is (even) lower than what foreseen according to the $\alpha_{OX} - L(UV)$ relation (Pu et al., 2020), lending support toward a strong disc-corona coupling at extreme accretion rates. In a significant fraction of these sources, strong winds at nuclear scales are also observed in the optical-UV band (Martocchia et al., 2017; Zappacosta et al., 2020) and in the X-rays (Laurenti et al., 2020). Such weakness seems to be intrinsic, since $L(X)$ remains faint even after accounting for the wind absorption.

1.3 Outflows in the X-ray band

1.3.1 Warm Absorbers

Since the first observations with the X-ray satellite *ASCA*, layer of absorbing gas are routinely detected in around 50% of the local AGNs (Reynolds, 1997; Piconcelli et al., 2005; Tombesi et al., 2013). Their ionisation state can be various, from nearly neutral to hydrogenic for medium-Z elements, and so they are commonly referred to as "Warm Absorbers". Velocity of warm absorbers can be measured through the Doppler shift of the absorption and emission features with respect to the host galaxy redshift, and is typically of the order of $v \approx 100 - 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Laha et al., 2014, 2016). From now on, we adopt the convention for which a positive velocity indicates a blueshift of the atomic feature, corresponding to a motion of the gas outward from the nucleus and towards the observer (i.e., an outflow). Conversely, a redshift represents an inflowing gas and it is denoted with negative velocity. Informations about the gas dynamics can be obtained by assuming the WAs to be in photoionisation equilibrium with the central UV and X-ray continuum luminosity, that is, its ionisation status is determined by the radiation rather than collisions and it is in a equilibrium configuration. In this case, its ionisation status is described by the ionisation parameter ξ , built as the ratio between the ionising photon flux and the gas surface density. Hereafter, we define ξ according to Tarter et al. (1969), i.e. $\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{nr^2}$, where L_{ion} is the "ionising" luminosity at energies higher than the H ionisation threshold (13.6eV) and up to 13.6keV, and r, n are the wind distance from the SMBH and its number density at r , respectively. The typical values of ξ span 4 orders of magnitude, from 10^{-1} to $10^3 \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$.

One of the best example WA spectrum is that of the Seyfert-I galaxy NGC3783 from Kaspi et al. (2002), obtained with a 900 *ks* *Chandra* observations using the high energy grating (HETG). We show it on Fig. 1.13. A wealth of absorption and emission lines is clearly visible, with the most prominent ones belonging to H-like and He-like ions (i.e., ions with only 1 or 2 bound electrons left) of N, O, Ne, Mg, Al, Si and S. Further structures belonging to Fe (the heaviest of the detected elements) are visible, although with variable significance, mainly from the 2nd and 3rd electronic shells (L and M, respectively), associated to a ionic range from Fe XVII to Fe XXIV (i.e., from 10 to 3 bounds electrons left). A total of 135 absorption features is detected, of which 42 are unblended and with a significant S/N. The mean outflow velocity is $\approx 600 \text{ km/s}$, however there is tentative evidence for a two- (or possibly three-) velocity outflow. Interestingly, these velocities are in agreement with the three layers observed in a previous UV spectrum of the same source (Kraemer et al., 2001), raising the possibility of a common origin/evolution.

While L_{ion} can be determined from the absorption-corrected X-ray spectrum, an additional determination is necessary in order to break the nr^2 degeneracy. Estimates for r can be built from v using virial (i.e., escape velocity) arguments, obtaining typical values between 1-100 pc , i.e. at BLR/NLR scales. However, in some cases is it possible to directly determine n , e.g. by observing the response of ξ to a change of the ionising flux in highly-variable AGNs (Behar et al., 2003; Krongold et al., 2007). This way, it is possible to derive r from the definition of ξ . Interestingly, these values differs significantly from the previous estimates. We report in Fig. 1.14 a sketch of the WA geometry for NGC4051 from Krongold et al. (2007), where the high- and low-ionisation phases are located at 0.5-1.0 light-days (2000-4000 R_S) and < 3.5 light-days ($< 16000 R_S$) from the luminosity source, respectively. These distance put the WA well within the AGN torus, since in this source the dust sublimation radius can be estimated an order of magnitude farther. Therefore, this WA must have been launched and accelerated from the accretion disc, hinting to a possible accretion-ejection interplay.

The third important parameter to characterise WA observational appearance is the column density, defined as the integrated gas number density along the line of sight: $N_H = \int_{LOS} n(r) dr$. It represents a proxy of the total wind mass, that can be calculated using N_H and a measurement of the outflow extension perpendicularly to the LOS. The observed column densities for WAs are in the range $N_H = 10^{20} - 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Interestingly, ξ and N_H can be combined to get hints on the density distribution of the flow along the LOS. The so-called Absorption Measure Distribution, first defined by Holczer et al. (2007) is a differential measure: $AMD = |dN_H/d \log(\xi)|$. It aims at describing the (column) density distribution over the range of ionisation of the flow, derived from the opacities of different ions of a given element. In order to perform a meaningful AMD measurement, the source must have both high quality X-ray spectra and a sufficient broad ionisation range. As an example, the IRAS 13349+2438 spectrum in Holczer et al. (2007) spans

Figure 1.13: The 900 *ks* Chandra grating spectrum of NGC3783. Top panel shows the broad 0.5-9 *keV* observed spectrum, while in the bottom ones the datapoints are reported with higher detail as a function of the wavelength. Each bin is reported with its 1σ uncertainty. Absorption lines from H-like and He-like ions are marked in red and blue, respectively, while lower ionisation ones are in green. The lines are marked at their expected rest frame wavelengths, highlighting the blueshift of the observed features. From Kaspi et al. (2002).

Figure 1.14: The locations of the high- and low-ionisation phases (HIP and LIP, respectively) of the WA in NGC4051. Also shown are the inferred locations of the $H\beta$ and He II Broad Emission Line Regions (BELR) and of the dusty molecular torus. From Krongold et al. (2007).

a ionisation range $-1.5 \leq \log(\xi) \leq 3.5$. Notwithstanding these requirements are not easy to meet, AMD profiles can be built for a small number of sources in the literature. Behar (2009) found flat AMD slopes for a sample of five, nearby AGNs, with values between 0 and 0.4. In the hypothesis that WAs are made by a continuous, large-scale flow, this implies a radial profile of the kind $n(r) \propto r^{-\delta}$, with $1 < \delta < 1.3$, thus ruling out both a constant density ($\delta = 0$) and a spherically symmetric ($\delta = 2$) outflow. Interestingly, this range for δ is in agreement with a magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) driving scenario for disc winds, that we will discuss in the following section. Further physical constraints can be obtained by comparing the observed AMD profiles with simulated ones, using photoionisation codes (Adhikari et al., 2019).

Due to their heterogeneous properties, a clear origin for WAs has not yet been established. Different theoretical works (see e.g. Elvis, 2000) suggest an unification picture between WAs and the fast, dense gas from the BLR observed in the optical band through a multiphase medium. The low density, hot phase is observed as WA and provides the pressure confinement for the low pressure, high density phase that is opaque in the optical-UV band and corresponds to the BLR. Eventually, NLR features can also be accommodated within this picture as the BLR counterpart at increasing distance to the SMBH and the accretion disc. However, the observational properties of the different components are not always easy to fit in a single picture. WA may also have a different origin, e.g. photoevaporated material from the inner boundary of the torus or by-products of the shock of the powerful, mildly relativistic accretion disc winds when they impact with the ambient medium (Laha et al., 2016).

1.3.2 Ultra Fast Outflows

Fig. 1.15 shows the values of ξ , N_H , v for a sample of WA from the literature. We also plot the so-called Ultra Fast Outflows (UFOs), that appear as the high energy counterpart and are observed in almost 40% of the local AGNs (Tombesi et al., 2010). Tombesi et al. (2011) estimated mean UFO values of $\log\left(\frac{\xi}{\text{erg cm s}^{-1}}\right) = 4.2$, $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $v_{out} = 0.15c$ for a sample of UFOs detected with *XMM-Newton* in nearby ($z \leq 0.1$) Seyfert 1 galaxies. They also first defined UFOs

Figure 1.15: From left to right: ξ vs. N_H ; ξ vs. v_{out} ; N_H vs. v_{out} for a sample of WAs (black points) and UFOs (green and red points) from the literature. Adapted from Serafinelli et al. (2019).

as those outflows with an observed outflow velocity $v_{out} \geq 10^4 km/s$, a definition that it is still in place today.

It is instructive to look at one of the first UFO reported in the literature, detected with *XMM-Newton* in a 60 ks observation of PG1211+143 (Pounds et al., 2003). In Fig. 1.16 we show the ratio between a power-law spectrum and the datapoints in the 1-10 keV energy band. The UFO is traced by an excess and a lack of photons, corresponding respectively to an emission and an absorption feature, at energies around 6-7 keV. These two combined components trace the absorption of the continuum X-ray radiation by the outflow and its simultaneous re-emission. The velocity shift between the peak of the two components is due to a projection effect of the wind velocity field along the line of sight (LOS). Absorption is detected only along the LOS, while emission is received from all over the wind.

To a good degree of approximation, the outflowing gas is directed radially outward, i.e. its direction of motion is parallel to the LOS. As a result, the blueshift of the absorption features is the highest possible and correspond to the outflowing velocity v_{out} . The velocity field observed in emission, instead, is given by the projection of v_{out} averaged over the entire wind volume. As a result, the peak of the emission feature is characterised by a lower energy than the absorption one, since the average projected velocity will be, in general, lower than the absorption v_{out} . This kind of profile is called P-Cygni and encodes a wealth of information on the outflowing wind. We will discuss it in detail in Sect. 2.

In Fig. 1.17 two different spectral fits of PG1211 are presented. In panel a), the absorption through is fitted with an inverted Gaussian profile. The best fit line energy, once corrected for the galaxy redshift, is $7.63 \pm 0.02 keV$, and its 1σ width is $100 \pm 30 eV$. If ascribed to one of the two strongest nearby lines, i.e. Fe XXV $He - \alpha$ or Fe XXVI $Ly - \alpha$ (6.70 and 6.97 keV rest energy,

Figure 1.16: The X-ray spectrum of PG 1211+143 observed with XMM-Newton: ratio between the datapoints and a power-law continuum. Wind features are clearly visible around 7 keV. From Pounds et al. (2003).

Figure 1.17: Left: same of Fig. 1.16, now including an inverted Gaussian profile to account for the wind absorption. Right: the best fit model calculated with the XSTAR photoionisation code. From Pounds et al. (2003).

respectively), implies $v_{out} = 0.122 \pm 0.005, 0.095 \pm 0.005c$ in the two cases. A more detailed assessment of the UFO features can, instead, be performed through a photoionisation modelling of the absorption features, e.g. using the XSTAR code (Kallman & Bautista, 2001), as showed in panel b). The absorption features are best fitted with a mixture of different, slightly lower energetic inner-shell features, implying a higher $v_{out} = 0.149 \pm 0.003c$. An interesting lesson

can be gained by visually inspecting the best fit model. It can be seen that i) gaussian profiles are not, in general, an exact description of the actual absorption pattern, even if they may be sufficient given the limited energy resolution of the datapoints and ii) photoionisation edges, as well as overlapping absorption lines, may alter the continuum profile of the spectrum, as can be noted blueward of the absorption complex at $E \geq 8 \text{ keV}$ and especially above 9 keV . This latter point is particularly important when also wind emission and/or additional spectral complexities at $1\text{-}2 \text{ keV}$ are present, such as WAs or a soft excess. In these cases, indeed, the estimate of the underlying power-law index may turn out to be a non trivial task. This, in turn, make a solid assessment of the outflow features more difficult.

As an example of the complexity of the observed spectra, we show in Fig. 1.18, upper panel, the prototypical P-Cygni from the UFO in PDS 456 observed simultaneously with *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* (Nardini et al., 2015). The power-law continuum is plotted with a red curve and a phenomenological model for the absorption/emission in light green. As already discussed for the absorption, a Gaussian line is inadequate to precisely describe the wind emission, too, which appears to be asymmetric and skewed redward. In lower panel we show the detailed $0.5\text{-}40 \text{ keV}$ best fit model, obtained from the composition of several spectral component. The total wind spectrum (black curve) is the result of two different layers of absorption: a total covering absorption by the UFO and, at higher distance, a partial covering by a cold absorber with covering factor C_f . Red curve represents the C_f fraction of the continuum flux absorbed by both the UFO and the cold absorber, while the blue one corresponds to the remainder $1 - C_f$ fraction absorbed only by the UFO. Finally, UFO emission is shown in green.

We also note here that the high average $\log(\xi) \approx 4$ implies that most of the UFOs features are due to *Fe*, one of the few elements massive enough not to be completely ionised (and the most cosmically abundant one). *FeXXV* and *FeXXVI* ions reach their maximum fractional abundance (i.e., most of the Fe atoms are in those ionisation status) for $\log(\xi) = 4, 5$, respectively (Kallman et al., 2004). Therefore, there is the possibility that some UFO are fully ionised, hence undetectable, and become observable only when the AGN ionising luminosity (and, then, the ionisation parameter) falls. Interestingly, Parker et al. (2017) suggests this scenario to explain the UFO variability in IRAS 13224-3809.

The resolution of UFO spectra is hampered by two main factor. First, they are usually detected through highly ionised Fe features, with typical rest frame energies above 6 keV , where the instrumental response and the effective area of X-ray telescopes is strongly reduced with respect to the soft X-ray band ($0.5\text{-}3 \text{ keV}$, see e.g. Jansen et al., 2001 for *XMM-Newton*). Secondly, as we will discuss in the following Section, powerful UFOs are typically observed in luminous AGNs which are predominantly at $z > 0.1$. This implies low X-ray fluxes, which lead to (even in the best cases) limited quality spectra and UFO parameters are therefore derived from

Figure 1.18: The X-ray spectrum of the quasar PDS 456. Top panel: black and blue points refer to *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* datasets, respectively. Red line represents a power-law continuum, with a superimposed P-Cygni component (light green). Bottom panel: the total best fit model (black lines) and the different spectral components (coloured lines, see text). Adapted from Nardini et al. (2015).

low-resolution CCD spectra.

The location of the UFOs, and precisely their distance r_0 from the SMBH, is of difficult determination. As for the WAs, given the difficulty to probe r_0 in a direct way, minimum and maximum estimates, r_{min}, r_{max} , are usually built in the following way. The lower limit can be derived from the radius at which v_{out} equals the escape velocity, i.e. $r_0 \geq r_{min} = 2GM_{BH}/v_{out}^2$. r_{max} , instead, can be calculated from the definition of ξ and approximating the outflow as geometrically thin, so that $N_H \approx n_0(r_1 - r_0) \approx n_0 r_0$. This way, we obtain $r_0 \leq r_{max} = L_{ion}/\xi N_H$ (Tombesi et al., 2013). Otherwise, it is also possible to constrain r_0 from the time lag with which the UFO ionisation status responds to changes in the illuminating ionising continuum, as done e.g. for PDS456 (Nardini et al., 2015) and IRAS13224 (Parker et al., 2017). Albeit with some initial assumptions, photoionisation models can also put constraints on the UFO launching radii (Fukumura et al., 2018; Laurenti et al., 2020). In all these cases, for the majority of UFO sources the derived r_0 is found to lie in a range from ≈ 50 to some hundreds r_G , much closer than for WAs, as expected given their higher ξ and v . This finding clearly indicates that UFOs must originate from the innermost part of the accretion disc, suggesting an intimate link between accretion and ejection. While spiralling toward the SMBH, part of the accreting gas is pushed out of the disc and then accelerated outward, even though there is still not a firm consensus on the acceleration mechanisms. As we will discuss in the Sect. 2.1, the two main suggested drivers are radiation pressure and magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) force.

Two quantities are widely used to assess the energetics of UFOs: the mass and kinetic energy outflow rates, $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$, respectively. \dot{M}_{out} is usually expressed in $M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (solar masses per year), and represents the amount of mass transported by the UFO. A first-order formula for \dot{M}_{out} widely adopted in the literature is that in Crenshaw & Kraemer (2012):

$$\dot{M}_{out} = 4\pi r_0 N_H \mu m_p C_f v_{out} \quad (1.5)$$

with μ the mean atomic mass per proton (≈ 1.2 , Gofford et al., 2015), m_p the proton mass, and C_f the wind covering factor, defined as the fraction of the solid angle covered by the UFO. Together with r_0 , C_f is the most difficult parameter to determine observationally. For those (few) cases in which UFO emission is observed, C_f is derived from the ratio between the equivalent width of emission and absorption components. Otherwise, it is estimated from the fraction of UFO-detected sources among the Seyfert-I population, or it is left as a free parameter. From \dot{M}_{out} and v_{out} , it is possible to estimate $\dot{E}_{out} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{M}_{out} v_{out}^2$.

Fig. 1.19, from Fiore et al. (2017) shows $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$ (left and right panels, respectively) for a large sample of UFOs, indicated with large red stars, and WAs, denoted with smaller stars. Both quantities appear to be tightly correlated with the AGN bolometric luminosity L_{bol} , suggesting

Figure 1.19: Left panel: \dot{M}_{out} as a function of L_{bol} for a sample of outflows from the literature observed at different scales from the SMBH. Blue, green, black and red points indicate molecular, ionised, BAL and X-ray outflows, respectively. Specifically, red small stars corresponds to WA, while larger stars, square, triangle and filled circle to UFOs. Right panel: same as before, but for \dot{E}_{out} . From Fiore et al. (2017).

that, at least in a subset of AGNs, UFOs are a systemic component, closely linked with accretion itself. WAs do not seem to share the same trend, casting doubts on a possible common origin of these two populations. UFOs E_{out} are between 1% and 100% the host AGN bolometric luminosity L_{bol} (dotted and dashed line, respectively). According to theoretical works, a value of some percent (from $\approx 0.5\%$ to 5% , see e.g. Di Matteo et al., 2005; Hopkins & Elvis, 2010) is enough to trigger a galactic-wide outflow, with dramatic consequences on the galaxy evolution and ultimately driving its transition from a gas-rich, star-forming system to a red and dead system, in which the gas has been made unavailable to form new stars. As we will discuss in the following Section, this may be achieved in different ways, either by sweeping the gas from the centre of the galaxy, by prompting a burst in star formation through increased ambient pressure or by heating the available gas, thus preventing its collapse, especially in galaxy clusters (see e.g. Fabian, 2012; Cresci et al., 2015; Fiore et al., 2017 and references therein).

1.4 Galaxy-scale outflows and feedback

Beside X-ray outflows, in Fig. 1.19 we also show the galactic-scale winds in the ionised and molecular phases (green and blue points, respectively). These outflows, observed from the optical to the IR band, have lower velocities with respect to the UFO ones (with maximum values of 10^3 km/s) but far higher \dot{m}_{out} , up to $10^4 M_{\odot}$. This mass outflow rate is found to be systematically

higher than the star formation rate, indicating that its driving force cannot be explained through galactic stellar activity alone, but instead must come from the AGN. In those cases in which the host galaxy can be resolved observationally (also thanks to interferometric measurements, e.g. with ALMA and NOEMA in the IR band), the outflow morphology is usually spherical or elliptical/biconical, in agreement with an origin from the central AGN (see e.g. Cicone et al., 2014; Feruglio et al., 2015; Cresci et al., 2015 and Menci et al., 2019 for a theoretical perspective). Interestingly, for the ionised phase a correspondence has also been observed between its major axis and that of the radio emission, when present (Rupke & Veilleux, 2013; Harrison et al., 2014).

Growing theoretical and observational evidences show that these winds may represent the galaxy-scale counterpart of the UFOs, as a result of their interaction with the ambient ISM that reduces v_{out} and increase the amount of matter embedded in the outflow, i.e. \dot{m}_{out} (Tombesi et al., 2015). This hypothesis is further supported by the properties of BAL winds, that indeed share intermediate properties between these two extremes. They are observed in $\approx 15\%$ of optically-selected AGNs through blueshifted optical/UV lines (C IV, Si IV, N V), with $\dot{m}_{out} = 100 - 10^3 M_{\odot}/yr$ and $v_{out} = 10^3 - 10^4 km/s (= 0.003 - 0.03c)$, with the fastest ones reaching $0.15-0.3 c$ (Hamann et al., 2018; Bruni et al., 2019). Their location is not tightly constrained and is estimated at nuclear scales, between 1 and 100 pc (see discussion in Bruni et al., 2019 and references therein). Interestingly, UFO and BAL absorption features have been both detected in some sources, and their properties seem to be in agreement with a common origin for the X-ray and UV gas phases; see e.g. Danehkar et al. (2018a); Kriss et al. (2018a) for the simultaneous *Hubble Space Telescope (HST)* - *Chandra* observation of the Quasar PG1211+143, Hamann et al. (2018) for a (tentative) detection of a $0.3c$ UV outflow in PDS456 and Kriss et al. (2019). Although the results are still limited to some single sources they show the importance of a comprehensive analysis of the high-energy end of the electromagnetic spectrum to trace the journey of nuclear winds and their evolution from the high-energy, small scale end (represented by UFO) to the optical/UV regime (Giustini et al., 2011). However, we also note that Kriss et al. (2018b) undertook a broad archival search for UV features in *FUSE* and *HST* spectra for 16 sources with detected UFOs, but were able to establish only upper limits for the UV absorbing columns. BLR winds also show intermediate properties and may represent an intermediate phase between nuclear, UFO-like winds and galaxy-scale outflows (Vietri et al., 2018, 2020). We present a composite view of the outflows at the different scales in Fig. 1.20 (from Cicone et al., 2018). Increasing spatial scales are presented in panels from a to c, from accretion disc scales up to the boundaries of the galaxy. Accordingly, panel d shows the *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* joint spectrum of PDS 456 from Nardini et al. (2015) (see also Section 1.3 and Fig. 1.18); panel e reports the outflow in Mrk 231, observed at scales of hundred of parsecs through neutral atomic and molecular transitions (Morganti et al., 2016 and Cicone et al., 2012, respectively); finally,

panel f reports the ionised wind in NGC1365 over a few kiloparsecs (Venturi et al., 2017).

In order to quantitatively explore this scenario, it is instructive to compare the energy liberated by the accretion process during the AGN lifetime with that of the host galaxy bulge:

$$E_{out} = \eta M_{BH} c^2 = 0.1 M_{BH} c^2 \quad (1.6)$$

where we assume for simplicity that most of the SMBH mass comes directly from accretion (Soltan, 1982; Pezzulli et al., 2016) and we fix $\eta = 0.1$, as for a Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973 thin accretion disc (see Section 1.2). On the other hand, the galaxy bulge binding energy is shaped by its velocity dispersion σ and can be written as:

$$E_{bulge} = M_* \sigma^2 \approx 10^{-6} M_{gal} c^2 \sigma_{300}^2 \quad (1.7)$$

where M_* , σ_{300} are the bulge mass and σ in units of 300 km/s, respectively. If we approximate $M_* = 10^3 M_{BH}$ (see Fig. 1.21, left panel), we get (King & Pounds, 2015):

$$E_{out} = \eta \cdot 10^{-3} M_* c^2 = 10^{-4} M_* c^2 \approx 100 E_{bulge} \quad (1.8)$$

This result implies that the energy released during the accretion could, in principle, "unbind" the host galaxy bulge, provided there is an efficient channel to communicate this energy to the environment. More realistically, we expect that AGN and host galaxy "knows" each other, and hence their evolution is somehow correlated. This process is what is usually called *coevolution*. Up to now there are several observational "hints" for AGN-host galaxy coevolution (see review by Kormendy & Ho, 2013 and Fiore et al., 2017 and references therein). The first one consists in the correlation between the SMBH mass and a number of properties of the host galaxy bulge, namely its mass, luminosity and velocity dispersion σ , with $M_{bh} - \sigma$ being the driving relation, see Fig. 1.21, right panel (e.g. King & Pounds, 2015; Shankar et al., 2016, 2019). It must be noted, however, that these relations are affected by the complex evolutionary history of the galaxy and the SMBH assembly, including mergers, secular instabilities and the influence of the galaxy cluster. Several results suggest that similar M_{BH} -bulge relations can be simply obtained if SMBH and bulges formed simultaneously, without a direct interaction between them (Menci et al., 2003). Peng et al. (2010); Jahnke & Macciò (2011) showed that galaxy mergers are able to drive the values of M_{BH} , M_* , making them converge toward a narrow correlation, even starting from an initial arbitrary distribution.

A more promising approach is to look at "derivative" quantities, such as the cosmological evolution of SMBH and the luminosity density of galaxies. A correspondence has indeed been found between AGN and galactic activity as a function of redshift (dubbed "downsizing", Boyle

Figure 1.20: A schematic representation of the different outflow scales, from accretion disc to the surrounding ISM and to the boundaries of the galaxy (panels a-c). Panels d, e, f report the spectra of the UFO in PDS 456, the neutral outflow in Mrk 231 and the ionised wind at kiloparsec scales in NGC 1365, respectively. See text for the references. From Cicone et al. (2018).

& Terlevich, 1998; Silverman et al., 2008; Brandt & Alexander, 2015), possibly driven by the AGN feedback toward its host galaxy. Moreover, in the modelling of galaxy evolution the star formation rate (SFR) derived from the standard Λ CDM scenario is systematically overestimated with respect to the observations for a broad range of galaxy masses, as reported in Fig. 1.22 (see review by Harrison, 2017 and references therein). For galaxy masses $M_{gal} \leq 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ the discrepancy can be solved considering the feedback from the star formation itself, including supernovae explosions, which cleans the surrounding environment from the fresh gas. Instead, for $M_{gal} > 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ stellar feedback is not sufficient, and AGN-driven outflows represent the best candidate (Cicone et al., 2014; Bongiorno et al., 2016; Fontanot et al., 2020).

As shown in Eq. 1.7, accretion energy is higher than the binding energy of the host bulge. On the other hand, UFOs have kinetic outflow rates between 0.01- 1 times the AGN luminosity. Therefore, they represent a perfect candidate to communicate the AGN energy outward. The fate of this transmission will depend on the efficiency of the coupling with the host environment.

From a theoretical point of view, the transmission is expected to take place in a first inefficient phase and to evolve later in a highly efficient one (Faucher-Giguère & Quataert, 2012; King & Pounds, 2015; Menci et al., 2019; Costa et al., 2020). The impact of the outflow with the interstellar matter (ISM) will produce a first (backward) shock front, given the high UFO velocity. After this, the expanding ISM will drive a second (frontward) shock against rest-frame ISM. The

Figure 1.21: Scaling relations between M_{BH} (y-axis) and the mass of the bulge, M_* (x-axis, left panel) and the bulge velocity dispersion σ_e (x-axis, right panel). Solid line and shaded region represent the least-squares fit and the associated 1σ uncertainty. Red points indicate galaxy bulges, black ones elliptical galaxies. Adapted from Kormendy & Ho (2013).

ex-UFO and the accelerated ISM shocked regions are separated by a contact discontinuity, conserving both momentum and pressure. We show in Fig. 1.23 a cartoon of the shock fronts. Gas temperature after the first shock is $T_s \approx 10^{10} - 10^{11} K$ (Faucher-Giguère & Quataert, 2012), while the AGN radiation field has $T_{AGN} \approx 10^7 K$. Given its high ionisation status, the gas is cooled predominantly via inverse Compton with cooling time t_{cool} . On the other hand, the wind propagation timescale can be estimated as $t_{prop} = R_s/v_s$, where R_s, v_s are the inward shock radius and the shocked wind velocity, respectively. Therefore, the wind will be efficiently cooled only if $t_{cool} > t_{prop}$: the post shock thermal energy will be "irradiated" away and only the wind ram pressure ($\propto \dot{M}_{out} \cdot v$) will be conserved. In this momentum-conserving phase (top cartoon in Fig. 1.23) the shell is geometrically narrow and the coupling between nuclear wind and ambient ISM is relatively inefficient. When $t_{cool} < t_{prop}$, instead, the shocked flow conserves its energy and expands adiabatically in an energy-conserving phase (bottom cartoon). Here the coupling is highly efficient and the outflowing gas is energetic enough to expand to galactic scales.

The separation between the two phases is given by a "cooling radius" R_C (King & Pounds, 2015). Since the photon density goes approximately as R^{-2} , $t_{cool} \propto R^2$. On the other hand,

Figure 1.22: Impact of star formation (SF) and AGN feedback on the host galaxy. The plot represents the ratio between stellar mass in the galactic halo and the halo total mass M_h (y-axis), as a function of M_h (x-axis, in units of M_\odot). The three scattered lines represent three galaxy simulation runs with different feedback prescriptions (see legend); in particular, the black one incorporates both SF and AGN feedback and best matches the empirical trend (gray continuous line). Shaded area indicates the 1σ uncertainty associated to the black line. Adapted from Harrison (2017).

Figure 1.23: Shock regions in the momentum- and energy-conserving cases (top and bottom cartoons, respectively). From King & Pounds (2015).

propagation timescale is proportional to the radius. $t_{prop} \propto R$, provided that v_s remains approximately constant. Hence, the shock is efficiently cooled only if it is close enough to the nucleus, $R < R_C$. Assuming an isothermal distribution for the ISM and that $L_{bol} = L_{Edd}$, it is possible to derive the cooling radius as:

$$R_C = 500 M_8^{1/2} \sigma_{200} p c \quad (1.9)$$

In the momentum-conserving regime, shock region is almost constant and confined to $R < R_C$, until M_{BH} reaches a critical value. The latter corresponds to $M_\sigma \equiv \frac{f_g \sigma_T}{m_p \pi G^2} \sigma^4$, where f_g , σ_T , m_p , G are the gas fraction with respect to the total bulge mass, Thompson cross-section, proton mass and Gravitational constant, respectively. Interestingly, the $M_{BH} - \sigma$ relation in Fig. 1.21 is best-fitted by $M_{BH} = 3 M_8 \cdot \sigma_{200}^{4.4}$, thus showing a similar dependence on σ with M_σ .

After M_{BH} reaches M_σ , the outflow is powerful enough to push the shock front farther until $R > R_C$. This way, it enters the energy-conserving phase, and the post shock region expands into the host bulge sweeping away its gas. During this expansion the outflow is traced by the ionised and molecular phases, which indeed are observed at galaxy scales. As discussed in Sect. 1.3, these outflows have velocities far lower than UFO ones, and their ratio can be estimated as

$\frac{v_{UFO}}{v_{gal}} \approx \frac{1000 \text{ km/s}}{0.15c} = 50$, where v_{gal} is the characteristic ionised and molecular outflow velocity from Fig. 1.19 and the average UFO velocity v_{UFO} is from Tombesi et al. (2010) (see Section 1.3). In the energy-conserving phase the post shock energy rate must be equal to the pre-shock one:

$$\dot{E}_{shock} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{m}_{shock} v_s^2 = \frac{1}{2} \dot{M}_{out} v_{UFO}^2 \quad (1.10)$$

However, since $v_{gal} \ll v_{UFO}$, the post-shock momentum rate \dot{m}_{shock} must be far higher than the UFO \dot{M}_{out} :

$$\dot{m}_{shock} = \dot{M}_{out} \left(\frac{v_{UFO}}{v_s} \right)^2 \approx \dot{M}_{out} \cdot 2500 \quad (1.11)$$

remarkably, this relation shows a qualitative agreement with the outflow properties described above. Thanks to this "momentum boost", galaxy scale winds are massive enough to exert a significant feedback onto the host galaxy and alter the equilibrium of its reservoir gas.

Unfortunately, up to now it has been possible to simultaneously probe both nuclear- and galactic-scale outflows in a handful of AGNs only. The majority of them shows a coupling efficiency between nuclear- and galaxy-scale intermediate between the momentum- and energy-conserving phases (Feruglio et al., 2015; Nardini et al., 2015; Tombesi et al., 2015; Nardini & Zubovas, 2018; Bischetti et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2019). We show in Fig. 1.24 the momentum ratio between UFO- and galaxy-scales outflow for these sources. Most of them show a limited enhancement of their large-scale component, indicating a limited coupling efficiency. This suggests that the two phases model is a schematic representation of the outflow dynamics; nevertheless, it is able to represent the two extreme modes of propagation. Near energy-conserving regime may still be possible, depending on the detection accuracy and the assumptions made in estimating the outflows energetics (see discussion in Bischetti et al., 2019). Finally, numerical simulations by Torrey et al. (2020) show that energy driven outflows may display apparent momentum boosts even below unity, depending on how galaxy-scale momentum is defined and, particularly, which threshold velocity is adopted to distinguish the outflow from the ISM gas at rest, which is characterised by the typical galaxy dispersion velocity.

Figure 1.24: Ratio between the galaxy-scale and the nuclear outflow momentum rates for several quasars hosting UFOs, ordered by increasing L_{bol} . Measurements for individual galaxies are shown as squares, circles and diamonds for ionised, molecular and atomic outflows respectively. Horizontal dashed line represents momentum conservation ($\dot{p}_{out}/\dot{p}_{UFO} = 1$), while orange rectangles show the predictions for energy conservation. $\text{H}\alpha$ and [O III] outflows for MR2251-1778 and PG 1126-041 are shown with filled and empty symbols, respectively. From Marasco et al. (2020).

2. Theoretical and numerical modelling of accretion disc winds

2.1 Theoretical picture

The dynamics of the accretion disc winds can be expressed through the momentum equation for a fluid (Proga, 2007):

$$\rho \frac{D\vec{v}}{Dt} + \rho \nabla \phi = -\nabla P + \frac{1}{4\pi} (\nabla \times \vec{B}) \times \vec{B} + \rho \vec{F}^{rad} \quad (2.1)$$

where ρ , v , P , B , ϕ , F^{rad} are respectively the wind density, velocity, pressure and magnetic field, and the gravitational potential and the radiation force determined by the AGN environment. To successfully launch an outflow, one of the right-hand terms (or a combination of them) must overcome gravity. Depending on which is the dominant term, the outflow can be thermally- (i.e. guided by the gas pressure gradient ∇P), magnetically- or radiatively-driven.

2.1.1 Thermal driving

In the first case, the heating term is mainly represented by the X-ray flux from the corona that interacts with the accretion disc surface. The effectiveness of thermal launching depends on two factors: the temperature of the X-ray heated gas and the escape velocity v_{esc} , which is given by the ratio between the black hole mass M_{BH} and the radius where heating is taking place. Since systems with lower M_{BH} are characterised by a higher disc temperature, it is clear why thermal driving is expected to be more efficient for stellar-mass systems, such as X-ray binaries and ultra-luminous X-ray sources (ULXs), with temperatures $\approx 10^6 - 10^7 \text{ keV}$. It is possible to estimate a typical thermal launching radius calculating where the sound velocity equals v_{esc} (Ohsuga & Mineshige, 2014):

$$R_{th} = \frac{GM\mu}{kT_X} \approx 3 \cdot 10^5 \left(\frac{T_X}{10^7 \text{ K}} \right) R_S \quad (2.2)$$

indicating that, for typical AGN temperatures, this process is expected to be efficient at radii approximately between the BLR and the dusty torus. Interestingly, Chelouche & Netzer (2005)

were able to reproduce the low velocity features of the warm absorber in NGC 3783 (see Sect. 1.3) using a thermal driven wind. This scenario is likely to be promising for explaining outflow features in X-ray Binaries ULXs (see e.g. Tomaru et al., 2018; Pinto et al., 2020 and refs therein).

2.1.2 Radiation driving

Radiation driving is perhaps the most intuitive mechanism. It is naturally expected given the large luminosity output of AGNs, that can sometimes even exceed the Eddington value in quasars. By definition, Thompson scattering (i.e., photon scattering on free electrons) is able to counteract gravity if the source is at or above Eddington. However, radiation driving can still be effective for lower luminosities, thanks to the gas opacity to resonant lines and ionisation edges (the so-called "line driving"). The relative strength of line-driving can be quantified by the ratio between the line opacity to the electron scattering, i.e. the force multiplier M_{rad} (Castor et al., 1975). For a gas illuminated by UV radiation, M_{rad} can be as high as $\approx 2000 - 4000$. However, this ratio quickly drops to zero in presence of a strong X-ray flux, that is able to ionise most of the gas elements, leading to a small number of lines available. For $\xi \geq 10^3 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}$, the line force is negligible compared to continuum scattering (Dannen et al., 2019). Therefore, the outcome of radiative driving depends on a delicate balance between the UV and X-ray luminosities, encoded in the AGN SED and in the power-law slope in the X-ray band. One of the first hydrodynamical simulations investigating radiation launching from an AGN accretion disc was published in Proga & Kallman (2004) (but see also Proga et al., 2000). We show in Fig. 2.1 their results. They assumed an axisymmetric thin accretion disc, with the X-ray luminosity coming from a point-like source at the origin of the axes. The full set of hydrodynamic equations is solved to determine velocity and density of the gas above the disc, which is assumed to be supplied from it.

It can be seen that a successful wind develops in the equatorial region, where the gas is denser, colder and then less photoionised. As a consequence, it has high M_{rad} and can reach velocities up to $0.05c$ (last panel). A key feature is the so-called "failed wind" (FW) within $\approx 300r_S$ from the axes origin, where the X-ray flux is so intense that it easily overionises the gas. As a result, the latter is unable to successfully accelerate, leading to a stalling outflow. Thanks to its high covering factor and density (due to its proximity to the X-ray source) the FW may act as a shield, absorbing a significant fraction of the X-ray flux and preventing the overionisation of the equatorial gas at higher distances. FWs are ubiquitously found in radiation driving simulations and are a fundamental element for their success (Proga et al., 2000; Nomura et al., 2016; Giustini & Proga, 2020). At higher height from the disc, the shielding of the FW is less effective and the gas is hot and rarified, with null or negative (inflowing) velocities, especially in the polar region. Radiation driving is able to reproduce both the velocity, distance and ionisation status of UV

2. Theoretical and numerical modelling of accretion disc winds

Figure 2.1: Physical structure of the Proga & Kallman (2004) model. Four squared panels, from top left to bottom right: color-coded maps of the gas density, temperature, photoionisation parameter and velocity field (see inset legends for the scale). Bottom three rectangular panels: quantities at the the outer boundary of the computational domain, as a function of the inclination θ in the altitude-radius plane (0 deg corresponds to the rotation axis and 90 deg to the accretion disc plane). Solid and dotted lines refer to the vertical axis on the left and on the right, respectively. In all the panels the spatial scale is in units of $r_* = 3r_S$.

Figure 2.2: Left panel shows the original ionisation parameter distribution in Proga & Kallman (2004). Right panel shows the distribution after the ray-tracing post-processing done in Higginbottom et al. (2014). The shielding from the inner FW is considerably reduced. For the SED assumed in this work, the parameter U is linked to ξ as $\log(U) = \log(\xi) - 1.75$. Adapted from Higginbottom et al., 2014

outflows, such as BALs and BLR outflows.

However, due to the extensive computational power required and the complicated physics behind accretion and ejection flows, these results are based on several assumptions, that make a comparison with observations less immediate. First, the disc structure is assumed, rather than being solved numerically, but this is not expected to be crucial since the accretion disc configurations are quite well settled in the literature (see Sect. 1.2.1). On the other hand, the introduction of Compton scattering significantly hampers the FW shielding, since scattered photons are able to "circumvent" the FW region and ionise gas located at higher radii, thanks to their "random walk". This has been shown in Higginbottom et al. (2014), as shown in Fig. 2.2. The original ionisation pattern from Proga & Kallman (2004) is plotted in the left panel, while in the right one it is shown the post-processed result to account for the random walk scattering. This finding significantly questions the shielding role of the putative FW. Moreover, strong X-ray absorption is not systematically observed in sources hosting optical/UV outflows, which instead seem to be partially associated with intrinsically X-ray weak emission (see Sect. 1.2.2 and Hamann et al., 2013; Zappacosta et al., 2020 and references therein).

These findings suggest that radiative driving can act with a certain efficiency only at a sufficient large distance from the X-ray Corona, i.e. at BLR-like distances, farther than the typical UFO launching locations $\sim 100r_S$. In this regard, we note that a number of models successfully reproduced UV features through funnel-shaped outflows arising from the accretion disc (from hundreds to thousands of r_S) and expanding outward (Higginbottom et al., 2013; Matthews et al., 2020).

2.1.3 Magnetic Driving

Given the high-ionisation, high-temperature plasma, magnetic fields are probably ubiquitous in the innermost part of accretion discs. As discussed in Sect. 1.2.1, they are also invoked to explain the α viscosity prescription through Magneto-Rotational Instabilities. A large-scale, ordered magnetic field anchored (and co-rotating) with the disc could efficiently channel a mass outflow from the disc itself. The disc rotational velocity is usually proportional to the Keplerian value, $v_{rot} \propto v_{kep} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R_0}}$, where v_{rot}, R_0 are in units of c and gravitational radii, respectively. Therefore, a co-moving magnetic field may easily reach relativistic velocities, and the gas transported along with it is immune from any overionisation or insufficient radiation drag problem. In analogy with the accretion disc structure, the field is usually assumed axisymmetric, with a poloidal and a toroidal component, B_p, B_ϕ . They are represented separately in Fig. 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Left panel: poloidal component B_p . Right panel: toroidal component B_ϕ . From Ohsuga & Mineshige (2014).

Blandford & Payne (1982) were among the firsts to analyse magnetic driving in detail. They concentrated on the B_p component, and demonstrated that a wind can be effectively launched provided that the field lines form an angle smaller than than 60 deg from the disc plane. They assume a perfect magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) fluid (i.e., with null resistivity), which then follows the field lines as beads on a wire. Thanks to the field corotation with the disc, the fluid conserves its specific angular velocity v_{ang} . The constraint on the line inclination ensures they provide enough centrifugal acceleration to the fluid, driving it at higher radii (see Fig. 2.3, left panel), where the corresponding rotational velocity is now smaller than v_{ang} . As a result, the fluid is pushed outward, giving rise to an outflow. Within this scenario, the gas acceleration is due to the magnetic tension.

However, a flow can be effectively accelerated also through the B_ϕ component, thanks to the gradient of magnetic pressure between adjacent field lines. The magnetic field intensity

Figure 2.4: Trajectories of test particles embedded in a magnetic field from a general relativistic 3-D MHD simulation. Test particles are generated from a sphere centred on the black hole with a radius of $80 r_G$. The inflow concentrates around the equatorial plane, while the outflows are evident at higher inclinations and perpendicularly to the plane. From Yuan et al. (2015).

decreases with increasing altitude from the disc plane and with increasing disc radius. The pressure gradient drives the gas accordingly, both along the rotation axis and close to the disc along the equatorial region. In the former case, magnetic pressure can give rise to collimated streams with jet-like velocities, while in the latter large-scale outflows with higher mass flux and lower velocities form (Kato et al., 2004; Yuan et al., 2015). We show a snapshot of an ideal, general relativistic 3-D MHD simulation from Yuan et al. (2015) in Fig. 2.4, where it can be seen that the two phases (tension- and pressure-dominated) are mixed in a continuous flow, from the rotation axis up to the equatorial region. The test particles are generated in a ring at $80r_G$ from the black hole, therefore the accreting matter is in the form of a thin ring rather than a distributed accretion disc, but in any case it is tightly confined around the plane of rotation.

It is possible to unify both directions in a single scenario, as done in Cui & Yuan (2020). The governing parameter is the mass loading factor μ : light (low mass) and fast winds develop mainly along B_p , while slower, highly massive winds are driven by B_ϕ . The flow trajectory is

obtained by solving the conservation equations and, particularly, by requiring a smooth transit over the three critical points, i.e., from the innermost to the outermost, the slow magnetosonic, the Alfvén and the fast magnetosonic ones. These points trace the acceleration of the gas, since they correspond to increasing wind velocities. The slow magnetosonic velocity $v_{m,s}$ is given by the thermal pressure speed (sound speed c_s) and the magnetic pressure speed v_A when they are in destructive resonance. The Alfvén velocity corresponds to v_A and it is due to the magnetic pressure speed alone (i.e. when pressure-density perturbations are orthogonal to the magnetic field ones). Finally, the fast magnetosonic velocity $v_{m,f}$ is the constructive resonance of c_s and v_A .

The terminal velocity of the wind along the poloidal direction can be written as:

$$v_p^\infty = v_0 \mu^{-1/3} = v_0 \left(\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{R_A}{R_0} \right)^2 - 1 \right)^{1/2} \quad (2.3)$$

where $v_0 = v(r = R_0)$ is the wind velocity (i.e. the magnetic field velocity) at the footpoint, the point where the field line crosses the accretion disc plane, and usually $v_0 \approx v_{rot}$. Therefore, the magnetic acceleration, i.e. the ratio between v_0 and v_p^∞ , depends almost linearly from the ratio between the R_A , the radius of the Alfvén point, and R_0 . This ratio is regulated by μ and can be written as:

$$\frac{R_A}{R_0} = \left(\frac{3}{2} (1 + \mu^{-2/3}) \right)^{1/2} \quad (2.4)$$

Therefore, for $\mu \rightarrow 0$, $\frac{R_A}{R_0} \rightarrow \infty$ and v_p^∞ can attain a virtually infinite velocity (this treatment is carried on in classical, non-relativistic framework). On the other hand, for $\mu \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{R_A}{R_0} \rightarrow (\frac{3}{2})^{1/2}$ and $v_p^\infty \rightarrow 0$. The ratio between B_ϕ and B_p can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{B_\phi}{B_p} \right)_{R=R_A} \approx \begin{cases} (19/8)^{1/2} & (\mu \ll 1) \\ 1.14\mu & (\mu \gg 1) \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

where, again, μ is the driving term. Poloidal and toroidal velocities, v_p, v_ϕ for a set of starting conditions in agreement with Seyfert- and quasar-like accretion discs are shown as a function of R in Fig. 2.5. Alfvén and fast magnetosonic points are represented with dots and triangles, respectively, while different curves refer to different magnetic field strengths, parametrised by the ratio between B_p and wind density at the footpoint $v_{Ap0} = B_{p0} / \sqrt{4\pi\rho_0}$. It can be seen that after the Alfvén radius, the velocity is almost entirely converted along the poloidal direction and settles to constant values, of the order of the starting rotational velocities v_0 . Increasing values of v_{Ap0} result in higher v_p, v_ϕ , as expected.

Magnetic wind models have been built by solving the Grad-Shafranov equation, which

Figure 2.5: Poloidal (v_p , left) and toroidal (v_ϕ , right) wind velocity components as functions of R for different values of v_{Ap0} , the magnetic field strength (see legend in the right panel). Adapted from Cui & Yuan (2020).

allows one to derive the wind density, momentum and energy (Fukumura et al., 2010, 2014; Kazanas et al., 2012). Although with some initial conditions and assumptions, such as perfect MHD, axisymmetry and self-similarity, these models have been successfully applied to UFOs in powerful quasars, such as those in PG 1211+143 (Fukumura et al., 2015) and in PDS 456 (Fukumura et al., 2018), showing a remarkable agreement with observed data. Fig. 2.6 shows the fit of the joint *XMM-Newton* - *NuSTAR* observation of PDS 456. Within their picture, the UFO is identified by the innermost layers of gas, launched at small radii from the SMBH as required by their fast velocities. An additional, appealing feature is that WAs can also be fit in this picture as their high-distance, low-density and low-velocity counterparts (Fukumura et al., 2018).

Interestingly, the same authors successfully applied the same magnetic model to the X-ray outflow of the accreting stellar mass black hole GRO J1655-40 (Fukumura et al., 2017). This may implicitly suggest a common trend of the magnetic fields with varying black hole masses (i.e., from stellar mass to supermassive ones).

However, in order to account for the highly non-linear MHD dynamics, several assumptions are adopted both in the theoretical analysis and in the comparison with the observed data. Particularly, the magnetic field is assumed to be self-similar, time-steady and its strength is determined *a priori*, rather than self-consistently. Equilibrium of the accretion flow is not discussed in general, and standard accretion disc solutions are employed. Finally, calculations

Figure 2.6: Left panel: magnetic wind structure in 3D (white lines). In the left and right walls it is shown the ionisation parameter and the density of the wind, respectively. Blue(red) corresponds to higher(lower) values. Right: Best fit (top) and ratio between datapoints and model (bottom) for the joint X-ray spectrum of PDS 456. Black and yellow points corresponds to *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* datasets, respectively. From Fukumura et al. (2018)

are performed in 2D, assuming axisymmetry.

A way to overcome these limitations and integrate magnetic driving with radiative and thermal contributions is to numerically solve the evolution of the gas around the black hole with hydrodynamics simulations. Computations are largely time consuming, and some approximations must be performed. However, as we will show in the next Subsection, the ubiquitous presence of outflow - both in form of disc winds and jets - is a common feature, regardless of the computational methods employed.

2.1.4 Combined action of gas pressure, radiation and magnetic fields

Given the difficulty to simultaneously take into account the three different forces, one usually has to turn on numerical simulations. Radiation-MHD (Rad-MHD) simulations have been extensively performed over the last ten years, and they all show the ubiquitous presence of outflowing gas above and below the accretion disc plane. Ohsuga et al. (2009); Ohsuga & Mineshige (2011) performed Rad-MHD simulations including radiative transfer, thermal energy dissipation and, notably, the electromagnetic resistivity. They successfully reproduced the three accretion states described in Sect. 1.2.1 by just controlling the initial gas density normalisation: high, medium and low values (model A, B, C) lead respectively to slim disc, standard disc and a radiatively inefficient accretion flow, similar to the ADAF solution. Fig. 2.7 shows a snapshot of the results from Ohsuga et al. (2009). Toroidal magnetic field lines on the equatorial plane

2. Theoretical and numerical modelling of accretion disc winds

Model	Corresponding States	A	B	C
		Slim disk	Standard disk	RIAF
normalized mass accretion rate*	$\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/(L_{\text{E}}/c^2)$	120	5.3×10^{-3}	5.8×10^{-5}
Eddington ratio*	L/L_{E}	1.0	7.3×10^{-4}	7.4×10^{-10}
ratio of outflow rate to accretion rate*	$\dot{M}_{\text{out}}/\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}$	0.045	0.013	0.1
ratio of kinetic luminosity to luminosity*	L_{kin}/L	0.16	0.0013	120
density [†]	$\log \rho [\text{g cm}^{-3}]$	$-1 \sim -2$	~ -5	~ -10
gas temperature [†]	$\log T [K]$	~ 8	~ 6	$10 \sim 11$
gas energy density [‡]	$\log E_{\text{gas}} [\text{erg cm}^{-3}]$	15.0	9.7	9.0
magnetic energy density [‡]	$\log E_{\text{mag}} [\text{erg cm}^{-3}]$	15.3	9.2	8.3
radiation energy density [‡]	$\log E_{\text{rad}} [\text{erg cm}^{-3}]$	17.2	10.4	3.2
plasma- β [‡]	$p_{\text{gas}}/p_{\text{mag}}$	0.33	2.1	3.3

Figure 2.7: Output from the simulations of Ohsuga et al. (2009). From left to right, perspectives refer to model A, B, C, i.e. from high- to low-density. In the upper panels the normalised density distribution (see colour legend) is overlaid with isosurfaces (light blue) at which the outward velocity equals the escape velocity. In the lower panels the normalised radiation energy density is overlaid with the magnetic field lines. In models A and B, the green surface indicate the photosphere (i.e., where the gas optical depth is unity), while model C is optically thin. Bottom table: gas properties for the three models. Adapted from Ohsuga et al. (2009).

are clearly visible in all models. Moreover, a magnetic toroidal "tower" along the jet direction develops in Model A and C, while in B (standard disc) magnetic field lines have larger poloidal component.

In Model A a strong radiative pressure-driven outflow reaches $v_{out} \approx 0.1 c$ within the velocity isosurfaces, shown in blue in the top row (i.e., the surfaces where the outflow velocity is equal to the escape velocity). Moreover, the radiation pressure gradient enables to collimate an inner jet-like stream, which evolves within the magnetic tower and is driven upward by the magnetic pressure gradient. Thus, the wide-angle outflow coexists with an axial, collimated jet which is the combined result of radiative pressure (inward confinement) and magnetic pressure (upward thrust). In Model B the outflow is both magnetically- and radiatively-driven, with no relevant collimation along the rotation axis. Finally, in model C, i.e. in the low accretion rate, low luminosity end, the development of a strong jet (along the magnetic tower) carries away most of the accretion energy. In fact, the ratio between kinetic luminosity (i.e., the energy rate of the outflow) and the radiative luminosity (mainly tracing the disc luminosity) is 120, orders of magnitude higher than in the previous models. Similarly, the ratio between outflow and accretion rates reaches a maximum of 10 %, i.e., a tenth of the matter is ejected from the disc and does not get accreted onto the SMBH.

The interplay between the different driving forces and the outflow evolution with the accretion rate are indicative of a profound link between accretion and ejection. These results indicate that outflows may also play a systemic role in the regulation of accretion, by propagating the accretion energy and transporting the angular momentum outward. Consistent results have also been obtained in sub- and super-critical accretion Rad-MHD simulations, specifically suited for AGNs (Jiang et al., 2016, 2019), as well as radiation, general-relativistic MHD simulations with stellar mass black holes (Sądowski & Narayan, 2016). In almost all the simulations reported in the literature, the Eddington-normalised accretion rate is the driving factor, while the black hole mass results in an overall scaling of the mass fluxes, both in accretion and ejection. We refer to the recent review of Davis & Tchekhovskoy (2020) for further discussions on numerical simulations.

2.2 Fitting the data with radiative transfer codes

As discussed in Sect. 1.3, spectroscopic observations of X-ray outflow are usually fitted with templates obtained from photoionisation codes, with *Cloudy* (Ferland et al., 1998, 2017) and *XSTAR* (Kallman & Bautista, 2001) among the most popular ones. Given the physical conditions of X-ray outflows, these codes assume radiation as the main source of ionisation (for different approaches, see e.g. the *SPEX* code, Kaastra et al., 1996), as well as local thermodynamic

equilibrium (LTE). We focus here on *XSTAR*¹, both because of its widespread adoption for UFO fitting and because it has been integrated into the WINE model, as we will discuss in the next Section. However, we note that the general working scheme is analogous to that of *Cloudy* and other similar codes.

Each run of the *XSTAR* code is divided in two steps. First, ionisation status of the gas is determined as a function of the incident luminosity and the gas properties, i.e. its number and column densities and the distance from the central source. The equilibrium is reached when radiative heating sources, mainly ionisation and Compton, are balanced by cooling via recombination, bremsstrahlung and radiative deexcitation of bound levels. Once the gas ionic population is determined, radiative transfer calculates the interaction of the photon field with the matter. All physical processes involving photons, such as free-free, bound-free, free-bound processes, radiative recombination continua, are taken into account. The informations relative to every interaction, such as atomic energy levels, transition probabilities and cross sections, are specified in the atomic database (Bautista & Kallman, 2001).

Summarising, the input quantities are:

- The incident spectrum profile and its integrated luminosity in the $13.6\text{eV} - 13.6\text{keV}$ range, i.e. the "ionising luminosity" L_{ion} entering in the definition of the ionisation parameter ξ .
- ξ_0, n_0 , where the subscript $_0$ indicates that they must be specified at the inner radius of the gas. From these quantities and L_{ion} , the radius r_0 is derived
- α , the coefficient regulating the radial dependence of n : $n = n_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r}\right)^\alpha$
- N_H , the gas column density. The ending radius r_1 can be calculated from N_H, n_0, r_0, α .
- v_{broad} , the gas velocity dispersion regulating the broadening of the absorption features (see discussion below).

After a simulation is run and has converged to a solution, several outputs are produced as result. The most important ones, for the aims of the present work, are the transmitted spectrum, i.e. the incident spectrum absorbed by the gas, and the spectrum emitted by the gas itself. These two spectra are conceptually symmetric, since absorption in the first and emission in the second arise from the same gas, although the single radiative processes may differ in the two directions. Moreover, a list of the atomic transition emissivities is given in output in units of $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$ (luminosity density).

Since its first version (Kallman & McCray, 1982), *XSTAR* has been used in a variety of astrophysical contexts, allowing high-quality analysis of X-ray absorbers in AGNs and compact

¹For an useful walk-through of *XSTAR* we refer to the online guide, available at this link.

sources (Danehkar et al., 2018b). However, its main physical assumption need to be carefully addressed when dealing with the relativistically-broadened profiles of UFOs and with fast disc winds in general.

The most relevant assumptions are:

- The gas is assumed to be a spherically symmetric layer centred on the luminosity source, which is approximated as point like. This way, absorption profiles can be calculated assuming that the radiation field hits the gas shell perpendicularly.
- The gas is assumed to be at rest. Atomic line absorptions are represented by Gaussian features, whose 1σ amplitude is given by the maximum between the local thermal velocity and v_{broad} .
- As a result of the previous points, emission spectrum is simply given by the atomic transitions, with energies corresponding to the rest frame ones and the luminosity calculated from the emissivities multiplied by the shell volume, i.e. $\frac{4}{3}\pi(r_1^3 - r_0^3)$. Spherical symmetry is not supported by the observations, which instead suggest a more structured medium, with some degree of clumpiness and a covering factor (i.e., the fraction of solid angle covered by the outflow) smaller than one. Moreover, we also expect that the hemisphere beyond the accretion disc (with respect to the line of sight) is covered by the disc itself, and hence is unobservable. Finally, as discussed in the Section 2.1, the theory of wind driving suggests a strong degree of spatial anisotropy for the outflow, regardless of the driving mechanism.

The standard approach is to represent a non-zero outflowing velocity v_{out} by blueshifting the computed model spectra when fitting the observed data. The best-fit blueshift, once corrected by the host galaxy systemic redshift, gives v_{out} . However, there are two main caveats in this procedure. First, real outflow velocities may be best represented by a distribution of velocities (i.e., a velocity profile), rather than a single (average) value, as also suggested by the complex acceleration patterns discussed in the above Sections. Moreover, as we will discuss in detail in Sect. 4, special relativity effects dramatically modify the gas opacity and, as a consequence, the equivalent width of the absorption features imprinted on the incident spectrum, as well as the emission ones.

2.3 The WINE model: general overview and conceptual scheme

In order to overcome the main limitations of *XSTAR* we developed a new model called Wind in the Ionised Nuclear Environment (WINE). This model couples the photoionisation code from

2. Theoretical and numerical modelling of accretion disc winds

Figure 2.8: WINE schematic flowchart. The coloured blocks represent iteration over the wind column density N_H .

Figure 2.9: Geometry of the WINE model. Yellow and blue area represent the accretion disc and the central luminosity source, respectively. The conical wind region is centred on the SMBH and its symmetry axis is perpendicular to the disc. Opening angles and inclination of the line of sight (LOS) are indicated. We assume the rear cone to be obscured by the disc.

XSTAR with two new instruments: a Monte Carlo treatment of the emitting region, that allows us to convolve the line emissivities with realistic emission templates according to the outflow geometry, and a special relativity treatment of radiative transfer to properly represent the gas motion. We outline a schematic flowchart of WINE in Fig. 2.8 to guide the reader towards the next Sections. A more detailed version is presented in Fig. 6.2.

The user interface is represented with a green box, where the initial parameters must be indicated. Similarly to *XSTAR*, we require $S_I, L_{ion}, N_H, \xi_0, \alpha$. Instead of n_0 , the starting radius r_0 is required, in order to directly focus on the gas location. n_0 , in turn, can be derived from r_0, ξ_0, L_{ion} . Moreover, we implement a radial velocity profile specified by v_0, β , such as $v(r) = v_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r}\right)^\beta$. We assume a conical wind geometry as shown in Fig. 2.9, as suggested by disc wind simulations and in analogy with galactic scale outflows (see Section above and 1.4). We assume that the cone symmetry axis coincides with the rotation axis of the accretion disc, and we retain the *XSTAR* approximation of a point source luminosity located at the vertex of the cone (i.e. the centre of the accretion disc). The opening angle of the cone, θ_{out} , is a free input parameter (last line of the green box). Moreover, we also allow for an inner cavity around the rotation axis with variable angular amplitude θ_{in} . The inclination of the line of sight (LOS) with respect to the cone symmetry axis is given by i .

We adopt a multilayer approach to represent the scaling of the wind density and velocity profiles, $n(r), v(r)$, along the radial coordinate r , i.e. the distance from the luminosity source. The

wind column is divided in a number M of shells with constant column $\delta N_H = N_H/M$. Starting from the innermost slab, photoionisation and radiative transfer is performed using *XSTAR*. Then, the transmitted spectrum and luminosity are used as input quantities for the second slab. This procedure is repeated over the M shells until the total column density N_H is reached. The value of δN_H is chosen as a tradeoff between computational time and accuracy. In particular, we check that, for the typical UFO and WA parameter space, a value of $\delta N_H = 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is small enough to ensure a smooth variation of the wind properties from one shell to the adjacent one, so that our multilayer approximation accurately reproduces a continuous radiative transfer within the wind. For each new slab, the code analytically computes all the required *XSTAR* input quantities (see the blue box). Slab velocity is also updated to include special relativity effects in the radiative transfer.

This way, the wind absorption spectrum is obtained. The iterative procedure allows us to accurately model the wind features as a function of the density and velocity profiles, overcoming the original *XSTAR* assumption of a layer of gas at rest.

Emission spectrum is obtained in a similar fashion. For each slab, random Monte Carlo coordinates are assigned to a high number of points, in order to fill homogeneously the slab volume, which is a function of the slab starting and ending radii and of $\theta_{in}, \theta_{out}$. Then, the projection along the LOS of each point luminosity and energy (i.e., the relativistic beaming and Doppler effects) are calculated. The composition of each point response gives the total slab emission profile. Slab spectrum is obtained by the convolution of the atomic emissivities with the emission profile. Finally, wind emission spectrum is obtained as the composition of all the slab emission spectra.

This Monte Carlo procedure allows to go beyond the original *XSTAR* assumption of spherical symmetry, giving the possibility to directly probe the source geometry and its covering factor, as we will discuss in detail in the next Section.

The WINE structure has been designed to minimise the number of physical assumptions and to directly probe the most important outflow parameters such as the innermost wind radius r_0 , the emission geometry, covering factor, velocity profile and N_H, ξ_0 . Its numerical accuracy can match the spectral resolution both of present-day X-ray gratings and CCDs and next-generation microcalorimeters, such as those onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*. Thanks to the modular structure of WINE, additional features can be easily added, such as an angular dependence of the wind properties or different velocity and density scalings. We tailored the number of free parameters to the typical data quality of UFO spectra. As discussed in Sect. 1.3.2, UFOs have been mostly detected in moderate-resolution CCD observations, therefore a very large number of free parameters would lead to some degeneracies among them as well as possible poorly constrained quantities in fitting the spectral data.

3. Monte Carlo modelling of the wind emission features

In the literature, detailed assessments of the UFO properties have been usually carried on focusing mainly on the absorption components, rather than the emission ones, (see e.g. Tombesi et al., 2011, 2015; Kosec et al., 2020) for two principal reasons. Firstly, emission profiles are detected only in a subset of UFO spectra, possibly as a result of the lower EW expected for emission lines with respect to the corresponding absorption processes, as we will discuss in detail in Sect. 6. Secondly, synthetic emission templates are usually built upon several assumptions, as discussed in Sect. 2.2, therefore their application to observed UFO spectra yields only limited insights on the UFO properties (see e.g. Nardini et al., 2015). In some cases, the emission counterpart has been examined using simple Gaussian components, again leaving little room for a proper determination of the UFO physical and geometrical properties (Smith et al., 2019). A detailed study of the emission is of fundamental importance, since it represents a powerful tracer of the global properties of the outflow, integrated all over the outflow volume and projected over the LOS. On the contrary, absorption profiles are a precise tracker of the wind properties exclusively along the line of sight. Therefore, a combined study of emission and absorption features allows to explore with the greatest detail the physics of the outflow and, in particular to estimate its mass and energy loading factors.

In fact, emission is fundamental to calculate the covering factor, C_f , defined as the fraction of the solid angle occupied by the outflow. Mass and energy outflow rates, \dot{M}_{out} , \dot{E}_{out} , respectively, directly depend on C_f , as expressed e.g. in Crenshaw & Kraemer (2012) (see Sect. 1.3.2): $\dot{M}_{out} = 4\pi r N_H \mu m_p C_f v_{out}$. Moreover, as discussed in Sect. 2.1, the global morphology of the outflow could allow to distinguish between competing launching scenarios. In fact, radiative driving favours an equatorial distribution of the outflowing gas (Proga & Kallman, 2004; Higginbottom et al., 2014) or, under certain initial conditions, a funnel-shaped path (Elvis, 2000; Sim et al., 2008; Hagino et al., 2015). Magneto-hydrodynamic scenarios, instead, foresee a different distribution of the gas in the equatorial-poloidal plane, with the wind mass loading factor as the driving parameter: lightest (and fastest) winds develop along the poloidal field lines, while the most massive ones are pushed through the magnetic pressure of the toroidal component

(see Cui & Yuan, 2020 for an extensive review).

In this Section we illustrate a Monte Carlo procedure to quickly build emission profiles and compare them with observed UFO spectra. This is a preliminar version of the one used in the final WINE model (which will be presented in Section 6), and it is intended to give an idea of our modelling approach and to demonstrate its effectiveness. To this aim, the properties of the model will be tailored to those of the intense and persistent UFO observed in the X-ray spectrum of PDS 456. We will reanalyse the joint *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* observations presented in Nardini et al. (2015) (N15 hereafter) and we will independently derive the wind properties, including v_{out} , C_f and, then, obtain improved estimates of \dot{M}_{out} , \dot{E}_{out} .

PDS 456 is a nearby and luminous quasar ($z = 0.184$, $L_{bol} \approx 10^{47} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) exhibiting a clear P-Cygni feature, due to highly-ionised Fe, with a ionisation parameter $\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{nR^2} \sim 10^5 \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$. The outflow velocity reported in the literature is $\sim 0.25 c$, the launching radius is $< 200 r_g$ and the energy transfer rate is as high as $\sim 20\%$ of the bolometric luminosity L_{bol} (see e.g. Reeves et al., 2003; Matzeu et al., 2017, N15). The extreme UFO properties of PDS 456 makes it an interesting test-bed for the development of our model.

This Section is based in part on Luminari et al. (2018). In particular, we refer to the paper for a detailed description of the *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* data reduction, which goes beyond the aim of the present work.

3.1 The Wind Emission Geometry

We present the wind geometry in Fig. 3.1. As discussed in Sect. 2.3, we model the outflow as a conical structure, with the symmetry axis coincident with the rotation axis of the accretion disc (represented in yellow in the picture) and with the vertex centred on the black hole. The opening angle of the cone θ_{out} and the inclination i of the line of sight (LOS) with respect to the symmetry axis are free parameters. We assume the gas to be directed radially outward, with a velocity profile defined as:

$$v(r') = v_{max}(1 - sr'), \quad (3.1)$$

where v_{max} , s are free parameters and $r' \equiv \frac{r}{r_{cone}}$ is the distance from the vertex normalised to the height of the cone ($r' \equiv r/r_{cone}$) and goes from 0 to 1. s is defined in the range $[0,1]$, as well, and represents the deceleration factor of the wind along r' . For $s = 1, 0$, the velocity at $r' = 1$ corresponds to $0, v_{max}$, thus representing a constant velocity and a totally decelerated wind, respectively. Equation 3.1 represents a first-order expansion of the velocity with respect to r and provides a basic description of the wind kinematic. In Sect 6 we will provide a more accurate parametrisation of $v(r)$, using the conservation of momentum and/or energy along the

Figure 3.1: Sketch of the WINE model. The wind opening angle θ_{out} and the inclination of the line of sight (LOS) i are indicated with blue and green shaded areas, respectively. The cone is perpendicular to the accretion disc (yellow rectangle) and centred on the supermassive black hole (SMBH, black dot). X-ray luminosity is assumed as a point source coincident with the SMBH. The rear cone, obscured by the disc, is shown with dashed lines.

flow to link $v(r)$ with the gas density $n(r)$. In this preliminary version of the model we require that $i < \theta_{out}$, that is, the LOS has to lie inside the wind, given the P-Cygni profile observed in the X-ray spectrum of PDS 456. We also consider a more refined version of the model, allowing for the internal cavity with variable angular aperture θ_{in} .

The conical geometry of the wind is approximated by a large number l (i.e., 100) of conical shells, equally spaced between $r = 0$ and $r = r_{cone}$. These shells have angular opening θ_{out} with respect to the symmetry axis. For each shell, we assign angular coordinates to a number p of points ($p = 10^4$ by default) through a Monte Carlo method. The radial velocity is determined from Eq. 3.1 using the shell radius $r' = \frac{l}{100}$.

We assume the same intrinsic brightness B_{int} for each point all over the cone in the wind reference frame, K' . This assumption is justified by the high degree of ionisation of the UFO in PDS 456, $\xi \approx 10^5 \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$, implying that most of the emission/absorption features arise from highly ionised Fe, i.e. Fe XXV and Fe XXVI (Kallman et al., 2004). Then, using special relativity, we calculate for each point of the shell the projected value of B_{int} and $v(r)$ from K' to the rest frame K (i.e. the observer frame) along the LOS: B_{proj} and v_{proj} , respectively. We show in Fig. 3.2 the spherical coordinate system for the emitting region, adopted both in this and in the following Sections. For the sake of simplicity and without any loss of generality, we

Figure 3.2: The spherical coordinate system adopted for the wind emission geometry.

assume that the observer LOS lies along the z -coordinate. In Fig. 3.3 we illustrate the relativistic transformation from K' to K affecting the gas emission, as a result of its outflowing motion with a velocity v_{out} . v_{proj} , B_{proj} can be calculated as (Rybicki & Lightman, 1986):

$$v_{proj} = \frac{v_{out}}{\gamma(1 - \beta \cos \theta)} \quad (3.2a)$$

$$B_{proj} = \frac{B_{int}}{\gamma^3(1 - \beta \cos \theta)^3} \quad (3.2b)$$

where $\beta \equiv \frac{v_{out}}{c}$, $\gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$ and θ is the angle between v_{out} and the LOS, as measured in K ($\theta = 0deg$ when v_{out} lies along the LOS, such as in the Figure). When radiation is emitted along the direction of motion both v_{proj} and B_{proj} increase with increasing v_{out} , corresponding to higher observed velocity (Doppler effect) and higher received luminosity (beaming effect). Viceversa, when radiation is emitted perpendicularly or backward ($\theta = 90 deg$ and $180 deg$, respectively) both the velocity and luminosity are reduced in K . The overall result is to concentrate the emitted radiation into a narrow cone along the direction of motion, as observed also in higher velocity systems such as jets in Blazars and GRBs (Urry, & Padovani, 1995; Ghisellini et al., 1993), where the LOS is almost aligned with the direction of motion. In Section 4 we will further discuss these transformations applied to wind absorption.

We calculate v_{proj} , B_{proj} for all the p points in the shell. Then, we group the projected luminosity into bins of $3,600 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In this way we obtain the spectrum of a single shell. The combination of each shell spectrum at all radii (i.e., from $r = 0$ to $r = r_{cone}$) provides the global

Figure 3.3: Relativistic beaming of the emitted radiation from the atom reference frame, K' , to the rest frame K .

spectrum emitted by the wind. We show in Fig. 3.4 a visual representation of this multi layer approach, where we also include an inner cavity.

We assume an isothermal radial density profile for the wind:

$$n(r) = n_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^2, \quad (3.3)$$

where n_0 is the density of the wind at a fiducial radius r_0 . This ensures that $\xi(r)$ is constant at all radii, in agreement with the UFO in PDS 456 which is dominated by Fe XXVI (Reeves et al., 2003, Reeves et al., 2009, N15). In fact, using Eq. 3.3 $\xi(r)$ can be expressed as:

$$\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{n(r)r^2} = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_0 r_0^2} \quad (3.4)$$

where there is no dependence on r . A constant ξ indicates that the relative abundance of the ions, including Fe XXVI, is roughly constant within the medium and therefore justifies our assumption of constant B_{int} . Since the area of the shells increases with r' as $(r')^2$, a density profile $n \propto (r')^{-2}$ implies a constant number of points for each shell, as specified above.

In the following we provide a detailed description of the free parameters of the model:

- v_{max} : the maximum velocity of the wind (in units of c) corresponding to the starting velocity at the vertex of the cone. We assume [0.1c, 0.6c] as the possible range of v_{max} and we span this interval with a resolution of 0.01c.
- The opening angle θ_{out} can range from 0 to 90 deg, representing respectively a cone with null volume and a maximally-opened cone, corresponding to a hemisphere filling the solid angle above the accretion disc plane (see Fig. 3.1). This interval is sampled by nine equally-space steps of 10 deg.
- i : the upper limit of this parameter is set by the requirement of having an LOS inside the cone aperture, that is, $i \leq \theta_{out}$. The possible range for i , [0, θ_{out}], is sampled with 11

Figure 3.4: A visual description of the multilayer Monte Carlo approach employed for the wind emission.

equally spaced steps.

- The deceleration factor of the wind s (Eq. 3.1) ranges from 0 to 1 and it is sampled through steps of 0.1.
- Furthermore, an inner cavity in the cone can be accounted for by an additional parameter θ_{in} , which represents the angular amplitude with respect to the symmetry axis. Parameter θ_{in} can span the open interval $(0, i)$.

From this set of free parameters it is possible to derive $v(r)$ through Eq. 3.1 and C_f , calculated as the fraction of solid angle covered by the cone:

$$C_f = 1 - \cos(\theta_{out}) \quad (3.5)$$

In the case of a cone with an inner cavity, Eq. 3.5 becomes:

$$C_f = \cos(\theta_{in}) - \cos(\theta_{out}) \quad (3.6)$$

3.2 Spectral analysis of the wind in PDS 456

We now apply the Monte Carlo profiles to the simultaneous *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* spectra of PDS 456, taken from the multi-epoch observational campaign carried on in 2013-2014 and presented in N15. We focus on Epoch 3 (September 15, 2013) and Epoch 4 (September 20, 2013;

see Table 3.1) in order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio. We consider these two datasets since they are virtually indistinguishable in terms of flux and spectral shape, as already noted in N15.

Data reduction and spectral extraction are performed using the data analysis software SAS 16.0.0 and NUSTARDAS v1.7.1 (calibration database version 20170222) for *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR*, respectively. Table 3.1 lists the journal of the observations. We adopt the same filtering scheme and spectral extraction regions as in N15. We use the XSPEC software (Arnaud, 1996) to analyse the observations. This code allows to perform detailed studies of X-ray spectra and to fit them using least squares techniques. It provides a variety of analytical model to compare with the observations, such as power-law and blackbody emission profiles (useful for the modelling of the continuum band in the $\approx 1 - 10\text{keV}$ spectral band, see Sect. 1.2.2), Gaussian, brehmsstrahlung and photoionisation edges profiles. We refer to the XSPEC online guide ¹ for a detailed description of the model components and the general working scheme. Interestingly, XSPEC also gives the user the possibility to upload its own fitting model. We compile a table model with the Monte Carlo outputs, spanning the whole range of all the free parameters, and we use it directly in the spectral fitting.

We co-add the spectra of Epochs 3 and 4, both for *XMM-Newton* and for *NuSTAR*, using the *ftools* task *addascaspec*, and finally group them to a minimum of 100 and 50 counts per energy bin, respectively. We base our fitting procedure on that of N15, with a lower energy bound of 3

Epoch	Telescope	Date and time	T_{tot} (ks) ^(a)	Inst.	T_{net} (ks) ^(b)	cts_{net} (k) ^(c)	Extr. ^(d)
3	XMM	2013-09-15 18:30:00	120.5	pn	102.2	207.6	35/60
	NuSTAR	2013-09-15 17:56:07	119.1	FPMA	44.0	4.3	80/80
				FPMB	44.0	4.0	80/80
4	XMM	2013-09-20 02:29:39	112.1	pn	94.9	188.5	35/60
	NuSTAR	2013-09-20 03:06:07	113.8	FPMA	58.5	5.9	80/80
				FPMB	58.5	5.7	80/80

Table 3.1: Journal of the observations. XMM Obs. ID is 0721010501, NuSTAR 60002032006. (a), (b) Observation lengths, in ks, before and after filtering, respectively. (c) Net counts in units of 10^3 photons in the 3-10(30) keV band for *XMM-Newton*(*NuSTAR*). (d) Extraction regions for source and/or background in arcsec.

keV in order to avoid two complex spectral features, which are uninteresting for our main goal: the soft excess at energies below $\sim 1\text{keV}$ and the warm absorber at $\lesssim 2\text{keV}$. The upper bounds are 10 and 30 keV for the *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* spectra, respectively. The spectra are always jointly fitted, with an intercalibration constant left free to vary.

¹available at <https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/xanadu/xspec/>

Figure 3.5: Ratio between data and the best-fit continuum model to the 3-5 keV + 15-30 keV spectrum, once the 5-14 keV region is included (see Sect. 3.2.1 for details). Black, green, and red crosses indicate *XMM-Newton*/pn, *NuSTAR* FPMA, and FPMB data, respectively.

3.2.1 Phenomenological fit

Similarly to N15, we first perform a preliminary fit to describe the continuum emission using a power law modified by a neutral partial covering absorber, responsible for the spectral curvature below 4 keV. For the moment, we ignore the energy interval around the Fe K shell features, from 5 to 14 keV. Using directly the XSPEC notation, the fitting model can be expressed by the analytical expression:

$$constant \cdot phabs \cdot zpcfabs \cdot zpowerlaw \quad (3.7)$$

where *constant* is a constant multiplicative factor, set $\equiv 1$ for *XMM-Newton* data and left free to vary for the two *NuSTAR* modules. This is necessary to account for intercalibration differences between the three instruments. *phabs* accounts for the Galactic absorption and is set to $N_H^{Gal} \equiv 2 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (see N15). The neutral partial covering absorber is described by *zpcfabs*. Finally, the spectral index Γ and normalization K of the power-law continuum are free to vary. The \cdot sign indicates that all the fitting components are convolved together.

After the fit, we obtain for the continuum component $\Gamma = 2.40 \pm 0.06$. Hereafter, all the errors are reported at 68 % confidence level, otherwise when stated. For the absorber, the best fit column density is $N_H = 2.4 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and the covering fraction is $C_f = 0.42 \pm 0.05$, suggesting a more distant feature from the AGN with respect to the UFO. These findings are in agreement with the low N_H and ξ and the low variability found in N15 for this component. The resulting χ^2 is 309 for 362 degrees of freedom. Table 3.2 shows the best-fit parameters. Figure 3.5 shows the ratio between datapoints and the best fit model in the 3-30 keV band.

Then, we consider the whole energy band and we model the absorption and emission features related to the Fe K shell with simple Gaussian lines. For the emission, we set the line energy to

Parameter	Value
constant ^(a)	1 ^(f) , 1.07 ± 0.02, 1.08 ± 0.02
phabs	
N_H	0.2 ^(f) × 10 ²² cm ⁻²
zpcfabs	
N_H	24 ⁺⁸ ₋₉ × 10 ²² cm ⁻²
f_{cov} ^(b)	0.42 ^{+0.05} _{-0.04}
zpowerlaw	
Γ	2.40 ± 0.07
K ^(c)	5.4 ^{+1.3} _{-1.0}
z	0.184 ^(f)
$\chi^2/d.o.f.$	309/362

Table 3.2: Best-fit values for the continuum fitting (see relation 3.7). with associated errors at 68% c.l.. ^(a) *constant* has three values since it is the only parameter allowed to vary between the different datasets (values shown for *XMM-Newton* pn and *NuSTAR* FPMA and FPMB, respectively). ^(b) f_{cov} is the covering fraction of the intrinsic cold absorber. ^(c) Normalization in units of 10⁻³photons keV^{-1} cm⁻²s⁻¹ at 1 keV . ^(f) Fixed value.

the Fe XXVI Ly α transition ($E = 6.97$ keV rest frame) and we leave the line width and redshift free to vary. For the absorption, we include two Gaussian lines for Fe XXVI Ly α and Ly β ($E = 8.25$ keV rest frame) and a photoelectric edge at $E = 9.28$ keV rest frame corresponding to the K shell edge from Fe XXVI. The resulting model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & constant \cdot phabs \cdot (zpcfabs \cdot zedge \cdot zpowerlaw \\
 & + zgauss_em_Ly\alpha + zgauss_abs_Ly\alpha + zgauss_abs_Ly\beta)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

In addition to the components in expression 3.7, $zgauss_em_Ly\alpha$ indicates the Gaussian emission associated to Fe XXVI Ly α and $zgauss_abs_Ly\alpha$, $zgauss_abs_Ly\beta$ represents the Gaussian absorption for Ly α and Ly β lines, respectively. The term $zedge$ corresponds to the Fe K shell photoelectric edge. The + symbol indicates the composition of different spectral components, which are independent from each other.

A simple fit leaving all the parameters free returns an almost identical redshift for both the absorption lines, $z = -0.100 \pm 0.009$, -0.107 ± 0.005 for Ly α and Ly β , respectively, corresponding to a blueshifted velocity of $\simeq 0.26$, 0.27 c while the redshift of the K shell edge is $z = -0.071 \pm 0.1$ and implies a velocity of $\simeq 0.24$ c . Since we expect the same gas to be responsible for all the absorption features, we impose the same redshift for the lines and the edge. Similarly, we link the Gaussian line widths in order to have the same velocity dispersion.

Moreover, we keep the continuum and the partial covering absorption parameters fixed to the values in Table 3.2 for simplicity. Table 3.3 lists the best fit values for emission and absorption components. The best-fit returns a remarkably good statistic: $\chi^2 = 649$ for 705 degrees of freedom (d.o.f.), confirming the validity of our approach.

Interestingly, the redshift of the emitting component is significantly shifted with respect of that of the host galaxy: $z = 0.117$ versus $z = 0.184$. This corresponds to a difference in terms of blue-shifted velocity along the LOS of $\simeq 0.06 c$ ($\sim 18,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), supporting the idea that we are observing an approaching emitting component, as in Fig. 3.1, rather than a spherically symmetric one, as usually assumed in *XSTAR* (see Sect. 2.2).

Parameter	Value
<i>zedge</i>	
<i>Edge En. (keV)</i>	9.28 ^(f)
$f^{(a)}$	0.19 ± 0.04
$z^{(b)}$	$-0.096^{+0.008}_{-0.007}$
<i>zgauss_em</i>	
<i>En. (keV)</i>	6.97 ^(f)
σ (keV)	0.7 ± 0.1
z	$0.12^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$
$K^{(c)}$	11^{+2}_{-1}
<i>zgauss_Lyα</i>	
<i>En. (keV)</i>	6.97 ^(f)
$\sigma^{(d)}$ (keV)	0.33 ± 0.04
$z^{(b)}$	$-0.0962^{+0.008}_{-0.007}$
$K^{(c)}$	$5.8^{+0.6}_{-0.1}$
<i>zgauss_Lyβ</i>	
<i>En. (keV)</i>	8.25 ^(f)
$\sigma^{(d)}$ (keV)	0.39 ± 0.05
$z^{(b)}$	$-0.0962^{+0.008}_{-0.007}$
$K^{(c)}$	2.6 ± 0.4
$\chi^2/d.o.f.$	649/705

Table 3.3: Best-fit values for the phenomenological fit (see relation 3.8). ^(a) f is defined as the absorption depth at threshold. ^(b) Linked values. ^(c) Gaussian function normalization K is in units of 10^{-6} photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ^(d) Linked values. ^(f) Fixed value.

3.2.2 Fit with the WINE model

We now replace the Gaussian emission line with two WINE model components, corresponding to Ly α and Ly β emission. The continuum and neutral partial covering absorber are still parametrized

as in Sect. 3.2.1. The fitting model is now:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{constant} \cdot \text{phabs} \cdot (\text{zpcfabs} \cdot \text{smedge} \cdot \text{zpowerlaw} \\ & + \text{WINE_Ly}\alpha + \text{WINE_Ly}\beta + \text{zgauss_Ly}\alpha + \text{zgauss_Ly}\beta) \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

where $\text{WINE_Ly}\alpha$ and $\text{WINE_Ly}\beta$ represent the two WINE model emission components. The two Gaussian absorption lines are again as in Sect. 3.2.1, while smedge (Ebisawa et al., 1994) is a smeared photoelectric edge that accounts for the velocity gradient of the wind (see Eq. 3.1). $\text{WINE_Ly}\alpha$ and $\text{WINE_Ly}\beta$ have identical parameters, except for rest-frame energy and normalisation. Specifically, the ratio between the normalisations corresponds to the ratio of the oscillator strength of Fe XXVI Ly α and Ly β (Molendi et al., 2003, Tombesi et al., 2011).

Since we expect that both the emission and absorption features are due to the same medium, we tie the redshift and broadening of $\text{zgauss_Ly}\alpha$, $\text{zgauss_Ly}\beta$, and smedge to the emission parameters of WINE. Specifically, since our LOS intercepts the UFO, the velocity component of the gas along the LOS (i.e., the gas responsible for the absorption) coincides with the radial velocity $v(r)$. So, the average redshift z_{avg} of $\text{zgauss_Ly}\alpha$, $\text{zgauss_Ly}\beta$ and smedge corresponds to the average outflow velocity, $v_{avg} \equiv v(r_{cone}/2)$, according to the equation:

$$z_{avg} = \frac{1 + z_{PDS}}{\sqrt{(1 + v_{avg})/(1 - v_{avg})}} - 1, \quad (3.10)$$

where $z_{PDS} = 0.184$ is the cosmological redshift of PDS 456. Moreover, we assume that the standard deviation σ of $\text{zgauss_Ly}\alpha$ and $\text{zgauss_Ly}\beta$ is dominated by the velocity shear of the wind. Hence, we set σ , in terms of velocity, equal to the difference $v_{max} - v_{avg}$, while in terms of energy it can be expressed as:

$$\sigma = E \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1.184 \sqrt{(1 - v_{max})/(1 + v_{max})}} - \frac{1}{1 + z_{avg}} \right), \quad (3.11)$$

where E is the rest frame line energy. The same formula is used for the smearing characteristic width in the smedge component, using the photoionisation energy threshold as E .

Figure 3.6 shows the result of the fit assuming a full cone (without inner cavity) and Table 3.4 lists the best fit values. The associated χ^2 (dof) is 652 (715). The radial velocity $v(r)$ ranges from $\simeq 0.28 c$ to $\simeq 0.17 c$. For the outflow geometry we obtain $\theta_{out} \simeq 70$ deg, $i \simeq 60$ deg, and a covering fraction (calculated as the fraction of visible hemisphere covered by the wind) of $C_f \simeq 0.7$.

We performed a further fit including an inner wind cavity, but we find it is not statistically required by the data. θ_{in} is poorly constrained with an upper limit of 21 deg (90% *c.l.*).

Figure 3.6: Top panel: data (symbols as in fig 3.5) and best-fit model (solid line) including two WINE model components (dotted lines). Bottom panel: ratios between data and best fit model. See Sect. 3.2.2 for more details.

3.2.3 Reliability of the WINE model

We perform two different simulations to check the reliability of the Monte Carlo modelling. We first use as input our best-fit values (see Sect. 3.2.2 and Table 3.4) and simulate *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* FPMA and FPMB spectra with the same summed (Epoch 3 + Epoch 4) net exposure times reported in Table 3.1. We adopt the same spectral grouping as described in Sect. 3.2. For each simulation, we first perform a fit in the range 3-10(3-30) keV for *XMM-Newton*(*NuSTAR*), ignoring the interval between 5 and 14 keV, to find the best-fit continuum and cold absorber parameters. Then, we freeze these parameters and we fit the WINE model (together with the two Gaussian absorption lines and the photoelectric edge) considering also the energy interval 5-14 keV.

Table 3.5, first column, reports the differences Δ between the input values and the results, according to the formula:

$$\Delta = \frac{|V_i - \bar{V}_{out}|}{\sigma_{out}} \quad (3.12)$$

where V_i is the input value, \bar{V}_{out} is the mean of the best-fit values from 100 simulated spectra, and σ_{out} is the standard deviation of the distribution. The agreement between the mean values and the input parameters is remarkably good. Then, we perform a second set of simulations with different, arbitrary input values, to check the capability of the WINE model to discriminate

Parameter	Value
<i>smedge</i>	
E (keV)	9.28 ^(f)
$z^{(a)}$	$-0.063^{+0.004}_{-0.005}$
$f^{(b)}$	0.23 ± 0.05
$index^{(c)}$	$-2.67^{(f)}$
$width^{(d)}$ (keV)	$0.60^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$
<i>WINE model</i>	
v_{max} (c)	$0.285^{+0.006}_{-0.007}$
s	$0.39^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$
θ_{out} (deg)	71^{+13}_{-8}
i (deg)	63^{+13}_{-16}
$K^{(e)(g)}$ (Ly α)	$1.2^{+0.3}_{-0.2} \times 10^{-7}$
$K^{(e)(g)}$ (Ly β)	$2.28^{+0.6}_{-0.3} \times 10^{-8}$
z	$0.184^{(f)}$
$v_{min}^{(h)}$ (c)	0.17 ± 0.01
$C_f^{(i)}$	$0.7^{+0.2}_{-0.1}$
<i>zgauss_Lyα</i>	
E (keV)	6.97 ^(f)
$\sigma^{(d)}$ (keV)	$0.45^{+0.06}_{-0.07}$
$z^{(a)}$	$-0.063^{+0.004}_{-0.005}$
$K^{(e)}$	$1.28 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5}$
<i>zgauss_Lyβ</i>	
E (keV)	8.25 ^(f)
$\sigma^{(d)}$ (keV)	$0.54^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$
$z^{(a)}$	$-0.063^{+0.004}_{-0.005}$
$K^{(e)}$	$4.0^{+0.6}_{-0.7} \times 10^{-6}$
$\chi^2/d.o.f.$	652/715

Table 3.4: Best-fit values for the absorption and emission components using the WINE model (see relation 3.9). ^(a) Redshift of the absorption components are linked. ^(b) f is defined as the absorption depth at threshold. ^(c) Photoelectric cross-section index. ^(d) Linked values. ^(e) Normalizations in units of total photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. ^(g) WINE model normalizations are linked according to the ratio of the Ly α and Ly β oscillator strengths. ^(h) Derived minimum velocity of the wind (i.e., $v(r)$ for $r = 0$ and $r = r_{cone}$). ⁽ⁱ⁾ Derived opening angle of the cone. ^(f) Fixed value.

between different scenarios. Columns 2 and 3 of Table 3.5 report the input values and the resulting Δ , respectively, showing the robustness of WINE in this task.

Parameter	Model 1 ^(a)		Model 2 ^(b)	
	Δ	Input	Input	Δ
v_{max}	0.07	0.35 c	0.35	0.05
s	0.37	0.7	0.7	0.21
θ_{out}	0.27	45 deg	45 deg	0.31
i	0.44	4.5 deg	4.5 deg	0.47
Derived qts. ^(c)				
v_{min}	0.36	0.10 c	0.10	0.21
C_f	0.30	0.29	0.29	0.26

Table 3.5: Results of the simulations to check the reliability of the WINE model. ^(a) Difference Δ between input values and results (see Eq. 3.12). Input parameters are those reported in Table 3.4). ^(b) Different arbitrary input values (center column) and corresponding Δ (right column). ^(c) These quantities are derived from the fit parameters, as described in Sect. 3.1.

3.3 Athena simulations

As anticipated in Sect. 2.3, the number of free parameters within our model is limited by the energy resolution and signal to noise of the observed UFO spectra. We now concentrate on θ_{in} , regulating the amplitude of the inner cavity of the wind cone. We want to investigate if the quality of the *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* observations did not allow us to constrain θ_{in} and whether the next-generation Advanced Telescope for High-Energy Astrophysics (*Athena*) (Nandra et al., 2013) will allow to overcome this limitation. To this aim, we run a set of 100 simulations of observation with the X-ray Integral Field Unit (X-IFU) microcalorimeter ¹ (Barret et al., 2016, 2018). We adopt the best fit model (see 3.9 and Table 3.4) including an internal cavity with $\theta_{in} = 21$ deg, i.e. the 90% upper limit reported in Sect. 3.2.2. We simulate a set of 100 spectra. For each one, we group the spectrum to a minimum of 100 counts per bin; then, we perform two different spectral fits of the data in the energy range 3-12 keV. In the first one we assume a full cone geometry, while in the second one we include the inner cavity. Finally, we perform the F-test to check if the difference in the statistics of the two fits is enough to justify the introduction of the cavity. We verify that an exposure time of 500 ks ensures that 90% of the simulated spectra allows us to discriminate the presence of the cavity with an F-test probability < 1%. This statistical significance corresponds to a confidence level of 90%.

Table 3.6 reports the mean and the standard deviation of the distribution of the best-fit values for an exposure time of 500 ks. Figure 3.7 reports one of the simulated 500 ks spectra along with

¹We use response files and background spectra available at <http://x-ifu.irap.omp.eu/resources-for-users-and-x-ifu-consortium-members/>. We simulate the case of a mirror module radius of 1469 mm and adopt a background spectrum for an extraction area of 5 arcsec radius.

the best-fit inner cavity model. All the parameters can be measured with an accuracy higher than 6%, except for θ_{in} and C_f , for which the relative uncertainties are 18% and 11%, respectively.

Parameter	Input ^(a)	Results ^(b)
v_{max} (c)	0.285	0.285 ± 0.003
s	0.39	0.38 ± 0.01
θ_{out} (deg)	71	66 ± 4
i (deg)	63	62 ± 3
θ_{in} (deg)	21	22 ± 4
Derived qts. ^(c)		
v_{min} (c)	0.174	0.176 ± 0.005
C_f	0.60	0.53 ± 0.06

Table 3.6: Best fit values of the *Athena* simulations. ^(a) Input values. ^(b) Mean \pm standard deviation for the distribution of the best-fit values for the 100 simulated spectra, with an observation time of 500 ks. ^(c) These quantities are derived from the fit parameters, as described in Sect. 3.1.

Figure 3.7: One of the *Athena* X-IFU 500 ks simulated spectrum, along with the best-fit model including an inner cavity (solid red line). The two FeXXVI Ly α and Ly β WINE model components are reported as dotted lines.

3.4 UFO energetics and impact on the host galaxy

The results of our analysis are in agreement with the estimates on the wind velocity and C_f in N15. For the first quantity they estimated $\sim 0.25 c$, which is inside our radial excursion ($0.17 - 0.28 c$) and remarkably close to our mean value $\sim 0.23 c$.

The covering fraction in N15 is evaluated in different ways. The normalisation of the *XSTAR* wind emission tables yields an average value between all the observations of $C_f = 0.8 \pm 0.1$, while the fraction of the absorbed continuum luminosity re-emitted by the wind gives $C_f > 0.5$.

Thanks to WINE, we directly constrained the wind opening angle $\theta_{out} = 71_{-8}^{+13} deg$ and we consistently derived the covering factor as in Eq. 3.5: $C_f = 0.7_{-0.1}^{+0.2}$. This value is consistent with N15 and with UFO detection rates in the larger AGN population, as discussed in Sect. 1.3.2 (see also Tombesi et al., 2010, 2014; Gofford et al., 2013).

We derive \dot{M}_{out} following Eq. 1.5. For the outflow velocity v_{out} we use $v = (0.23 \pm 0.06) c$, i.e. the average velocity of the UFO v_{avg} as the mean value and v_{max} and v_{min} (i.e., $v(r_{cone})$) as upper and lower limits, respectively. Moreover, we set $C_f = 0.7$ and we take the following quantities from N15: $N_H = 6 \cdot 10^{23} cm^{-2}$, $r = 100r_G = 1.5 \cdot 10^{16} cm$, $L_{bol} \simeq 10^{47} erg s^{-1}$ and a black hole mass $M_{BH} = 10^9 M_\odot$. We find $\dot{M}_{out} \sim 16 \pm 4 M_\odot yr^{-1} = 0.23 \pm 0.06 \dot{M}_{Edd}$, for a radiative efficiency $\eta = 0.3$, as expected for luminous quasars such as PDS 456 (see Sect. 1.2.1 and Davis & Laor, 2011, Trakhtenbrot, 2014). We derive a momentum rate $\dot{P}_{out} = 7 \pm 3 \times 10^{36} dyne$, $\sim 2.1 \pm 1.1$ times the radiation momentum rate $\dot{P}_{rad} = L_{bol} c$, and an energy rate $\dot{E}_{out} = 3 \pm 2 \times 10^{46} ergs^{-1}$, that is $\simeq 30 \pm 20\% L_{bol}$.

The average values for \dot{M}_{out} and \dot{E}_{out} are a factor of ~ 1.5 and ~ 1.3 times greater than that found in N15, respectively. This difference is mainly due to our different μ , since they assume $\mu \equiv 1$ (i.e., the gas is composed only by hydrogen) and, more importantly, to the different C_f (0.7 versus their 0.5).

4. Special relativity effects

As anticipated in Sect. 2.3 special relativity effects are of fundamental importance to correctly analyse the outflow spectral signatures, given the mildly relativistic velocities of UFOs and BAL winds. While in Sect. 3 we concentrated on the effects on the emission profiles, here we focus on the absorption side.

The observed optical depth of the absorption features is usually considered a proxy of the outflow column density N_H along the LOS, independently of v_{out} . However, this assumption is no longer appropriate for accretion disc winds, since the observed (i.e. apparent) optical depth of the spectral features significantly underestimates the intrinsic N_H already for $v_{out} \gtrsim 0.05 c$ and, consequently, \dot{M}_{out} and \dot{E}_{out} as well. In this Section we develop an algorithm to take into account these effects in radiative transfer calculation and it will be implemented in the final version of WINE in Sect. 6.

It must be noted that this pure special-relativistic effect is universal (i.e. it applies to any fast-moving outflow intercepting the LOS), so its applications go well beyond the context of disc winds in AGNs. Moreover, it affects not only our estimate of the kinetic power of the outflow, but also the ability of the radiative source to effectively accelerate the outflow outwards, possibly posing a threat to the radiative driving scenario. We will explore this topic in Section 5. The work in this Section is based on Luminari et al. (2020).

4.1 Special relativity transformations

According to special relativity, the luminosity L' seen by a clump of gas moving at relativistic speed is reduced of a factor Ψ , with respect to a static gas, as:

$$L' = L \cdot \Psi \quad (4.1)$$

where L is the luminosity seen by an observer at rest and Ψ (i.e. the de-boosting factor) is defined as:

$$\Psi \equiv \psi^4 = \frac{1}{\gamma^4(1 + \beta \cos(\theta))^4} \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.1: Deboosting factor Ψ in the gas reference frame K' as a function of v_{out} assuming $\theta = 0$. For speeds lower than $0.01c$, the radiation intercepted by the outflow and by the (rest-frame) observer at infinity are virtually the same. For higher speeds, the fraction of intercepted radiation drops dramatically due to special relativity effects.

where $\gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$, $\beta = v_{out}/c$, v_{out} is the gas velocity, and θ is the angle between the incident luminosity L and the direction of motion of the gas. Figure 4.1 shows Ψ as a function of v_{out} for $\theta = 0 \text{ deg}$, corresponding to a radial outward motion of the gas. The deboosting factor is due to the combination of the space-time dilation in the gas reference frame K' , and the relativistic Doppler shift of the received radiation (Rybicki & Lightman, 1986).

Using Eq. 4.1, the radiative intensity (i.e. the luminosity per solid angle) $\frac{dL'}{d\Omega'}$ received by the outflowing gas in K' can be written as a function of the intensity in the rest frame K , as:

$$\frac{dL'}{d\Omega'} = \Psi \frac{dL}{d\Omega} = \psi dE \cdot \psi^3 \frac{1}{dt d\Omega}, \quad (4.3)$$

where dE , dt , and $d\Omega$ corresponds to the energy, time, and solid angle intervals in K . Specifically, in Eq. 4.3, ψdE is the energy transformation term, which represents the Doppler shift of the wavelengths in K' . The second term, $\psi^3 \frac{1}{dt d\Omega}$, indicates a reduction of the intensity due to the space-time dilation in K' . The solid angle element can be transformed as $d\Omega = \psi^2 d\Omega'$, and the time interval as $dt = \psi dt'$.

It should be noted that Eqs. 4.1 and 4.3 corresponds to Eqs. 3.2, describing the relativistic beaming of the gas emission. In fact, another way of describing the reduction of the luminosity seen by the outflowing gas is the following. In K' , the luminosity source appears to be moving away with velocity v_{out} and $\theta = 0 \text{ deg}$ (for a pure radial motion), which results in a de-boosting

Figure 4.2: From left to right and top to bottom: input spectrum $S_I(K)$; $S_I(K')$, obtained panel a) by multiplying the frequencies by ψ (red arrows) and the intensities by ψ^3 (cyan arrows); $S_T(K')$; $S_T(K') \cdot \psi^{-1}$, obtained from panel c) dividing the frequencies by ψ (violet arrows); $S_{out}(K)$, the relativistic-corrected absorption spectrum.

of the received luminosity due to the relativistic beaming, according to Eq. 4.1.

4.2 Inclusion of special relativity effects for absorption

We include these special relativity corrections in modelling spectral absorption features from the outflowing gas, according to the following procedure. For clarity, we also provide a graphical example of the algorithm in Fig. 4.2, to which we will refer in the steps below.

Following Eq. 4.3, the incident spectrum $S_I(K)$ (panel a) is transformed in the outflowing gas reference frame by multiplying the frequencies by a factor ψ and the intensity by a factor ψ^3 . The resulting spectrum is $S_I(K')$ (panel b).

For a given set of outflow parameters ($N_H, \log(\xi_0), n_0, v_{out}$), we run an *XSTAR* simulation by using $S_I(K')$ as incident spectrum. As a result we obtain the transmitted spectrum $S_T(K')$ displaying the absorption features due to the outflowing gas (panel c).

We then calculate the difference spectrum as follows:

$$S_{T-I}(K') = S_T(K') - S_I(K') \quad (4.4)$$

Accordingly, $S_{T-I}(K')$ represents the absorption features produced by the outflowing gas, with the relativistic-corrected optical depth. As the next step we calculate the relativistic-corrected,

rest-frame absorbed spectrum as:

$$S_{out}(K) = S_I(K) + S_{T-I}(K') \cdot \psi^{-1}, \quad (4.5)$$

where $S_{T-I}(K') \cdot \psi^{-1}$ represents the difference spectrum in rest frame (K) frequencies, which is obtained by dividing the frequencies by a factor ψ (panel d). Using Eq. 4.4, we can rewrite Eq. 4.5 as:

$$S_{out}(K) = S_I(K) \cdot \Delta + S_T(K') \cdot \psi^{-1} \quad (4.6)$$

where $\Delta \equiv 1 - \psi^3$ and $S_I(K) \cdot \Delta$ indicates a scaling of the intensity of the spectrum $S_I(K)$ of a factor Δ . Panel e shows S_{out} (solid line), together with $S_I(K) \cdot \Delta$ and $S_T(K') \cdot \psi^{-1}$ (dashed lines), from bottom to top, respectively.

We note that in the low-velocity limit $v_{out} \ll c$, $\Psi \approx 1$, $\Delta \approx 0$, and the resulting spectrum is $S_{out}(K) = S_T(K') \cdot \psi^{-1}$, as is usually calculated. For the opposite high-velocity regime $v_{out} \rightarrow c$, $\Psi \approx 0$, and the outflowing gas does not interact with the ionising radiation. In fact, $S_I(K')$ and $S_T(K')$ have null intensity (see Eq. 4.3), $\Delta \approx 1$, and $S_{out}(K) \approx S_I(K)$.

In our calculations we assume that the outflow has a net velocity v_{out} and direction θ . From a physical point of view, v_{out} and θ correspond to the average velocity and direction of the outflow, respectively. Therefore, if a turbulent velocity component is present, the above discussion is still valid, provided that $v_{turb} \ll v_{out}$. Furthermore, if the outflowing velocity is a function of the spatial coordinates (i.e. $v_{out} = v(\vec{r})$) the above procedure can be implemented by dividing the outflow into small slabs, and assuming v_{out} to be constant in each of them. This procedure corresponds to the general adopted algorithm to reproduce a scaling of the outflow properties with r in the majority of wind models (Schurch & Done, 2007; Saez & Chartas, 2011; Fukumura et al., 2010, 2014; Hagino et al., 2015), as well as in the preliminary and final versions of WINE (Sect. 3 and 6, respectively). Finally, the treatment of more complicated scenarios for $v(\vec{r})$ requires a radically different approach, such as the Monte Carlo simulation of the photon paths (also known as "ray tracing", Sim et al., 2008, 2010a,b).

As discussed in Sect. 2.3, the emissivities of all the atomic lines listed in the *XSTAR* atomic database are saved in a separated file. In Sect. 6 we will use them to build relativistic-corrected outflow emission profiles, using the Monte Carlo approach illustrated in Sect. 3. These profiles will be combined with the absorption ones to obtain self-consistent wind emission and absorption spectra.

Figure 4.3 shows the X-ray spectrum in the range 6 – 16 keV of a power-law continuum source with $\Gamma = 2$ and an ionising luminosity $L_{ion} = 5 \cdot 10^{46} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ in the 1-1000 Ry (1 Ry= 13.6 eV) energy interval, modified by an absorber with $v_{out} = 0.0, 0.3$, and $0.5 c$. In all cases, we assume an absorbing column density of $N_H = 6 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and an ionisation

Figure 4.3: Absorption spectra for increasing outflow velocity: $v_{out} = 0.00$ (left panel), $= 0.30$ (centre panel), $= 0.50 c$ (right panel). For comparison, in the centre and right panels we show the absorption spectrum for $v_{out} = 0.00 c$ (in light grey). See Sect. 4.2 for details on the spectral parameters used in this simulation.

parameter $\log\left(\frac{\xi}{\text{erg cm s}^{-1}}\right) = 4.5$, as for UFOs (see Sect. 1.3.2). The middle and right panels of Fig. 4.3 also report the $v_{out} = 0$ case for an easier comparison. It can be seen that the absorption features related to the relativistically outflowing gas are both blueshifted and significantly weaker than the $v = 0$ case. This effect dramatically increases for increasing velocity, as shown in a more quantitative way in Fig. 4.4, which displays the column density N_H necessary to reproduce outflow absorption features with a fixed optical depth, as a function of v_{out} . The required column density corresponds to $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for $v_{out} = 0$, and it increases by an order of magnitude for $v_{out} = 0.8c$. It is interesting to note that this effect may introduce an observational bias in current X-ray data, which are typically restricted to $E < 10 \text{ keV}$, making outflows at higher velocity more difficult to detect due to the weakening of their spectral features at $E < 10 \text{ keV}$.

We also note that Schurch & Done (2007) and Saez & Chartas (2011) presented AGN outflow models including special relativity effects to provide an estimate of both N_H and ξ . However, the two studies seem not to account properly for the reduction of the optical depth in the calculation of $S_{out}(K)$. In Eq. 4.6 the relativistic-corrected optical depth of the wind is preserved by transforming the transmitted spectrum back to the source rest frame K , while this aspect has not been considered in these studies. They do, however, draw the attention to an interesting implication regarding ξ . Since this parameter describes the ionisation status of the outflowing gas, it has to be calculated using L' rather than L , as well as $n' = n/\gamma, r' = \Upsilon r$,

Figure 4.4: Absorbing gas N_H required to reach a given value of the optical depth as a function of v_{out} . Spectral parameters are as in Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.5: Same of Fig. 4.3, but keeping ξ_{teo} constant between the different runs.

where $\Upsilon = 1 + (\gamma - 1)\cos(\theta)$ (Mihalas & Mihalas, 1984; Rybicki & Lightman, 1986), so that $\xi = \frac{L'}{n'(r')^2} = \frac{L'}{n(\Upsilon r)^2/\gamma}$. We used this definition for the simulations in Fig. 4.3 where, indeed, it can be seen that the ratio between the different absorption lines (i.e., the ratio between different ionic populations) is constant. Instead, keeping $\xi_{teo} \equiv \frac{L}{nr^2}$ fixed with increasing v_{out} leads to a

decreasing ionisation status, as shown in Fig. 4.5: in fact, for $\theta = 0$, the luminosity received by the wind decreases as $\left(\frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta}\right)^2$ and $n'r'$ goes as $nr/\gamma = nr \cdot \sqrt{1-\beta^2}$, so putting all together we obtain $\xi_{teo} = \xi \cdot \frac{(1-\beta)^{5/2}}{(1+\beta)^{3/2}}$. When $v = 0.0$ (left panel), $\xi_{teo} = \xi = 10^{4.5}$, while for $v = 0.30, = 0.50c$ the value of ξ_{teo} decreases to $10^{3.9}$ and $10^{3.5}$, respectively.

We note that it is important to take into account the transformations between n', r' and n, r when performing time-evolving photoionisation (see Sect. 1.3.1 and Nicastro et al., 1999). For those cases in which it is possible to constrain the wind density, i.e. n' , through the ionisation variation timescale, the wind distance from the ionising source can be estimated as $r' = \sqrt{\frac{L'}{\xi n'}}$, and then r can be calculated using the above relation.

4.3 Impact of the corrections on the observed UFO population

Neglecting special relativity effects results in a significant underestimate of N_H and, in turn, of \dot{M}_{out} and \dot{E}_{out} . As an example, we correct for these effects in the reported values of $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$ for the UFOs observed in AGNs from Gofford et al. (2015) and Fiore et al. (2017). Specifically, for the UFOs in Gofford et al. (2015) we use the average values between the reported $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$ calculated using r_{min} and those using r_{max} , where r_{min} (r_{max}) is the minimum (maximum) inferred launching radius. Values of $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$ reported in Fiore et al. (2017) are calculated in the same way. In Figure 4.6 we plot the ratio of the relativistic-corrected energy rates \dot{E}_{out}^{rel} to the original values \dot{E}_{out}^0 as a function of v_{out} . The value of \dot{E}_{out}^{rel} is a factor of > 2 higher than \dot{E}_{out}^0 for the fastest observed outflows ($v_{out} \geq 0.3c$).

As shown in Fig. 4.4, we expect even higher ratios for higher velocity outflows. In this respect, the improved sensitivity and resolution of the next generation X-ray telescopes, such as *XRISM* and *Athena*, will be particularly promising and it will allow us to partially overcome the observational bias discussed in Sect. 4.2. Interestingly, evidence for velocities $\geq 0.4 - 0.5c$ have indeed already been reported for some high-luminosity quasars, such as PDS 456 and APM 08279+5255 (Reeves et al., 2018a; Chartas et al., 2009).

Figure 4.7 shows the ratio of the relativistic-corrected mass loss rate \dot{M}_{out}^{rel} to the mass accretion rate \dot{M}_{acc} , as a function of $\lambda_{Edd} \equiv L_{bol}/L_{Edd}$ (i.e. the ratio between the bolometric and Eddington luminosities). We derive the mass accretion rate as $\dot{M}_{acc} = \frac{L_{bol}}{\eta c^2}$, assuming $\eta = 0.1$ as for a thin accretion disc (see Sect. 1.2.1). We note that for almost half of the sources $\frac{\dot{M}_{out}^{rel}}{\dot{M}_{acc}} \geq 1$, indicating that \dot{M}_{out}^{rel} is comparable to (or higher than) the mass accretion rate of the disc. This may indicate a limit for the outflow lifetime, after which the accretion disc is depleted and it can no longer sustain the outflow (see e.g. Belloni et al., 1997). The plot also shows an apparent lack of sources with $\frac{\dot{M}_{out}^{rel}}{\dot{M}_{acc}} > 1$ at high λ_{Edd} . However, the sample is too small to allow

Figure 4.6: Ratio of the relativistic-corrected energy transfer rates \dot{E}_{out}^{rel} to the original values \dot{E}_{out}^0 as a function of v_{out} , for a sample of ultra-fast outflows observed in AGNs (see Sect. 4.3 for details).

us to draw any conclusions. Future observations of high λ_{Edd} AGNs are needed to shed light on this aspect.

Finally, we compare the outflow momentum rate, defined as $\dot{P}_{out} = \dot{M}_{out} v_{out}$, with the momentum rate of the radiation of the AGN (i.e. $\dot{P}_{rad} = \frac{L_{bol}}{c}$). We obtain a median $\frac{\dot{P}_{out}}{\dot{P}_{rad}}$ value of 0.64 for the original sample, and 0.96 after the relativistic correction. Interestingly, the latter value is consistent with unity, as expected for outflows accelerated through radiation pressure (see Sect. 2.1 and King & Pounds, 2015).

It is worth noting that in Eq. 4.2 we use the total gas velocity v_{out} . We assume that the velocity v_{los} along the LOS coincides with v_{out} . As a result, the derived relativistic correction must be regarded as a conservative limit. The correction would increase in the presence of an additional velocity component v_{\perp} perpendicular to the LOS, which implies $v_{out} = \sqrt{v_{los}^2 + v_{\perp}^2}$.

As an example, we consider the MHD model presented by Fukumura et al. (2010, 2014), where the outflowing gas is launched from the accretion disc at Keplerian velocity. Close to the launching radius, most of the velocity is in the direction of the disc rotation ϕ , and it is converted to radial velocity at higher distances (i.e. close to the Alfvén point). For a wind launched at $r_0 = 10r_G$ the rotational speed has a roughly constant value of $v_{\phi} = 0.3c$ until $r \approx 100r_G$, while the radial velocity (i.e. the component parallel to the LOS) has an average value of $v_{LOS} \approx 0.2c$. In Figure 4.1 we show that when $v_{out} = 0$, $\Psi = 1$ and the relativistic effects are absent. On the other hand, when $v_{out} \rightarrow c$, $\Psi \approx 0$ and the effects are the highest. Using v_{LOS} as a proxy for

Figure 4.7: Ratio of the relativistic-corrected outflow mass rate \dot{M}_{out}^{rel} to the inflow mass rate \dot{M}_{acc} , as a function of $\lambda_{Edd} \equiv L_{bol}/L_{Edd}$. The sample is as in Fig. 4.6. The dotted line corresponds to $\frac{\dot{M}_{out}^{rel}}{\dot{M}_{acc}} = 1$.

v_{out} in Eq. 4.2 yields $\Psi = 0.8$, while using the total velocity (i.e. the composition between v_r and v_ϕ) gives $\Psi = 0.6$, a factor of 0.25 lower.

5. Radiative wind driving

In Section 4 we discussed the importance of special relativity effects for UFO-like velocities. The radiative power received by the outflow decreases with increasing v : with respect to a layer of gas at rest, the amount of radiation impinging on the wind is reduced of $\sim 30\%$ for $v = 0.1 c$, and of $\sim 90\%$ for $v = 0.5 c$. As a result, the radiative driving scenario has to be revised to incorporate these effects.

Similarly, broad absorption lines (BALs) in the UV regime are observed in $\sim 10 - 20\%$ of optically selected quasars. As detailed in Sect. 1.4, their velocities can be up to $0.3c$ and are located at parsec-scales from the SMBH (Hamann et al., 2018; Bruni et al., 2019), thus representing another potential energy input for a galactic-scale feedback. As for the X-ray winds, radiative driving has been suggested as their main driver (Elvis, 2000; Matthews et al., 2020)

In this Section, based on Luminari et al. (2021), we integrate the equation of motion for a wind launched at accretion disc scales in order to assess the impact of special relativity effects on radiative acceleration. We will mainly focus on X-ray winds; however, our results applies to BAL winds as well.

5.1 One-dimensional, spherically symmetric wind model

In order to have a glimpse on the importance of special relativity effects, we start from a simple toy model as follows. We assume that all the luminosity comes from a central point source and the gas has an initial velocity v_0 at a distance r_0 from the centre. We solve the equation of motion along the radial coordinate r . According to the Euler momentum equation, the force exerted by a radiative pressure gradient ∇p on an infinitesimal wind element with density ρ is:

$$\rho \frac{dv(t)}{dt} = \nabla p - \frac{GM_{BH}\rho}{r^2} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\frac{dv}{dt}$ is the wind acceleration and G, M_{BH} are the gravitational constant and the SMBH mass, respectively. For the sake of simplicity, we assume for the moment that i) the wind is optically thin and ii) its opacity is dominated by the Thomson cross-section. We will relax these

assumptions in the following. This way, we obtain an equation of motion for the wind:

$$\frac{dv(t)}{dt} = \frac{L'k}{4\pi r^2 c} - \frac{GM_{BH}}{r^2} \quad (5.2)$$

Where L' is the central luminosity in the wind reference frame K' and k is the opacity of the wind, that we approximate as $k = \frac{\sigma_T}{m_p}$, where σ_T, m_p are the Thomson cross-section and the proton mass, respectively (Rybicki & Lightman, 1986). In the definition of L' we include special relativity effects as in Section 4, so that $L' = L \cdot \Psi$, where L is the luminosity in the source frame K and $\Psi = \psi^4 = \frac{1}{\gamma^4(1+\beta\cos(\theta))^4}$, where γ is the Lorentz factor, $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$ and θ is the angle between the velocity of the gas and the incident luminosity L .

For a wind that is moving radially outward, $\theta = 0deg$, the luminosity can be written as $L' = L \frac{(1-\beta)^2}{(1+\beta)^2}$. We can rewrite Eq. 5.2 as:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = L \frac{(1-\beta)^2}{(1+\beta)^2} \frac{\sigma_T}{4\pi r^2 c m_p} - \frac{GM_{BH}}{r^2} \quad (5.3)$$

Where r and β are functions of v itself. The complete set of equations, including initial conditions, can be written as:

$$\frac{dv(t)}{dt} = L \frac{(1 - \frac{v(t)}{c})^2}{(1 + \frac{v(t)}{c})^2} \frac{\sigma_T}{4\pi r(t)^2 c m_p} - \frac{GM_{BH}}{r^2} \quad (5.4a)$$

$$r(t) = r_0 + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v(t) dt \quad (5.4b)$$

$$r_0 = r(t = t_0) \quad (5.4c)$$

$$v_0 = v(t = t_0) \quad (5.4d)$$

Where t_0, t_1 are the starting and ending time of the numerical integration, respectively. Moreover, we assume that the launching velocity of the wind v_0 corresponds to the rotational velocity of an accretion disc, orbiting around the black hole with a Keplerian profile, at $r = r_0$, so that $v_0 = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{BH}}{r_0}}$. Albeit this choice of v_0 may seem arbitrary at this point, it will be useful to compare the results with those of the following Sections. We also note that the escape velocity

at $r = r_0$ is equal to $\sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r_0}} = \sqrt{2}v_0$. We can rewrite Eqs. 5.4 as:

$$\frac{dv(t)}{dt} = \left(\lambda_{Edd} \frac{(1 - v(t))^2}{(1 + v(t))^2} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{r(t)^2} \quad (5.5a)$$

$$r(t) = r_0 + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v(t) dt \quad (5.5b)$$

$$r_0 = r(t = t_0) \quad (5.5c)$$

$$v_0 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{r_0}} \quad (5.5d)$$

where λ_{Edd} is the luminosity in units of the Eddington luminosity $L_{Edd} = \frac{4\pi GM_{BH} m_p c}{\sigma_T}$, r, t are in units of the gravitational radius and time, $r_G = \frac{GM_{BH}}{c^2}$, $t_G = \frac{r_G}{c}$ respectively, and v is in units of c . We span the interval between 5 and 500 r_G for r_0 , to encompass the typical launching radius of UFOs, which usually lies between ~ 50 and some hundreds r_G (Tombesi et al., 2012, 2013; Nardini et al., 2015; Tombesi et al., 2015; Laurenti et al., 2020). We divide this interval in five logarithmically-spaced steps: $r_0 \in [5.0, 15.8, 50.0, 158.1, 500.0]r_G$. As we will discuss in detail in Sect. 5.4, we note that the assumption of a point source may be less accurate for launching radii smaller than $50.0r_G$. Nonetheless, it is instructive to study the solutions down to the smallest radii to identify possible trends. We integrate the equation for $10^6 t_G$, after which the dynamics of the wind reaches a steady state and the velocity appears to be almost constant in all the cases. We note that $10^6 t_G$ corresponds to $\sim 1(100) yrs$ for $M_{BH} = 10^7(10^9)M_\odot$, while present-day X-ray observations have observation times smaller than a month. This will allow us to follow the wind dynamics for a sufficient time scale to compare with the observations for any value of M_{BH} inside the typical AGN range. We find that the wind evolution is best sampled by a logarithmic time grid, rather than by linear steps. We fix the number of time elements to $5 \cdot 10^6$ to obtain an optimal numerical accuracy. Using a higher resolution does not produce noticeable improvements in the solutions.

We show in Figure 5.1 the numerical result of Eqs. 5.5 for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$. For comparison, we also show the classic analogue of Eq. 5.5, i.e., without the luminosity reduction factor Ψ due to relativistic effects. Hereafter, we will indicate with solid(dashed) lines the values relative to the relativistic(classic) treatment, if not stated otherwise. Since we input a luminosity corresponding to the Eddington limit, $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$, in the classic case the radiative pressure is able to counteract (by definition) the gravitational pull from the black hole. As a result, the acceleration of the gas is null and we obtain constant velocity solutions. Once the wind is launched with a given v_0 , it escapes from the system with constant $v = v_0$, as can be seen in the right panel of Fig. 5.1.

As expected, relativistic effects reduce radiation pressure, resulting in a deceleration of the

Figure 5.1: Left: $r(t)$ as a function of t for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$ and $v_0 = v_{rot} = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{BH}}{r_0}}$; Right: $v(t)$ as a function of $r(t)$. Solid lines indicate the trajectories in the relativistic framework (Eqs. 5.5), while dashed lines correspond to the classic (i.e., non-relativistic) ones.

wind under the gravitational pull of the SMBH. Indeed, it can be seen that the wind trajectories, especially the ones at smaller radii (i.e., closer to the black hole) undergo a significant velocity reduction. In the extreme case of $r_0 = 5r_G$, the velocity drops to 0. When $v = 0$, relativistic effects vanish and radiation pressure is able, as in the classic case, to sustain the wind against the gravitational force, leading to a "stalling wind". The highest final velocity is given by the case with $r_0 = 50r_G$ and it is $\approx 0.1c$, consistent with the typical observed UFO velocities (e.g., Tombesi et al., 2011; Gofford et al., 2015).

5.2 Preliminary model of an axisymmetric wind launched from an accretion disk

Let us now rewrite Eq. 5.5 in the case of a wind launched from an accretion disc. We assume axisymmetry and a geometrically thin disc, such as in Shakura & Sunyaev (1973), orbiting with a Keplerian profile. We adopt a cylindrical coordinate system (R, ϕ, z) . The set of equations is

then:

$$\frac{dv_R}{dt} = \left(\frac{\lambda_{Edd}}{\gamma^4(1 + \beta \cos\theta)^4} - 1 \right) \frac{R}{r^3} + \frac{l^2}{R^3} \quad (5.6a)$$

$$\frac{dv_z}{dt} = \left(\frac{\lambda_{Edd}}{\gamma^4(1 + \beta \cos\theta)^4} - 1 \right) \frac{z}{r^3} \quad (5.6b)$$

$$R = R_0 + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v_R dt \quad (5.6c)$$

$$z = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v_z dt \quad (5.6d)$$

$$r = \sqrt{R^2 + z^2} \quad (5.6e)$$

$$\vec{v}_0 = \vec{v}(t = t_0) = (0, v_{rot}, v_{z,0}) \quad (5.6f)$$

$$\vec{r}_0 = \vec{r}(t = t_0) = (R_0, 0, 0) \quad (5.6g)$$

where, as in Eqs. 5.5, r, t are in units of r_G, t_G , θ is the angle between the incident luminosity and the direction of motion of the gas and we assume that the luminosity source is point-like. Hereafter, we indicate in bold the vectorial quantities. In the first two equations, the second term in the right-hand bracket corresponds to the gravitational attraction. l is the specific angular momentum (angular momentum per unit mass), which is a conserved quantity during the motion. \vec{r}_0, \vec{v}_0 are the starting radius and velocity, respectively. We assume that, initially, the gas lies on the disk plane and the starting velocity lifts the gas above the disk, along the z coordinate, with a velocity proportional to the disc rotational velocity $v_{rot} = \sqrt{\frac{l}{r_0}}$. The velocity along the ϕ coordinate is updated at each step to ensure the conservation of l . These initial conditions are rather general, and represents a good approximation of the radiatively-driven wind scenario (Proga et al., 2000; Proga & Kallman, 2004), as well as the magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) scenario, in which the gas is lifted through magnetic field lines co-rotating with the disk (Blandford & Payne, 1982; Contopoulos & Lovelace, 1994; Fukumura et al., 2010, 2014; Cui & Yuan, 2020; see also Sect. 2.1).

Fig. 5.2 shows the solutions of Eqs. 5.6 for $R_0 = [5.0, 15.8, 50.0, 158.1, 500.0]r_G$, an integration time of $10^6 t_G$, a logarithmic temporal resolution of $5 \cdot 10^6$ steps, as in Sect. 5.1, $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$ and $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$. For comparison, we also show the corresponding classic solutions. As expected, the highest differences are observed at smaller radii, where the velocity is higher and the relativistic effects are stronger. We present in Fig. 5.3 the evolution of the distance and velocity of the wind with time.

Hereafter, we concentrate on the outflow velocity, defined as $v_{out} = \sqrt{v_R^2 + v_z^2}$, rather than on the total wind velocity $v = \sqrt{v_R^2 + v_\phi^2 + v_z^2}$, to better compare our results with observations.

Figure 5.2: Wind trajectories for $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ and $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$. From left to right: trajectories of the wind in the $z - R$ plane; outflow velocity v_{out} as a function of r (where $v_{out} = \sqrt{v_R^2 + v_z^2}$); v_{out} as a function of t . Solid(dashed) lines refer to the relativistic(classic) treatment.

Figure 5.3: Wind trajectories for $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ and $\lambda_{Edd} = 1$. From left to right: distance r from the BH (where $r = \sqrt{R^2 + z^2}$) as a function of t ; v_R (radial velocity) as a function of t ; v_z (vertical velocity) as a function of t . Bold(thin) lines refer to the relativistic(classic) treatment.

The velocity of the observed UFOs is primarily derived through spectroscopy, thanks to the Doppler shift of the wind absorption lines. These lines are usually described with Gaussian or Voigt profiles, i.e. they have an average energy and some degree of broadening. The observed wind outflow velocity v_{obs} is usually derived from the average velocity, while the broadening is phenomenologically ascribed to turbulence or rotational motion within the wind.

In our model, v_{obs} is given by the projection of $\vec{v}_R + \vec{v}_z$ along the line of sight (LOS), while the rotational velocity v_ϕ only contributes to the broadening of the line, thanks to the axisymmetry of the system. The highest v_{obs} is given by v_{out} , and corresponds to the case in which the LOS is parallel to $\vec{v}_R + \vec{v}_z$. We refer to Fukumura & Tombesi (2019) for a detailed discussion on this point. Interestingly, the authors discuss the possibility that a rotational motion of the wind around the X-ray corona is responsible for the broadening of the absorption lines, in a similar fashion to the discussion here.

5.3 Axisymmetric equation with accurate force multipliers

In the accretion disc wind literature, the wind opacity is usually calculated from the force multiplier M_{rad} , encompassing a broad range of absorption lines in the UV and X-ray energy range (see e.g. Proga & Kallman, 2004; Risaliti & Elvis, 2010; Sim et al., 2010b; Dyda & Proga, 2018; Quera-Bofarull et al., 2020). Here, we use the *XSTAR* code (Kallman & Bautista, 2001). Saez & Chartas (2011); Chartas et al. (2009) performed calculations in a similar fashion using Cloudy photoionisation code (Ferland et al., 2017), albeit with a different formalism.

As discussed in Sect. 2.2, *XSTAR* computes the transmitted spectrum S_T through the wind, as a function of the following input quantities:

- S_I , the incident spectrum, and the ionising luminosity L_I^{ion} .
- r_0 , the distance of the gas from the central luminosity source
- n_0 , the gas number density at r_0
- N_H , its column density
- α , the coefficient regulating the radial dependence of n : $n = n_0 \cdot (\frac{r_0}{r})^\alpha$
- v_{broad} , the gas velocity dispersion regulating the broadening of the absorption features.

The difference $L_I - L_T$ (where L_I, L_T are the integrated luminosity of S_I, S_T) corresponds to the amount of radiation absorbed by the wind thanks to its opacity. This difference corresponds to a momentum Δp deposited on the wind, which can be written as $\Delta p = \frac{L_I - L_T}{c} = \frac{L_I \cdot f_{rad}}{c}$, where

we introduce the new variable $f_{rad} = \frac{L_I - L_T}{L_I}$. Specifically, for a given set of initial parameters $[S_I, r_0, n_0, N_H, \alpha, v_{broad}]$ we run an *XSTAR* simulation and we calculate f_{rad} as:

$$f_{rad} = \frac{\int_{E_0}^{E_1} s_\nu^I - s_\nu^T}{\int_{E_0}^{E_1} s_\nu^I} d\nu \quad (5.7)$$

where E_0, E_1 correspond to the lower and upper energy bound and s_ν^I, s_ν^T are the incident and transmitted flux, respectively, as functions of the frequency ν , so that $\int s_\nu^I d\nu = S_I$ and $\int s_\nu^T d\nu = S_T$. From a mathematical point of view, f_{rad} corresponds to a weighted average of the wind opacity. In all the cases of interest, absorption features are comprised in the energy interval between 0.1 eV and 100 keV , that we choose as E_0, E_1 , respectively.

As discussed in Sect. 2.2, *XSTAR*, as well as other photoionisation codes such as *Cloudy*, does not allow the inclusion of a net velocity of the gas and the related relativistic effects. In order to take them into account, it is convenient to transform the spectra from the rest frame K to the wind reference frame K' , and to manipulate S_I and S_T , namely to shift their frequencies by a factor ψ and multiply their fluxes by ψ^3 , as explained in Section 4. However, since f_{rad} is calculated as a ratio between S_T and S_I , the transformations cancel out so that f_{rad} can be directly calculated in K without the need of any relativistic transformation.

We integrate the equation of motion, Eq. 5.2, for a radial interval Δr , in which a wind column density N_H is enclosed, and we include the momentum Δp . The resulting equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dv}{dt} &= \frac{\Delta p}{4\pi r^2 m_p N_H} + \frac{L'_{bol} \sigma_T}{4\pi r^2 c m_p} - \frac{GM}{r^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi r^2 c m_p} \cdot \left(\frac{L'_{UX} \cdot f_{rad}}{N_H} + L'_{bol} \cdot \sigma_T \right) - \frac{GM}{r^2} \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

where we also include Thompson scattering and L'_{bol}, L'_{UX} correspond to the bolometric luminosity and the incident luminosity between $E_0 E_1$, respectively. The ' symbol indicates that the luminosities are in the K' frame, i. e. $L'_{bol}(L'_{UX}) = L_{bol}(L_{UX}) \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma^4(1+\beta \cos(\theta))^4}$. It must be noted that, for this equation to hold, Δr must be small enough so that r can be approximated as constant (i.e., $\Delta r \ll r$).

We put ourselves in the same framework of Sect. 5.2 (axisymmetry, thin accretion disk and

conservation of l). The complete set of equations is then:

$$\frac{dv_R}{dt} = \left(\frac{\lambda'_{UX} \cdot f_{rad}}{\sigma_T N_H} + \lambda'_{Edd} - 1 \right) \frac{R}{r^3} + \frac{l^2}{(GM/c)^2 \cdot R^3} \quad (5.9a)$$

$$\frac{dv_z}{dt} = \left(\frac{\lambda'_{UX} \cdot f_{rad}}{\sigma_T N_H} + \lambda'_{Edd} - 1 \right) \frac{z}{r^3} \quad (5.9b)$$

$$R = R_0 + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v_R dt \quad (5.9c)$$

$$z = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v_z dt \quad (5.9d)$$

$$r = \sqrt{R^2 + z^2} \quad (5.9e)$$

$$\vec{v}_0 = (0, v_{rot}, v_{z,0}) \quad (5.9f)$$

$$\vec{r}_0 = (R_0, 0, 0) \quad (5.9g)$$

where, as in Sect. 5.2, r, t are in units of r_G, t_G and $\lambda'_{UX} \equiv L'_{UX}/L_{Edd}$, $\lambda'_{Edd} \equiv L'_{bol}/L_{Edd}$.

5.4 Initial parameters and force multipliers calculation

Since we are primarily interested in winds from AGN accretion discs, we focus on "typical" values of λ_{Edd} between 0.1 and 2 and a black hole mass $M = 10^8 M_\odot$. However, as we show later in this section, the properties of the wind, and then the values of f_{rad} , mainly depend on λ_{Edd} , rather than on M or L_{bol} alone, so our results are applicable regardless of the black hole mass.

We use the bolometric corrections of Lusso et al. (2012) to obtain the 2-10 keV luminosities. We assume a simple power-law incident spectrum with photon index $\Gamma = 2$, consistent with the typical values observed in AGNs (Piconcelli et al., 2005; Tombesi et al., 2011), to extrapolate L_{ion} and L_{UX} .

Regarding the properties of the wind, we concentrate on a set of initial number density $\log(n_0) \in [10, 11, 12, 13] cm^{-3}$ in order to match the ionisation parameters of the observed UFOs, as we will discuss in the following, and a range of $N_H \in [5 \cdot 10^{22}, 10^{24}] cm^{-2}$. As starting radii we use the same set of values of Sect. 5.1 and 5.2: $R_0 \in [5.0, 15.8, 50.0, 158.1, 500.0] r_G$. In our picture, we assume that all the luminosity comes from a point source located at the coordinate origin ($R = 0, z = 0$). However, the X-ray corona is usually comprised within $\sim 10 r_G$ from the SMBH, as discussed in Sect. 1.2.2 (see also Chartas et al., 2012; Reis & Miller, 2013; Reis et al., 2014; Kara et al., 2016; Caballero-Garcia et al., 2020; Szanecki et al., 2020), while the UV radiation is due to the disc emissivity which, for a thin disc, has a peak at $\sim 20 r_G$

(Quera-Bofarull et al., 2020). As a result, we expect that in our code the radiative contribution may not be fully modelled for $R_0 < 50.0r_G$; however, we include the cases for $R_0 = 5.0, 15.8r_G$, since the fate of the wind is governed primarily by v_0 , rather than by the radiation pressure, as we will show later.

We fix α , the exponent regulating the radial dependence of n , to 2, so that $n = n_0(\frac{r_0}{r})^2$, as expected by mass conservation for a medium expanding in a spherical geometry. Since we expect a high degree of velocity shear within the wind due to its acceleration, we use a high turbulent velocity $v_{broad} = 3000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to prevent line saturation. This value is consistent with those typically observed in UFOs (see Fukumura & Tombesi, 2019 and references therein).

We briefly summarise here the range of input quantities of our simulations, from which we calculate a grid of f_{rad} values:

- λ_{Edd} : we divide the interval of interest in four values, logarithmically spaced: $\lambda_{Edd} = [0.1, 0.5, 1., 2.]$.
- n_0 : we divide the range in logarithmic steps: $\log(n_0) \in [10, 11, 12, 13] \text{ cm}^{-3}$
- $r_0 \in [5.0, 15.8, 50.0, 158.1, 500.0]r_G$.
- N_H : we span the range $[5 \cdot 10^{22}, 10^{24}] \text{ cm}^{-2}$ with steps of $5 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

We compute the geometrical thickness of the wind to check whether the $\Delta r \ll r$ condition in Eq. 5.3 is met. The results are plotted in Fig. 5.4 (first three panels). With our density profile $n(r) = n_0(\frac{r_0}{r})^2$ (see Sect. 5.4), the upper limit for the column density corresponds to $N_{H,max} = n_0 r_0$. For all the values of n_0, r_0 in this paper, $N_{H,max} > 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and, moreover $\Delta_R/R_0 < 1$. The only exception is for $n_0 = 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_0 = 5r_G$ (first panel, blue line), for which $N_{H,max} = 7.4 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

However, as we will discuss later, the properties of the wind are quite independent from N_H , and we will focus on the typical UFO value of $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Tombesi et al., 2011) in most of the cases. In the last panel of Fig. 5.4 we show the ionisation parameter $\xi(r)$, defined as $\frac{L_{ion}}{nr^2}$, for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1.0, 0.1$. This parameter is of great importance since the absorption structure of the wind, and then the values of f_{rad} , mainly depends on it. Our range of ξ , from 10^0 to 10^6 , agrees well with the broad population of UFOs and Warm Absorbers (see e.g. Laha et al., 2014; Serafinelli et al., 2019); this, in turn, justifies our range of $\log(n_0)$. Moreover, our values for $\log(n_0)$ are in agreement with those commonly estimated for the Broad Line Region (BLR) and for UV and X-ray outflows (see e.g. Elvis, 2000; Schurch & Done, 2007; Saez & Chartas, 2011; Netzer, 2013). Finally, Fig. 5.5 shows f_{rad} as a function of N_H , for different R_0 (color coding) and $\log(n_0) = 10, 11, 12, 13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (from left to right). From top to bottom, $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$.

5. Radiative wind driving

Figure 5.4: First three panels: geometrical thickness of the wind as a function of N_H for $\log(n_0) = 10, 11, 12, 13$ (color coding) and increasing R_0 (from left to right). Last panel: ionisation parameter as a function of R_0 for different $\log(n_0)$ (color coding) and $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (dashed and solid lines, respectively).

Figure 5.5: Values of f_{rad} as functions of N_H for $\log(n_0) = 10, 11, 12, 13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (from left to right) and $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$ (from top to bottom).

5.4.1 Impact of the initial parameters on the wind dynamics.

We solve the system of Eqs. 5.9 for the whole grid of initial parameters for an integration time of $10^6 t_G$, the same temporal resolution of Sect. 5.1 and using a set of $v_{z,0} \in [1.0, 10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}] v_{rot}$. For a complete discussion of the results, we first analyse the impact of the different parameters. To characterise the wind dynamics, we define a wind successfully launched if it has a positive (outbound) velocity at the end of the integration time $t = t_1$, and we compute its terminal velocity as $v_t = v_{out}(t_1) = \sqrt{v_R(t_1)^2 + v_z(t_1)^2}$.

λ_{Edd} and $v_{z,0}$ are the dominant parameters, since they regulate the amount of radiation pressure and the initial velocity of the wind. When $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$, the high initial velocity allows the wind to be successfully launched for any value of λ_{Edd} (albeit reaching different v_t). For $v_{z,0} = 10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3} v_{rot}$, instead, the impact of the initial velocity itself to the wind evolution is almost negligible, and the different solutions are indistinguishable between them. However, $v_{z,0}$ lifts the gas above the disk, displacing it from its equilibrium radius and exposing it to the radiation pressure. The fate of the wind will then depend on λ_{Edd} and, secondarily, on R_0 , but it is unaffected by the exact value of $v_{z,0}$. We plot in Fig. 5.6 the failed wind region (i.e., the radius up to which the wind cannot be successfully launched) as a function of λ_{Edd} , for different $v_{z,0}$. For $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$, the wind is always successful. Then, the failed region increases for decreasing $v_{z,0}$, and becomes quite constant for $v_{z,0} \leq 10^{-1} v_{rot}$. Please note that in this

Figure 5.6: Failed wind region as a function of λ_{Edd} for different $v_{z,0}$. It can be seen that for $v_{z,0} \leq 10^{-1} v_{rot}$ the region becomes quite constant, since the wind dynamics does not depend anymore on the value of $v_{z,0}$.

Figure we do not take into account wind opacity (i.e., we use the same treatment of Sect. 5.2) due to the long computational times required. However, the overall behaviour of $v_{z,0}$ is similar. For simplicity, from now on we will concentrate only on $v_{z,0} = [10^{-2}, 1.0]v_{rot}$. We note that $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ represents a remarkably high starting velocity, which could be justified only under certain particular physical conditions (see discussion in Sect. 5.6) and is significantly higher from the velocities commonly assumed in the literature, which are closer to the $v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$ case (see e.g. Proga et al., 2000; Nomura et al., 2016, 2020). As we will detail in the following, we run the simulations using this starting value as a case study, in order to set an upper bound for the wind velocities that can be reached through radiative pressure, once corrected for relativistic effects.

For what concerns n_0 , it can give rise to differences in v_t of up to $0.05c$, but it generally does not affect the overall behaviour of the wind. We show in Fig. 5.7 the terminal velocity v_t as a function of R_0 for different n_0 (color coding). From left to right, $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$. Top (bottom) row refers to $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ ($v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$). v_t is similar for any value of n_0 , except for $v_{z,0} = 0.01v_{rot}$ and $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.5, 1.0$, where the initial velocity is low enough (and the luminosity is not too low nor too high) so that different f_{rad} values can give rise to different wind behaviours.

Figure 5.7: Terminal velocity of the wind for $\log(n_0) = 10, 11, 12, 13$ (in units of cm^{-3} , color coding) and for different luminosities (from left to right $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$). In the top(bottom) panel $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ ($v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$). For simplicity, we fix $N_H = 10^{23} cm^{-2}$.

Figure 5.8: Terminal velocity of the wind for $\log(n_0) = 10, 13$ (in units of cm^{-3} , purple and green lines) and $N_H = 5 \cdot 10^{22}$ and $10^{24} cm^{-2}$ (in units of cm^{-2} , solid and dashed lines, respectively). In the top(bottom) panel $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ ($v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$).

Since f_{rad} is always roughly directly proportional to the column density, the wind solutions are also quite independent from N_H , because these two terms balance each other in the first term on the right-hand side of Eqs. 5.9a,b. In Fig. 5.8 we plot v_t for $\log(n_0) = 10, 13 cm^{-3}$ for the lower and upper values of N_H ($5 \cdot 10^{22}$ and $10^{24} cm^{-2}$). It can be seen that the overall dynamics of the wind is weakly sensitive to N_H . We note that this trend holds also for optically-thick winds. In facts, for column densities $\approx \sigma_T^{-1} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{24} cm^{-2}$, line opacity grows equally or less than linearly with N_H (Tombesi et al., 2011), and so the f_{rad}/N_H term in Eqs. 5.9a,b will not contribute more than for the optically-thin wind. From now on we will focus on $\log(n_0) = 11 cm^{-3}, N_H = 10^{23} cm^{-2}$, if not stated otherwise.

5.5 Results

To examine the wind behaviour, we plot in Fig. 5.9 the trajectories in the $R - z$ plane, for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (left and right panels, respectively). Hereafter, we convert the distance from the black hole (x -axis) from r_G to pc assuming $M_{BH} = 10^8 M_\odot$. As discussed in Sect. 5.4.1, the dominant parameter in the wind motion is $v_{z,0}$: for $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ (solid lines) the wind is always successful, while when $v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$ (dashed lines) it can be launched only for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1.0$

Figure 5.9: Trajectories of the wind in the $z - R$ plane (y and x axis, respectively) for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (left and right panel, respectively). Solid(dashed) lines correspond to $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}(10^{-2}v_{rot})$. Thick and thin lines refer to the relativistic and classic (i.e., non-relativistic) treatment. Distances are reported both in units of r_G and pc , where the latter are calculated assuming $M = 10^8 M_\odot$.

and $R_0 > 5r_G$. In Fig. 5.9 and in the followings, a truncated trajectory corresponds to a failed wind, since we interrupt the numerical integration when the gas falls back to the disk plane. Classic and relativistic trajectories (represented with bold and thin lines, respectively) are almost indistinguishable; however, as we will see in the following, their velocities are rather different.

In Fig. 5.10 we show a comparison between the velocities in the relativistic and in the classic treatments as a function of t , for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (left and right panel, respectively). Purple, light blue and green lines corresponds to $R_0 = 5.0, 50.0, 500.0r_G$, respectively. Solid and dashed lines correspond to $v_0 = 1.0$ and $= 10^{-2}v_{rot}$, respectively. The impact of relativistic effects is remarkable, especially in the highest velocity cases. The maximum v_t drops from $\approx 0.6 c$ to less than $0.3 c$ when taking into account the reduction of radiative pressure due to special relativity effects. We also note that, in most of the cases, the wind attains its terminal velocity within $10^4 t_G$ (corresponding to $0.1 yr$, i.e. roughly a month, for $M = 10^8 M_\odot$). For $R_0 = 5r_G$, this time is reduced to $10^3 t_G$ ($10^{-2} yr$, i.e. a few days). For comparison, we indicate the times corresponding to one day and one month with vertical dotted lines.

Figure 5.10: Velocity of the wind as functions of t_G for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (left and right panel, respectively). Line styles as in Fig. 5.9. Times are converted from t_G to yr assuming $M = 10^8 M_\odot$.

Figure 5.11: Velocity vs. distance from the black hole for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1, 1.0$ (left and right panel, respectively). Line styles as in Fig. 5.9. Distances are converted from r_G to pc assuming $M = 10^8 M_\odot$.

In Fig. 5.11 we show the velocity of the wind as a function of the distance from the black hole. To give an idea of the dimensions of the accretion disc - torus system, we also indicate the typical distance at which BLR are observed and the dust sublimation radius, as a proxy of the inner boundary of the torus. We choose $0.01 pc$ as the BLR inner radius and $0.5 pc$ as the dust sublimation radius, which marks the boundary between the BLR and the torus (Coffey et al., 2014; Róžańska et al., 2014; Adhikari et al., 2016; Sturm et al., 2018; Czerny, 2019). By comparing Fig. 5.11 with Fig. 5.10 it can be seen that the wind reaches BLR-like distances after ~ 1 month, possibly suggesting an interaction with the gas in the BLR orbiting above the accretion disc.

For a detailed analysis of the wind dynamics we show in Fig. 5.12 the case for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1, v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$.

Figure 5.12: Wind solutions in the relativistic and classic cases (solid and dashed lines) for $\lambda_{Edd} = 1, v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ and taking into account the wind opacity. From top to bottom and left to right: distance r from the BH (where $r = \sqrt{R^2 + z^2}$) as a function of t ; outflow velocity v_{out} as a function of r ($v_{out} = \sqrt{v_R^2 + v_z^2}$); v_{out} as a function of t ; trajectories of the wind in the $z - R$ plane; v_R (radial velocity) as a function of t ; v_z (vertical velocity) as a function of t . Bold(thin) lines refer to the relativistic(classic) treatment.

Figure 5.13: Terminal velocities v_t as functions of R_0 for different values of λ_{Edd} (color coding). Solid lines refer to the relativistic treatment, dashed to the classic (i.e., non-relativistic) one. In the left panel $v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}v_{rot}$, in the right panel $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$.

5.6 Comparison with the observed UFO population

To have an idea of the overall behaviour of the wind, we plot (Fig. 5.13) v_t as a function of R_0 for $v_{z,0} = 10^{-2}, 1.0 v_{rot}$ (left and right panel). We also plot with dashed lines v_t obtained in the classic case. The null values indicate an unsuccessful wind. In order for the wind to attain the typical velocities of UFOs, i.e. $\gtrsim 0.1c$, either the luminosity must be very high ($\lambda_{Edd} \geq 1.0$) or the initial velocity $v_{z,0}$, must be comparable to the rotational velocity v_{rot} .

In Fig. 5.14 we plot v_t as a function of ξ_0 (which is a monotonically decreasing function of R_0) in the densest and in the lightest cases, i.e. $\log(n_0) = 10$ and $= 13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1$ and $= 1.0$ (left and right panels, respectively). Generally, v_t is found to be a monotonically increasing function of ξ (see e.g. Tombesi et al., 2013). Interestingly, this behaviour can be reproduced only with $v_{z,0} \propto v_{rot}$, lending support to the evidence discussed above.

We now compare our results with UFOs from the literature. Our goal is to establish whether the observed UFOs velocities can be reproduced within our radiative driving framework. To do so, we consider two different limiting velocities emerging from our results. The first one is the terminal velocity, v_t , which is almost reached by the wind after a very short time, and thus is the most likely to be observed. The second one is the maximum velocity reached by the wind, v_{max} , which is associated with the short-living, initial phases of the wind motion (see Figs. 5.10,

Figure 5.14: v_t as functions of ξ_0 for $\log(n_0) = 10, 13$ (in units of cm^{-3} , yellow and gray lines, respectively). Solid and dashed lines refer to $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ and $= 10^{-2}v_{rot}$, respectively. In the left panel $\lambda_{Edd} = 0.1$, in the right panel $= 1.0$.

5.11), and hence represents an upper limit of the observable velocity. Since we are interested in the highest possible velocities, we focus on the $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ cases.

We compute the highest values of v_t, v_{max} as a function of λ_{Edd} for $R_0 \geq 50r_G$, that represents a lower bound for the launching radius of the observed UFOs (see discussion in Sect. 5.1). We plot the results in Fig. 5.15, denoting with dark orange and blue the regions below the curves of v_t, v_{max} , respectively. These regions correspond to the allowed velocity ranges.

We assemble a sample of all UFO sources reported in the literature for which robust estimates of λ_{Edd}, v_{out} are available, as shown in Table 5.1. The sample is composed by three main groups. The first one is taken from the Tombesi et al. (2011) sample, with the updated L_{bol} from Fiore et al. (2017), while the second one is from Gofford et al. (2015). The third one comprises the sources reported in Fiore et al. (2017) and not previously reported in Tombesi et al. (2011), together with other individually-reported UFOs published from 2017 on for which robust estimates of both λ_{Edd} and v_{out} are available. Where possible, the black hole mass M_{BH} and the AGN bolometric luminosity L_{bol} have been updated with recent works, listed in the last column.

We plot the UFOs from our sample with different symbols (see legend). Interestingly, many points lie above the v_t (orange) allowed region, and many also above the v_{max} (blue) region. Such high velocities, which can be hardly explained within our radiative driving model, may

Figure 5.15: Comparison between UFO velocities from the literature (dots and squares) and the results of the present work as a function of λ_{Edd} . Theoretical limit according to the terminal velocity v_t for $R_0 \geq 50r_G$ corresponds to the orange shaded area. Limit according to the maximum (but short-lived) velocity v_{max} corresponds to the light blue area. See Table 5.1 for a description of the sample and the related references.

lend support to other launching mechanisms. As discussed in Sect. 5.4.1, $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ represents an upper bound of the expected launching velocities for a radiatively-driven wind. Lower, physically-motivated $v_{z,0}$ would result in even lower limiting velocities than those reported in Fig. 5.15, thus strengthening our conclusion that radiative driving, once corrected for special relativity effects, is not sufficient to produce the observed UFO velocity distribution.

Particularly, we signal the possibility of a magnetocentrifugal acceleration mechanism, which is capable to drive the wind up to very high terminal velocities. Typical values are $\sim 1 - 3$ times the rotational velocity at the wind launching radius R_0 (Fukumura et al., 2010, 2014; Tombesi et al., 2013; Cui & Yuan, 2020). For $R_0 = 50r_G$, this corresponds to terminal velocities between 0.14-0.42 c , thus easily accounting for the observed UFO velocities.

Although many of the UFO reported velocities could, in principle, be explained through the terminal velocity of a radiatively-driven wind with both $R_0 \geq 50r_G$ and $v_{z,0} = v_{rot}$ (see Fig.

5.13), we rule out this hypothesis for two main reasons. First, such small R_0 is significantly lower than the launching radii commonly estimated for UFOs and would be in competition with the size of the X-ray corona and with the disc region where most of the UV luminosity is produced (see Sect 5.1 and 5.4). Secondly, the total launching velocity would correspond to a very high value: $|v_0| = \sqrt{v_{rot}^2 + v_{z,0}^2} = \sqrt{2} \cdot v_{rot} = 0.63c$, very difficult to justify for a steady state accretion disc (see discussion below).

Finally, we signal two interesting implications of our results. Several observations show the simultaneous presence in AGN X-ray spectra of fast absorbers with comparable $v_{out} \sim 0.1 - 0.2c$ and orders of magnitude differences between their ξ (Longinotti et al., 2015; Serafinelli et al., 2019; Reeves et al., 2020). This evidence can be easily explained within our model. The weak dependence of the outflow solutions from n indicates that different wind elements can be launched with similar velocity (and column density) but rather different ionisation parameters, as shown in Fig. 5.14. This, in turn, is due to the sub-dominant contribution of the force multipliers (and then of the line driving) with respect to Thompson scattering, as outlined also in Dannen et al. (2019).

Secondly, failed winds (FW) are a natural outcome in any radiative driven scenario, as shown in Sect. 2.1. In fact, in our analysis we show that successful winds can be launched only through very high launching velocities ($v_{z,0} \propto v_{rot}$) or extreme $\lambda_{Edd} (\gtrsim 1)$. However, many AGNs hosting UFOs have $\lambda_E \sim 0.1$ (see Fig. 5.15), and such high $v_{z,0}$ are very difficult to justify in the framework of a steady-state accretion disc, unless postulating a "kick velocity" through hydrodynamic instabilities (see e.g. Janiuk & Czerny, 2011 and references therein), disc magnetic reconnection (Di Matteo, 1998; Ergun et al., 2020; Ripperda et al., 2020) or, again, resorting to a large scale MHD-driven outflow (see Yuan et al., 2015 for numerical simulations). Within the dynamics of the accretion-ejection system, we expect the FW to act as a shield for the gas launched at higher R_0 , possibly regulating its ionisation status and observational properties (Giustini & Proga, 2019, 2020). However, we note that the effectiveness of FW in favouring the launching of more distant layers of gas has not been proven yet, as detailed in Sect. 2.1.2 (see also Higginbottom et al., 2014; Zappacosta et al., 2020 and references therein). Within our picture, FW are confined into a narrow equatorial region (i.e., their z height is \ll than the radial coordinate r , see Fig. 5.9), since the gravitational attraction prevents them from reaching high altitudes before bouncing back to the accretion disc, making them particularly difficult to observe. A careful modelling of the wind duty cycle and of the disc region is needed in order to further shed light on this topic.

Group	Name	λ_{Edd}	v (c)	Refs.
1	NGC4151	0.05 ± 0.01	0.106 ± 0.007	A
	IC4329A	0.08 ± 0.03	0.098 ± 0.004	
	Mrk509	0.09 ± 0.01	0.173 ± 0.004	A
	Mrk509	0.14 ± 0.01	0.138 ± 0.004	A
	ARK120	0.17 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.02	A
	Mrk79	0.08 ± 0.01	0.092 ± 0.004	B
	NGC4051	0.07 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.02	B
	Mrk766	0.19 ± 0.02	0.082 ± 0.006	C
	Mrk766	0.30 ± 0.03	0.088 ± 0.002	C
	Mrk841	0.02 ± 0.00	0.06 ± 0.02	D
	1H0419-577	0.24 ± 0.04	0.079 ± 0.007	E
	Mrk290	0.19 ± 0.02	0.16 ± 0.02	B
	Mrk205	0.16 ± 0.10	0.100 ± 0.004	F
	PG1211+143	0.17 ± 0.03	0.151 ± 0.003	D
	MCG-5-23-16	0.09 ± 0.02	0.116 ± 0.004	G
NGC4507	0.79 ± 0.54	0.20 ± 0.02		
2	3C111	0.02 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.04	H
	3C3903	0.09 ± 0.02	0.145 ± 0.007	A
	4C+74.26	0.04 ± 0.00	0.18 ± 0.03	
	ESO103-G035	0.13 ± 0.03	0.06 ± 0.03	
	MR2251-178	0.16 ± 0.03	0.137 ± 0.008	
	Mrk279	0.03 ± 0.00	0.220 ± 0.006	B
	NGC5506	0.28 ± 0.05	0.246 ± 0.006	I
SQJ2127	0.16 ± 0.00	0.231 ± 0.006		
3	Mrk231	0.17 ± 0.03	0.067 ± 0.008	L,M
	PDS456	0.46 ± 0.15	0.25 ± 0.01	N
	Iras 11119	0.65 ± 0.19	0.26 ± 0.01	L,O
	IZwicky1	0.85 ± 0.17	0.27 ± 0.01	P
	Iras 05189	1.30 ± 0.27	0.110 ± 0.010	Q,R
	PG 1448+273	0.76 ± 0.077	0.150 ± 0.008	S
	APM08279	0.40 ± 0.30	0.36 ± 0.02	T,U
MCG-03-58-007	0.20 ± 0.07	0.20 ± 0.01	V	

Table 5.1: Sources plotted in Fig. 5.15. From left to right, columns indicate the number of the group, the source name, λ_{Edd} , the UFO velocity v_{out} (in units of c) and the additional references for each source. Group 1: UFO v_{out} and black hole mass M_{BH} from Tombesi et al. (2012), L_{bol} from Fiore et al. (2017). Group 2: values from Gofford et al. (2015). For both groups, M_{BH} , L_{bol} have been updated (where possible) with recent values from the literature, see reference column. Group 3: individual sources, see reference column. References: A Peterson et al. (2004), B Ricci et al. (2017), C Bentz & Manne-Nicholas (2018), D Vestergaard & Peterson (2006), E Tilton & Shull (2013), F Kelly & Bechtold (2007), G Caglar et al. (2020), H Chatterjee et al. (2011), I Ricci et al. (2017), L Nardini & Zubovas (2018), M Feruglio et al. (2015), N Nardini et al. (2015); Bischetti et al. (2019), O Tombesi et al. (2015), P Reeves & Braitto (2019), Q Smith et al. (2019), R Onori et al. (2017), S Laurenti et al. (2020), T Chartas et al. (2009), U Saturni et al. (2018), V Braitto et al. (2018)

6. The Wind in the Ionised Nuclear Environment (WINE) model

We gave a general overview of the WINE model in Sect. 2.3. We now outline the implementation of the WINE model obtained by combining the work described in the previous Sections. The Monte Carlo modelling of emission profiles (Sect. 3) is coupled to the relativistically-corrected radiative transfer, performed using *XSTAR* and the algorithm outlined in Sect. 4. The WINE program is written in bash language, with the absorption and emission routines in Python. The program allows to explore a whole range of physical and geometrical parameters given by the user. This is useful when using WINE to analyse the parameter space and to minimise the fit of spectral wind features. The synthetic spectra obtained with WINE may be submitted to spectral fitting programs, such as *XSPEC* for the X-ray band, as anticipated in Sect. 3.2. At the end of this Section we also present some theoretical results obtained with WINE, to shed a new light on disc winds features. In particular, we report on the presence and observability of P-Cygni profiles as a function of the typical UFO parameters such as N_H , ξ , v_{out} . As discussed in Sect. 3, the occurrence of emission components is not fully settled observationally and it is not yet clear in which physical conditions the outflow manifests itself simply through absorption features or, instead, with P-Cygni profiles. We present here a clear and physically grounded outlook on this topic obtained with WINE simulations.

6.1 The working scheme of WINE

We describe the wind as a biconical region, centred on the supermassive black hole (SMBH) and with the same symmetry axis of the accretion disk. We consider that the rear cone is obscured by the disc (in yellow) and we assume a point like luminosity source, centred on the SMBH (blue and black dots, respectively), as shown in Fig. 6.1. The wind is enclosed by an initial and final radius, r_0 , r_1 , and has an inner and outer opening angle, θ_{out} and θ_{in} , respectively (shown in red and green in Fig. 6.1), while the inclination of the line of sight (LOS) i is shown in pink. The geometry, already introduced in Sect. 3.1, is in line with most of the simulations on accretion disc wind in the literature. Moreover, galactic-scale outflows also show spherical or biconical

Figure 6.1: Geometry of the WINE model. Gray shaded area indicate the wind volume. $\theta_{in}, \theta_{out}$ represents the wind inner and outer opening angle with respect to the symmetry axis (vertical dotted line). The line of sight (LOS) has an inclination angle i with respect to the axis. Accretion disc is represented with a yellow bar, and the black and blue dots indicate respectively the supermassive black hole and the ionising and X-ray luminosity sources, which are assumed as point like. Finally, r_0, r_1 indicate the wind initial and final radius, respectively.

morphologies, as discussed in Sect. 1.4. The inner cavity, specified by θ_{in} , represents a first-order parametrisation for (possible) density variations along the polar angle. Such variations are indeed expected for both radiative and MHD accelerations, which produce variable wind distributions along the equatorial and the poloidal directions, as discussed in Sect. 2, 3. For magnetically-driven winds, the interplay between poloidal and toroidal magnetic fields (B_p, B_ϕ) may also lead to a collimated, relativistic jet-like outflow around the rotation axis and a smooth, mildly relativistic outflow outside the jet region (see Sect. 2.1.3). In this case, we expect the jet region to lie in the $0 < \theta < \theta_{in}$ interval, and the wind in the $\theta_{in} < \theta < \theta_{out}$ one. Moreover, a configuration with $\theta_{in} \approx \theta_{out}$ is able to reproduce a funnel-shaped wind; such structure is foreseen by several theoretical models (see e.g. Elvis, 2000; Matthews et al., 2020) with the aim to unify most of the outflowing structures observed in the optical and X-ray bands, i.e. from the UFO up to, possibly, the Narrow Line Region.

Density and velocity are parametrised as power-law functions of the radial coordinate of the cone:

$$n(r) = n_0 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^{-\alpha} \quad (6.1)$$

$$v(r) = v_0 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^{-\beta} \quad (6.2)$$

where $n_0 \equiv n(r = r_0)$, $v_0 \equiv v(r = r_0)$ and we assume the wind to be directed radially outward. Several analytical calculations seem to point toward such power-law trends (see e.g. Faucher-Giguère & Quataert, 2012; Menci et al., 2019) in the case of a fast wind expanding in a perturbation-free environment. Specifically, in the case of momentum- and energy-conserving flows the following relations hold (Faucher-Giguère & Quataert, 2012):

$$\beta = \begin{cases} (2 - \alpha)/2 & \text{Momentum cons.} \\ (2 - \alpha)/3 & \text{Energy cons.} \end{cases} \quad (6.3)$$

so it is possible to link the velocity profile to the density one. We concentrate on a "ideal" (perturbation-free) outflow since we expect strong inhomogeneities to be suppressed at typical UFO scales. Even though an intrinsic degree of anisotropy in the gas properties - density, temperature - is naturally expected at the outflow launching point, the strong acceleration gradients and the extreme velocities, which make the gas trans- to super-sonic (see e.g. Proga et al., 2000; Cui & Yuan, 2020; Quera-Bofarull et al., 2020), are expected to quench the growth of physical gradients and the setting of multiphase flows. The development of a fully inhomogeneous flow, i.e. $\delta\rho/\langle\rho\rangle \gtrsim 1$, $\delta T/\langle T\rangle \gtrsim 1$ (where $\delta\rho = |\rho - \langle\rho\rangle|$ and $\langle\rho\rangle$ is the average density and the same holds for the temperature T) is typically expected at WA and BLR scales. The theoretical picture,

however, is not yet fully established, and we refer to Dannen et al. (2020); Waters et al. (2021) and references therein for further discussions.

The perturbation-free assumption in WINE can be relaxed in two main ways. First, it is possible to modify the density and velocity profiles, Eqs. 6.1, 6.2, introducing a stochastic fluctuation pattern at perturbation length scales on top of the "ideal" powerlaw trend. Secondly, the synthetic spectra of a multiphase wind can be represented through the superposition of the absorption/emission features due to the different outflow phases. While we do not expect significant observational signatures of the wind inhomogeneities in current, moderate resolution UFO spectra (see discussion in Sect. 1.3.2), we plan to explore this topic in greater detail with the resolution of the next-generation microcalorimeters onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*. Depending on the future observations, we will also consider to introduce further degrees of freedom in WINE to account for the wind anisotropy, e.g. through the density contrast $\delta\rho/\langle\rho\rangle$.

In order to accurately calculate radiative transfer within the wind, we use a multilayer approach, similarly to what done in Schurch & Done (2007); Fukumura et al. (2010); Saez & Chartas (2011). For a given N_H^{max} , we divide the wind in M thin slabs, each with a constant column density δN_H , so that $\delta N_H \cdot M = N_H^{max}$. This slicing allows to build absorption and emission templates for increasing column density by sampling the entire interval $]0, N_H^{max}]$ with steps of δN_H . Then, the whole procedure is iterated over a range of ionisation parameters ξ_0 calculated at $r = r_0$, i.e. $[\xi_0^{min}, \xi_0^{max}]$ with steps of $\delta\xi_0$.

In addition to the iteration of ξ_0, N_H , the emission spectrum is generated over three further ranges of values for $\theta_{out}, \theta_{in}, i$, specifying the geometry of the system. The opening angle spans an increasing set of values, $\theta_{out} \in]0, 90] \text{ deg}$, with steps of $\delta\theta_{out}$. The lower value corresponds to a narrow jet-like region around the symmetry axis, while the upper value to a hemisphere. Similarly, $i \in]0, 90 \text{ deg}]$ with steps of δi , corresponding respectively to face-on and edge-on sight lines (with respect to the accretion disc). Since the inner cavity of the wind must be $0 \leq \theta_{in} < \theta_{out}$, its range is defined as $\theta_{in} \in [0, \theta_{out}[$ with a number Q of equally-spaced steps.

Finally, the incident spectrum is specified by S_I , the spectral shape in the UV-X-ray range, and L_{ion} , its integrated ionising luminosity in the 13.6 eV - 13.6 keV range. We present a detailed flowchart of WINE in Fig 6.2 to better illustrate the different steps of the model.

6.1.1 The free parameters

The complete set of input parameters in WINE is the following (see the top green panel of Fig. 6.2):

Figure 6.2: Flowchart of the main steps of the WINE model.

- L_{ion} , the incident ionising luminosity in the 1-1000 Ry (13.6eV – 13.6keV) interval or, equivalently, in the 2-10 keV interval.
- The spectrum shape S_I , which can have one of the following forms:
 - A power-law with spectral index Γ
 - A black-body with temperature kT (in eV)
 - A custom spectrum uploaded by the user
- r_0 , the initial radius of the cone. It can be expressed both in cm or in r_G . In the second case, the black hole mass M_{BH} must be also provided
- $N_H^{max}, \delta N_H$, the maximum column density of the wind and the sampling step
- $\xi_0^{min}, \xi_0^{max}, \delta \xi_0$, the minimum and maximum ionisation parameter at the base of the wind and the sampling step
- α , the index of the density profile in Eq. 6.1
- v_0, β , the starting velocity and the index in Eq. 6.2. β can also be linked to α using the relations of Eq. 6.3
- $\delta \theta_{out}$, the sampling step for the opening angle θ_{out} , which spans the interval]0, 90 deg]
- δi , the sampling step of the inclination of the LOS i , which spans the interval [0, 90 deg]
- Q , the number of steps for the inner cavity θ_{in} , which spans the interval [0, θ_{out} [

After writing a log of all the input quantities, the program starts the simulation.

The outer (first level) iteration is performed over the ionisation parameter (light grey panel) in the range $[\xi_0^{min}, \xi_0^{max}]$ with steps $\delta \xi_0$.

For each value ξ_0 , the initial density of the wind n_0 is determined by inverting the definition of ξ_0 :

$$\xi_0 \equiv \xi(r = r_0) = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_0(r_0)^2} \quad (6.4)$$

and the final radius of the wind r_1 is found inverting the definition of N_H :

$$N_H^{max} = \int_{r_0}^{r_1} n(r) dr \quad (6.5)$$

Then, the wind is divided in M slabs (such that $\delta N_H \cdot M = N_H^{max}$). An inner iteration (second level, blue panel) is performed over the slabs, with m ranging from 1 to M . In this way, absorption

spectra are calculated for increasing N_H . For the sake of simplicity and higher modularity, the absorption and emission processes are treated separately. This assumption is permitted given the low reabsorption probability, since that UFOs usually have observed optical depth τ lower than unity. As discussed in Sect. 5.4.1, $\tau = 1$ roughly corresponds to $N_H \approx \sigma_T^{-1} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, while the average column density for UFOs is 10^{23} cm^{-2} . Moreover, the optical depth is further reduced for gas moving at mildly relativistic speed, as detailed in Sect. 4.

6.1.2 Wind Absorption

For each m -th slabs, the program analytically calculates all the required quantities to perform a relativistically-corrected *XSTAR* run. We first describe the procedure for $m = 1$, and then we generalise it for the following slabs. The slab initial radius is $r_1^i = r_0$ and the final radius r_1^f is found inverting Eq. 6.5 with $N_H = \delta N_H$. The procedure described in Section 4 is implemented to account for the (column density-averaged) slab velocity, v_{avg} , and the related special relativity effects in radiative transfer. v_{avg} is defined as $v(r_{avg})$, where r_{avg} is the radius enclosing half of the slab column density: $\delta N_H / 2 = \int_{r_1^i}^{r_1^{avg}} n(r) dr$. A turbulent velocity is required by *XSTAR* to reproduce the smearing of the wind features. This velocity is defined as:

$$v_{turb} = \max : \begin{cases} \delta v & \text{(velocity shearing)} \\ \sigma_{int} & \text{(intrinsic turbulence)} \end{cases} \quad (6.6)$$

where $\delta v = |v(r_1^i) - v(r_1^{avg})|$ represents the variation of $v(r)$ within the slab, while $\sigma_{int} = 0.1 \cdot v(r_{avg})$ and accounts for the intrinsic turbulence of the outflow. We set a lower limit to σ_{int} equal to 3000 km s^{-1} , in order to match the typical turbulence detected in the more distant (and perhaps less turbulent) Broad Line Region clouds (Kollatschny, & Zetzl, 2013). The *XSTAR* run returns the (relativistic-corrected) transmitted spectrum from the first slab, corresponding to a column density $N_H = \delta N_H$, and a separate file with the wind line emissivities.

To calculate the radiative transfer in the second slab, the transmitted spectrum from the first slab $S_{T,1}$ is given as input incident spectrum. Accordingly, the initial radius of the slab corresponds to the final radius of the previous slab, i.e. $r_2^i = r_1^f$, and the final radius r_2^f is calculated in the same way of r_1^f . *XSTAR* is run using $\delta N_H, n(r = r_2^i), S_{1-2}, \xi(r = r_2^i) = \frac{L_{T,1}}{n(r=r_2^i)(r_2^i)^2}$, where $L_{T,1}$ is the luminosity of $S_{T,1}$. Similarly, relativistic effects are calculated using the averaged velocity of the second slab and v_{turb} is calculated following Eq. 6.6. Therefore, the transmitted spectrum corresponds to a column density $N_H = 2 \cdot \delta N_H$.

This procedure is iterated over the M slabs, up to the N_H^{max} of the wind. In this way, WINE generates absorption templates up to N_H^{max} , with steps of δN_H .

6.1.3 Wind Emission

In *XSTAR* the emission from the wind is calculated assuming that the wind has null velocity and its geometry is spherically symmetric around the central luminosity source. In order to go beyond the null velocity assumption and to set geometrical constraints on the wind, WINE directly calculates the emission spectrum according to the geometry and the velocity of the wind. Wind emission is calculated with the same multilayer approach of the absorption. A second level iteration (see the bottom, orange block in Fig. 6.2) is performed over the range of values of $\theta_{out}, \theta_{in}, i$, specifying the geometry of the wind. Furthermore, for each set of parameters, a third level iteration (light yellow) is performed over N_H , from 0 to N_H^{max} with m steps.

For each slab the code uses the line emissivity values calculated by *XSTAR*, which takes into account all the transitions listed in the atomic database (roughly from the UV regime up to $> 100keV$). The emissivities ζ are in units of $erg s^{-1} cm^{-3}$ and represent a "luminosity density" for a given transition within the slab, and are stored in a dedicated file.

The energy range is restricted to the $E = 0.5 - 40keV$ range, to encompass the whole X-ray band of interest for accretion disc winds, with a resolution of 10^4 logarithmically-spaced bins. Within this interval, only the I lines brighter than a fraction ϵ of the brightest one are considered, where $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$. The energy resolution and ϵ are chosen as a tradeoff between computing time and the accuracy required for analysing CCD observations with current X-ray observatories such as *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton*. It must be noted, however, that the accuracy can be easily increased to match the energy resolution of the next generation microcalorimeters, such as those onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*.

The emission spectrum of the m -th slab is calculated according to the following steps:

- The volume of the slab V_s is determined as a function of its initial and final radius, r_m^i, r_m^f , and of $\theta_{out}, \theta_{in}$
- As in Section 3.1, we populate the slab with a high number K of points, whose coordinates are randomly assigned with a Monte Carlo method inside V_s . We find that 10^4 points are necessary to optimally sample the slab volume while still being computationally feasible, so we fix $K = 10^4$.
- For each k -th point (where $k \in [1, K]$):
 - An average volume $\delta V = V_s/K$ is assigned, and the luminosity Z_i of the i -th transition is calculated as $Z_i = \zeta_i \cdot \delta V$, where $i \in [0, I]$.
 - Using special relativity formulae, the line energy E_i and luminosity Z_i are projected

along the observer line of sight (LOS) according to the following expressions:

$$E_i^{LOS} = \psi \cdot E_i \quad (6.7)$$

$$Z_i^{LOS} = \psi^3 \cdot Z_i \quad (6.8)$$

where $\psi = \frac{1}{\gamma(1-\beta\cos(\theta))}$, $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$, $\beta = v_{avg}/c$. θ is the angle between the LOS and the coordinates of the k -th point and, therefore, depends also on the LOS inclination i . v_{avg} represents the column density-averaged slab velocity.

– The collection of E_i^{LOS} , Z_i^{LOS} from all the transitions of interest, i.e. from $i = 0$ to $i = I$, gives the emitted spectrum of the k -th point.

- The sum of the spectra from all the K points produces the slab emission spectrum, which is then binned according to the provided energy range and resolution.

Finally, by adding the slab emission spectra for increasing m we get the wind emission spectrum for increasing column density, up to N_H^{max} , with steps of δN_H .

6.1.4 Subslicing

It is important to note that in order to increase the resolution of the multilayer runs, without saving the data related to each slab, it is possible to introduce a further sub-slicing. Each slab can be divided in equally-spaced sub-slabs with column density δN_H^{sub} . Then, WINE applies to these sub-slabs the same multilayer approach described above. Radiative transfer is propagated over all the sub-slabs to obtain the profile of the parent slab. The value of δN_H^{sub} is, again, a trade-off between accuracy and computing time. By running a set of simulations we find that a value of $\delta N_H^{sub} = 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ provides excellent accuracy for both the emission and absorption profiles and, remarkably, it is largely computationally feasible even for laptops and small servers ($\lesssim 10$ CPUs).

6.2 Sample of program outputs

In this section we focus on a typical AGN with 2-10 keV luminosity of $L_{2-10} = 10^{43} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and a black hole mass $M_{BH} = 10^7 M_\odot$, thus implying a value $\lambda_{Edd} \equiv \frac{L_{bol}}{L_{Edd}} \approx 0.1$ for a $L_{2-10} - L_{bol}$ correction factor of ≈ 30 (Lusso et al., 2012). We assume typical UFO values of $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $v_0 = 0.10c$, $\xi_0 = 10^4 \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$ and an initial radius $r_0 = 50r_G$ (see Sect. 1.3.2). Hereafter, ξ_0 will be expressed in units of erg cm s^{-1} . Moreover, we assume $\alpha = 0$ and an X-ray continuum power-law slope with $\Gamma = 2$ (see Sect. 1.2.2).

Figure 6.3: Left: Absorption profiles for $N_H = 10^{23}$ and $6 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (blue and orange lines respectively), $v_0 = 0.10 c$, $\xi_0 = 10^4$ (ionisation parameter is in units of erg cm s^{-1}). The wind opacity increases almost linearly with N_H . Right: Absorption profiles for $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10, 0.30c$ (colour coding, see legend) and $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $\xi_0 = 10^4$. For increasing v_0 , absorption lines are increasingly blueshifted and shows lower EWs, as expected from the special relativity effects. Please note that the two panels have different scales.

Within these initial conditions, the wind is in a geometrically thin configuration and the scaling of v, ξ with r is limited, and this allows us to clearly assess the impact of the different input parameters. An useful quantity to characterise the wind geometrically thickness as a function of N_H is $\Delta r = \frac{r(N_H) - r_0}{r_0}$, i.e., the difference between the radius enclosing a column density N_H and the initial radius r_0 , normalised by r_0 . According to α , Δr can be written as a function of the initial parameters as follows:

$$\Delta r = \begin{cases} \frac{N_H}{n_0 r_0} \propto \frac{N_H}{\lambda_{Edd}} & \alpha = 0 \\ \exp \frac{N_H}{n_0 r_0} - 1 \propto \exp \frac{N_H}{\lambda_{Edd}} & \alpha = 1 \\ \frac{1}{1 - N_H / (n_0 r_0)} - 1 \propto \frac{1}{1 - N_H / \lambda_{Edd}} & \alpha = 2 \end{cases} \quad (6.9)$$

where we used the definition of ξ_0 (Eq. 6.4) and the initial radius is expressed in units of $r_G \equiv GM_{BH}/c^2 \propto M_{BH}$, so that $n_0 r_0 = L_{ion}/(\xi_0 r_0) \propto L_{ion}/(\xi_0 GM_{BH} c^{-2}) \propto L_{ion}/M_{BH} \propto L_{bol}/M_{BH} \propto \lambda_{Edd}$. Therefore for a given ξ_0 , Δr simply depends on λ_{Edd} , while it is independent from L_{bol}, M_{BH} . This enables a quick characterisation of the wind properties and their dependence from N_H . For a generic value of $\alpha \neq 1$, the formula reads as:

$$\Delta r = \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{N_H}{n_0 r_0 (\alpha - 1)}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha - 1}}} - 1 \quad (6.10)$$

Fig. 6.3, left panel, shows two absorption spectra with $N_H = 10^{23}$ and $6 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (blue and orange lines, respectively). It can be seen that the wind opacity increases almost linearly

with N_H , as expected for an optically thin gas (see e.g. Tombesi et al., 2011). The strongest absorption profiles in the hard X-ray band ($E > 5 keV$), are due to the Ly α and Ly β lines of Fe XXV and XXVI, which are the most abundant Fe ions for our assumed value of $\xi_0 = 10^4$ (Kallman et al., 2004) and have rest frame energies of 6.7, 7.9 keV (Fe XXV Ly α and Ly β , respectively) and 7.0, 8.2 keV (Fe XXVI). In the right panel of Fig. 6.3 we show three spectra with $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10, 0.30c$. As discussed in Sect. 4 (see Fig. 4.3), special relativity effects clearly affect both the absorption feature blueshifts and their equivalent widths. Moreover, the turbulent velocity v_{turb} increases for increasing v_0 (following Eq. 6.6) and strongly modifies the absorption profiles, blending together the Ly α lines of Fe XXV and XXVI for $v_0 = 0.30 c$ at energies around 9 keV¹.

Fig. 6.4 shows the emission profiles for different wind geometries. We recall that the projected velocity can be expressed as $v_{proj} = \frac{v_{out}}{\gamma(1-\beta \cos \theta)}$, where θ is the angle between the LOS and the gas velocity and depends on $\theta_{out}, \theta_{in}, i$ (see Eq. 3.2). When the gas is directed radially outward and v_{out} lies along the LOS, $\theta = 0 deg$, the projected velocity reaches its highest value of $v_{proj} = \frac{v_{out}}{\gamma(1-\beta)}$, while when the gas is antiparallel to the LOS, i.e. $\theta = 180 deg$, the projected velocity reaches its lowest value of $v_{proj} = \frac{v_{out}}{\gamma(1+\beta)}$.

In the top left panel we show the case for $\theta_{out} = 90 deg, i = 0$: the transmitted flux is maximised, since the emitting volume is the largest possible, as shown in the cartoon (i.e., a hemisphere filling the solid angle above the accretion disc) and the LOS coincides with the symmetry axis, resulting in a beamed emission towards the observer (see Sect. 3.1 and Fig. 3.3). The accretion disc is thus seen "face on" and θ ranges from 0 to 90 deg.

The emission profile is the result of the composition of the lines due to several ions, with the strongest ones being originated by O VIII ($E = 0.6 - 0.7 keV$), Mg XII (1.5 keV), Al XIII (1.7 keV), Si XVI (2.6 - 3.1 keV), Cl XVII (3.0 keV), Ar XVIII (3.3 keV), Ca XX (4.1 keV), Cr XXIII/XXIV (5.6 - 5.9 keV), Mn XXV (6.4 keV), Ni XXVII (7.8 - 8.1 keV) and, finally Fe XXV/XXVI (6.7 - 8.2 keV). Interestingly, we note a lack of emission in a narrow range just above 6 keV, due to the higher ionisation potential of the heaviest elements (Mn, Ni, Fe). In the top right panel we reduce the emission region by setting the cone aperture θ_{out} equal to 30 deg, while keeping fixed $i = 0$. The emitted luminosity is lower than that found in the previous scenario. In particular, this is true for the low-energy (low-velocity) side of each emission peak. In fact, this side corresponds to the high inclination angles w.r.t to the LOS, i.e. the gas located at an angular amplitude θ_{out} between 30 and 90 deg. In the $\theta_{out} = 90$ and $i = 90 deg$ case (bottom left panel of Fig. 6.4), the accretion disc is instead seen "edge on", and then θ ranges from 0 to 180 deg. As a consequence, the spectral features are broadened over a larger energy interval than

¹Note that in Sect. 4 simulations were performed with XSTAR using the default value for v_{turb} equal to the thermal broadening ($\sim 300 km s^{-1}$), therefore this latter aspect was not considered.

Figure 6.4: Emission profiles for different geometries, shown as cartoons, and the other parameters set to their assumed values (see Sect. 6.2). Top row: wind seen "face on" ($i = 0$) and $\theta_{out} = 90, 30$ (left and right panel, respectively). Bottom row: "edge on" winds ($i = 90$ deg) and $\theta_{out} = 90, 30$ (left and right panel, respectively). For comparison, in all the panels the $i = 0, \theta_{out} = 90$ case is reported with light grey lines.

Figure 6.5: Emission spectrum for increasing $v_0 = 0.10$ and $= 0.30 c$ (blue and orange profiles, respectively). The emission lines are spread over a higher range of projected energies (i.e., velocities) and, as a result, are blended together for $v_0 = 0.30 c$.

in the "face on" case (plotted again with grey lines for comparison), since they are projected over an increased velocity space. Finally, for $\theta_{out} = 30, i = 90 deg$ (bottom right panel) the emission region lies outside the LOS and θ ranges from 60 to $120 deg$. This explains the lower v_{proj} and the overall decrease of the transmitted flux, since the relativistic beaming reduces the radiation projected toward the LOS.

Fig. 6.5 shows wind emission spectra for increasing v_0 : $v_0 = 0.10c$ (blue line) and $v_0 = 0.30c$ (orange line) assuming $\theta_{out} = 90$ and $i = 0 deg$. For $v_0 = 0.3c$ the emission features are spread over a larger velocity (energy) interval. As a consequence, the emitted flux per unit energy (in units of $erg s^{-1} keV^{-1}$, as shown in the picture) is lower, and the emission peaks are less intense with respect to the $v_0 = 0.10c$ case. This will have important implications on the detectability of emission features in the total (emission+absorption) wind spectra, since the emission tends to be weaker for increasing v_0 and typically overwhelmed by the absorption spectrum.

6.3 Wind Emission Detectability

In order to have a glimpse on the relative strength of absorption and emission features, we plot the wind spectrum for $v_0 = 0.10 c, \xi_0 = 10^4$ and $\theta_{out} = 90 deg, \theta_{in} = 0, i = 0$ (Fig. 6.6, top panel). For $N_H = 10^{23} cm^{-2}$ the emission flux (yellow line) remains always lower than the absorption one (cyan line) over the $0.5 - 10.0 keV$ energy band. A similar trend is found for $N_H = 10^{24} cm^{-2}$ (orange and blue lines, respectively), with the exception of the Fe structures above $7 keV$. The

Figure 6.6: Absorption and emission spectra for $N_H = 10^{23}$ (yellow and cyan lines, respectively) and $= 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (blue and orange lines). From top to bottom ξ_0, v_0 have different values, i.e. $\log(\xi_0) = 4.0, v_0 = 0.10c$ in top panel, $\log(\xi_0) = 4.0, v_0 = 0.05c$ in the middle panel and $\log(\xi_0) = 3.0, v_0 = 0.10c$ in the bottom panel.

relative weakness of the emission features may be the cause of their very limited detection rate in AGN spectra so far. To give an idea of the impact of the wind parameters on this aspect, we also show different configurations obtained by varying a single parameter one at time. In the middle panel we show a slower wind, $v_0 = 0.05c$, where the absorption and emission features are projected over a smaller energy interval (colour coding as above). As a result, emission and absorption features show a slightly larger overlap. Finally, in the lower panel we show a wind with $\xi_0 = 10^3$, for which the Fe L-shell absorption complex around 1 keV absorbs a significant fraction of the transmitted radiation, thus allowing the emission spectrum to be detectable over a broader energy range.

Starting from these cases, we further explore a broader parameter range to evaluate the strength of the emission features in simulated X-ray spectra. For a given set of values for the wind parameters, we define the emission *detectable* if the flux of the emission spectrum is higher than the absorption flux in at least two adjacent bins. We select two energy bands of interest, a soft band from 0.5 to 2.5 keV and a hard band between 5 and 15 keV. We perform WINE simulations with an energy resolution of 2 eV to match that of the X-IFU camera onboard *Athena*.

We concentrate on a range of $\log(\xi_0) = [3, 4, 5, 6]$, $v_0 = [0.05, 0.10, 0.30]c$ and $N_H \in [10^{23}, 10^{24}]cm^{-2}$ with steps of $10^{23}cm^{-2}$. For the emission, we set $\theta_{out} = 90 deg$, $\theta_{in} = 0$, $i = 0$ in order to explore the most favourable scenario for detecting the emission from the wind. We also assume $L_{2-10} = 10^{43} erg s^{-1}$, $M_{BH} = 10^7 M_\odot$, $\Gamma = 2$ as above. Fig. 6.7 shows the "observed" equivalent width (EW) of the emission features, built according to the following procedure. We scan the soft and hard energy bands looking for intervals of two or more bins satisfying the detectability requirement. For each interval we calculate the EW of the emission lines. Finally, we calculate the median value of the distribution of EWs for all the intervals. We focus on the median EW values (mEW), rather than the total EW, since we are primarily interested on the detectability. Although an emission spectrum whose flux is slightly higher than the absorption one in a significant energy range will have a non-negligible EW, it would be difficult to detect the emission features due to the low contrast with respect to the underlying continuum component. Conversely, emission features which are much stronger than the (absorbed) continuum, even if concentrated in few energy bins, will lead to an easily detectable spectral feature. Finally, null mEW values indicate that the detectability condition has not been matched in the whole energy band.

We plot in Fig. 6.7 the values of mEW as a function of N_H for both the soft and the hard bands (dashed and solid lines, respectively). Different panels show increasing values of ξ_0 (from top to bottom and left to right). For $\xi_0 = 10^3$ (top left panel) emission is easily detectable (mEW $\approx 100eV$) already for $N_H \approx 3 \cdot 10^{23}cm^{-2}$ for all the velocities but $v_{out} = 0.30 c$, for which mEW $\approx 10eV$ is reached only for a column $N_H \approx 6 \cdot 10^{23}cm^{-2}$. The values of the mEW as a function

Figure 6.7: Median Equivalent Width (mEW) of the wind emission as a function of N_H , plotted for increasing v_0 (colour coding, see legend). Soft and hard X-ray band, corresponding to 0.5 - 2.5 and 5-15 keV, respectively, are shown with dashed and solid lines. We assume $\log(\xi_0) = 3, 4, 5, 6$ in the top-left, top-right, bottom-left and bottom-right panel, respectively.

of N_H are comparable between the soft and the hard band for given ξ_0 and v_0 .

For higher ionisation parameters the fraction of bound electrons in the gas significantly decreases, leading to a strong reduction of the wind absorption and emission features especially in the soft band. As an example, for $\xi_0 = 10^4$ the fractional abundance of Fe peaks at Fe XXV (He-like Fe, with only two bound electrons), while for $\xi_0 = 10^5$ has a maximum for Fe XXVI (H-like Fe, with just one electron left; Kallman et al., 2004). For $\xi_0 = 10^4$ (top right panel), emission mEW is strongly reduced, particularly in the soft band. The values of the mEW are strongly dependent on v_0 . This can be explained by looking at the difference between the $\xi_0 = 10^3$ and $= 10^4$ spectra in Fig. 6.6 (bottom and top panels, respectively). For $\xi_0 = 10^3$ the Fe L shell absorption manifests over a broad energy range. As a result, the emission spectrum has a higher flux than the absorption one over a wide energy interval. Therefore, the impact of increasing v_0 on the absorption and emission profiles does not likely affect significantly the detectability threshold. On the contrary, for $\xi_0 = 10^4$, the absorption and emission features overlap only over a narrow range, therefore a high v_0 may impact the detectability threshold in two ways. First, it reduces the optical depth of the absorption lines and makes them more blueshifted (see Fig. 6.3 and Sect. 4). Secondly, a high v_0 is associated with emission lines projected over a higher observed energy range (see Fig. 6.5) and therefore reduces the emitted flux per unit keV . We show these combined effects in detail in Fig. 6.8.

Finally, for $\xi_0 = 10^5$ (bottom left panel of Fig. 6.7) the detectability of the wind emission features is further reduced, and a non-zero mEW can be observed only for $v_0 = 0.0c$ and $N_H > 6 \cdot 10^{23} cm^{-2}$. For $\xi_0 = 10^6$ the emission spectrum of the wind is basically undetectable for any wind velocity and column density.

6.4 P-Cygni profiles

We now focus on the detectability of P-Cygni profiles from the Fe K shell in wind spectra, such as the ones presented in Sect. 1.3.2. Our goal is to understand if the relative weakness of emission, compared to the absorbed continuum, is able to explain the limited number of P-Cygni profiles associated to UFOs detected in AGN so far. In Fig. 6.8 we show a variety of wind profiles around the typical P-Cygni energy band between 5 and 10 keV , for different wind properties. We plot with green lines the total (emission+absorption) spectrum and with yellow ones the two separate spectra. As found in Sect. 6.3, the emission component is (marginally) visible in the low-ionisation, low-velocity case $\xi_0 = 10^3$, $v_0 = 0.10c$ (top left panel, green spectrum).

We directly fit the spectra in the $E = 5 - 10 keV$ interval in order to accurately calculate the EWs associated with emission and absorption lines. We first fit the continuum spectrum with a power-law component in a narrow interval centred on the features. Then, we scan the

Figure 6.8: Details of wind spectra for $\xi_0 = 10^3, 10^4$ (top and bottom row) and $v_0 = 0.10, 0.30c$ (left and right column). Yellow lines correspond to the absorption and emission profiles, while green line shows the total spectrum.

interval and we ascribe to the wind emission(absorption) a flux in excess(below) that prescribed by the fit. We span the same parameter range of the previous section but the $v_0 = 0.0c$ case for simplicity. Fig. 6.9 shows the total EW of emission and absorption lines (top and bottom panels, respectively) as a function of N_H and for increasing ξ_0 (from left to right). Furthermore, figures 6.10-6.13 show the spectral fits for increasing ξ_0 from 10^3 to 10^6 . Specifically, in Fig. 6.10 we plot the fits for $\xi_0 = 10^3, N_H = 10^{23}, 5 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (blue and green lines, respectively) and for $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10, 0.30 c$ (left to right). Top panel shows the ratio between the wind spectrum and the incident continuum spectrum. Bottom panel reports the emitted and absorbed fluxes in units of $10^{50} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ erg}^{-1}$. We note that v_0 clearly affects the observational appearance of the wind features. In particular, for $v_0 = 0.05c$ the absorption and emission features partially overlap, therefore they tend to cancel out each other and their EWs are both reduced with respect to the

$v_0 = 0.10c$ case, where instead they appear quite separated. This is similar to what shown in Fig. 6.8, top row, for $v_0 = 0.10$ and $0.30c$ (please note that Figs. 6.8 and 6.10 have different scales). For $v_0 = 0.30c$ the emission is too weak to be detected above the continuum spectrum, therefore its EW drops. Absorption lines, instead, have stronger EW for $v_0 = 0.30c$ than for $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10c$, since they are now basically unaffected by the emitted flux. The trend is similar for $\xi_0 = 10^4$ (see Fig. 6.11) with the only exception of the emission line for $v_0 = 0.30c$, which is detected above the continuum and has intermediate EW between the $v_0 = 0.05$ and $v_0 = 0.10c$ cases. For $\xi_0 = 10^5, 10^6$ (Figs. 6.12, 6.13, respectively) the fraction of bound electrons in Fe elements is considerably reduced, therefore the EW of absorption and emission features drops significantly. As a consequence, emission flux is too low to affect the absorption features, and the EW of the absorption lines are therefore independent on v_0 .

Figure 6.9: EWs of emission and absorption features (top and bottom panels, respectively) as a function of N_H . Cyan, light and dark green lines refer to $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10, 0.30c$. From left to right, we report increasing ξ_0 , from $\log(\xi_0) = 3$ to 6 (see titles). Note that panels have different scales

We note that, due to the complex spectral shape in the 5-10 keV band, our fit has been restricted to a narrow range around the Fe K resonant line features. These lines, together with the Fe K shell photoionisation edge at $E = 9.28 \text{keV}$, span an energy interval from $\approx 6 \text{keV}$

to $\gtrsim 10\text{keV}$. Therefore a proper determination of the spectrum both in the soft band (up to 5keV) and above 10keV is necessary to accurately estimate the underlying continuum and, then, to properly constrain the outflow spectral features. In the soft band, additional spectral components may complicate the determination of the continuum, such as a soft excess or a warm absorber (see Sect. 1.2.2). On the other hand, absorption from the Fe K shell photoionisation edge may be mismatched for a steeper power-law continuum at $E \gtrsim 9\text{keV}$, especially for typical *XMM-Newton* and *Chandra* datasets which are usually limited to $E \leq 10\text{keV}$. As a result of a poor determination of the continuum spectrum, outflow features may not be properly resolved, especially emission lines for a high v_0 , which are spread over a wide energy range and have lower flux per unit keV and, hence, their detectability critically depends on a precise determination of the underlying continuum. Joint observations between e.g. *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* are particularly useful, since they allow to probe the whole X-ray energy band from ≈ 0.4 to $> 20\text{keV}$, as done e.g. in Nardini et al. (2015) for PDS 456.

As shown in Fig. 6.7, absorption features always exhibit higher EW with respect to the emission ones, i.e. a factor ~ 4 for $\xi_0 = 10^3$ and ~ 40 for $\xi_0 \geq 10^4$. For $\xi_0 = 10^3, 10^4$ the detectability of the emission features strongly depends on the accurate estimation of the underlying continuum spectrum. For extreme values of ξ_0 , i.e. $10^5, 10^6$, emission is particularly faint for any value of v_0, N_H . These results may explain the low detection rate of P-Cygni profiles among the UFOs reported in the literature. We plan to address these findings in a quantitative way through extensive simulations, by considering the spectral resolution of present-day X-ray CCD detectors as well as the higher one offered by the the next-generation microcalorimeters onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*, for both local, high X-ray flux Seyfert galaxies and high- z , low X-ray flux quasars.

Figure 6.10: Wind spectra for $\xi_0 = 10^3$. Blue and green lines refer to $N_H = 10^{23}$ and $5 \cdot 10^{23} \text{cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Top panels show the ratio between the wind spectrum and the incident continuum (blue dotted line represents unity), while bottom panels report the wind flux (in units of $10^{50} \text{erg s}^{-1} \text{erg}^{-1}$). Black dashed lines represents the local fit around the Fe K shell absorption lines. Light blue and yellow shaded areas show the wind emission and absorption features, respectively. Left, centre and right columns correspond to $v_0 = 0.05, 0.10, 0.30c$, respectively.

Figure 6.11: Same of Fig. 6.10 for $\xi_0 = 10^4$.

Figure 6.12: Same of Fig. 6.10 for $\xi_0 = 10^5$.

Figure 6.13: Same of Fig. 6.10 for $\xi_0 = 10^6$.

7. Application to the X-ray spectrum of PG 1448+273

PG 1448+273 is a low redshift ($z = 0.0645$) quasar characterised by an extremely high Eddington ratio of $\lambda_{edd} = 0.7$ and a bolometric luminosity of $1.9 \cdot 10^{45} \text{ ergs}^{-1}$. Kosec et al. (2020) first reported the evidence of a UFO in a 2017 *XMM-Newton* observation of this quasar, with best fit values $\log \xi = 4.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}$, $N_H = 2.8_{-0.7}^{+1.2} \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $v_{out} = 0.090 \pm 0.002 c$.

Given the remarkable UFO feature observed at $E \sim 6 - 8 \text{ keV}$, we reanalyse the X-ray spectrum using WINE. The results presented in this Chapter are part of a work in collaboration with M. Laurenti, F. Tombesi, F. Vagnetti, R. Middei, E. Piconcelli, accepted for publication in A&A (Laurenti et al., 2020).

7.1 Observations and data analysis

We analyse the observation of PG 1448+273 from the *XMM-Newton* satellite (Jansen et al., 2001) performed on January 24, 2017. We refer to Laurenti et al. (2020) for an extensive description of the data analysis and reduction. Raw data have been retrieved from the *XMM-Newton* Science Archive and then processed using the *XMM-Newton* Science Analysis System (SAS v18.0.0) with the latest available calibration files. Following the canonical process of data reduction for both EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 datasets, which is fully described in the SAS web page, we bin the spectra in order to have at least 25 counts in each bin, without oversampling the instrumental energy resolution by a factor larger than 3. This allows us to consistently adopt the χ^2 statistics. We present a journal of the observations in Tab. 7.1, and in Tab. 7.2 we illustrate the general

Table 7.1: Journal of the observation.

Obs. ID	Start date yyyy-mm-dd	Instrument	Net exp. (ks)
0781430101	2017-01-24	pn	76.3
		MOS1	107.2
		MOS2	110.0

Table 7.2: Overall properties of PG 1448+273. From left to right: Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) identifier; Galactic hydrogen column density; bolometric luminosity; black hole mass; Eddington ratio from Shen et al. (2011); source redshift.

SDSS ID	$N_{H,gal} (cm^{-2})$	$L_{bol} (erg s^{-1})$	$\log(M_{BH}/M_{\odot})$	λ_{Edd}	z
J145108.76+270926.9	$3.0 \cdot 10^{20}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{45}$	7.29	0.75	0.0645

properties of PG 1448+273. We also note that *XMM-Newton* observed PG 1448+273 also on February 8, 2003 for a shorter exposure time (~ 20 ks), resulting in a lower-quality dataset which is basically featureless (Inoue et al., 2007; Kosec et al., 2020).

7.2 Spectral analysis and phenomenological modelling

We carry out a phenomenological analysis which will allow us to characterise the X-ray continuum spectrum, together with an assessment of the basic properties of the Fe K lines, which are the strongest in the spectrum. This analysis will pave the way for a detailed study of the outflow signatures with WINE. We first concentrate on the hard X-ray spectrum ($E = 2 - 9$ keV rest frame), where the Fe K profiles are observed. We conservatively exclude from the analysis all data above 9 keV due to their poor S/N ratio and possible background contamination. Then, we extend the analysis to the soft X-ray band to accurately describe the broadband continuum spectrum in the $E = 0.3 - 9$ keV band. Throughout this section, errors are stated at 90% c.l., if not stated otherwise. We always jointly fit EPIC-pn and the two MOS datasets.

7.2.1 Hard X-ray spectrum

The spectrum is characterised by a remarkable absorption line at ~ 7.5 keV, preceded by emission at ~ 6.7 keV. We start with a simple continuum model consisting in a power-law modified by Galactic absorption and an intercalibration constant between the different instruments. The best fit value of the power-law photon index is $\Gamma = 1.90 \pm 0.03$. The overall statistics is poor, with a value of $\chi^2 = 466.5$ for 264 d.o.f. We report the best fit values in Table 7.3, first column. Hereafter, the redshift of all the components and the Galactic absorbing column are fixed to the values reported in Table 7.2.

We show the ratio between the data points and the continuum model in Fig. 7.1. A strong absorption line around 7-8 keV is clearly visible, together with a (weaker) emission line at lower energies. To reproduce these features we add a Gaussian line to the model, with line energy free to vary between 5 and 9 keV and a normalisation that can take both positive and negative values (corresponding to an emission and an absorption line, respectively). The contour plot of line

Figure 7.1: Ratio between the data points and the best fit model describing the hard X-ray continuum, zoomed on the 4 – 9 keV energy interval. Data from EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 are shown respectively in black, red and blue. The model consists in a power-law with Galactic absorption. Data are rebinned to a minimum S/N of 20σ and up to 2 counts for plotting purposes only.

energy vs. normalisation in the 5-9 keV band confirms the presence of these two features at 99% confidence level (Fig. 7.2).

The fit improvement is substantial, with $\chi^2 = 308.2$ for 261 d.o.f. ($\delta\chi^2 = 158$ for 3 d.o.f. with respect to the previous model). The absorption line has an energy $E = 7.51 \pm 0.07$ keV, a width $\sigma = 0.28^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$ keV and an equivalent width $EW = -390 \pm 70$ eV. The underlying continuum is now best fitted with a shallower photon index, $\Gamma = 1.80 \pm 0.03$ (see Table 7.3, second column). We perform an F-test and we find that the detection is statistically sound in each of the EPIC dataset, and the joint EPIC-pn+MOS1+MOS2 confidence level is $> 9\sigma$ (see Table 7.4). We also find that the equivalent widths of the absorption line detected in each instrument are compatible within the errors. These findings are also supported by the Monte Carlo simulations performed in Kosec et al. (2020). We also note that in the energy interval of the absorption line ($E = 7 - 8$ keV) the background contribution is not substantial, counting for less than 17% of the total counts.

As a further refinement, we now include a second Gaussian component to take into account

Table 7.3: Best fit values. First three columns report the values relative to the hard spectrum, for increasing number of fitting components (left to right). Last column shows the best fit values for the broadband spectrum. Note: (a) Fixed value.

Component	Value	Value	Value	Value
	Hard spectrum			Broadband Spectrum
<i>const</i>	1.03	1.02	1.03	1.02
<i>TBabs</i> (10^{20}cm^{-2})	3.0 ^a	3.0 ^a	3.0 ^a	3.0 ^a
<i>zpowerlaw</i>				
Γ	1.90 ± 0.03	1.80 ± 0.03	1.82 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.01
<i>norm</i> (10^{-4})	5.2 ± 0.2	4.6 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.2	5.2 ± 0.1
<i>zgauss_{abs}</i>				
<i>E</i> (keV)	-	7.51 ± 0.07	7.50 ± 0.07	7.48 ± 0.04
σ (keV)	-	$0.28^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	0.3 ± 0.1	$0.26^{+0.06}_{-0.05}$
EW (eV)	-	-390 ± 70	-410 ± 80	-340 ± 40
<i>zgauss_{em}</i>				
<i>E</i> (keV)	-	-	6.67 ± 0.08	$6.65^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$
σ (keV)	-	-	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a
EW (keV)	-	-	90^{+50}_{-30}	100 ± 20
<i>blackbody</i>				
<i>kT</i> (eV)	-	-	-	110.8 ± 0.3
<i>norm</i> (10^{-5})	-	-	-	5.62 ± 0.05
$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f}$	466.5/264	308.2/261	293.3/259	763.0/410

Figure 7.2: Contour plot describing the normalisation vs the rest-frame energy of a Gaussian line component, added on top of the power-law continuum. Black, red and green lines refer, respectively, to 68%, 90% and 99% confidence levels.

Table 7.4: F-test probability for the absorption line component in the EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 datasets. The fit improvement $\Delta\chi^2$ is associated to $\Delta(\text{d.o.f.}) = 3$.

Instrument	$\Delta\chi^2$	P_F
pn	72.58	$> 6\sigma$
MOS1	60.97	$> 5\sigma$
MOS2	39.14	$> 5\sigma$
pn + MOS1 + MOS2	158.3	$> 9\sigma$

the apparent emission feature at ~ 6.7 keV. This model can be described, in the XSPEC language, as:

$$\text{const} \cdot TBabs \cdot (zpowerlaw + zgauss_{em} + zgauss_{abs}) \quad (7.1)$$

where $TBabs$, $zpowerlaw$, $zgauss_{em}$, $zgauss_{abs}$ represents Galactic absorption, power-law continuum and Gaussian emission and absorption lines, respectively. The \cdot and $+$ signs indicate a convolution and a composition of different spectral components, as in Sect. 3.2.1. We obtain a best fit value for the line energy of $E = 6.67 \pm 0.08$ keV and an equivalent width $EW = 90_{-30}^{+50}$ eV. The line width is unconstrained and we fixed it to the instrumental energy resolution of 100 eV. The continuum and the other spectral components are consistent with the previous fit. The statistic improvement is $\Delta\chi^2 = 15$ for $\Delta d.o.f. = 2$ (see Table 7.3, third column), corresponding to a probability $P_F > 3\sigma$. We show the best fit in Fig. 7.3.

Figure 7.3: Top panel: Hard X-ray spectrum of PG 1448+273. The data from EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 are shown respectively in black, red and blue. The fitted model consists in a power-law (corrected for Galactic absorption) and Gaussian emission and absorption lines. Bottom panel: Ratio between the data points and the best fit model. Data are rebinned for plotting purposes.

Notwithstanding the goodness of the fit, we observe some deviation in the residuals around ~ 7.5 keV. Thus, we try to model the single broad absorption with two narrow Gaussian line profiles. By freezing the energies of the two putative lines to those related to Fe XXV (6.7 keV)

and Fe XXVI (6.97 keV) K-shell resonant transitions, we find them to be characterised by the same blueshift, corresponding to a velocity of $\sim 0.09c$. However, the additional component is not supported by a significant statistic improvement, and we postpone any further refinement of the fitting model to the analysis performed with WINE.

7.2.2 Broadband X-ray spectrum

The extension of the $E = 2 - 9\text{keV}$ model to the broadband ($E = 0.3 - 9\text{keV}$ observer frame) spectrum shows a strong soft excess (Fig. 7.4, top panel), that we model with a blackbody

Figure 7.4: Broadband spectrum ($E = 0.3 - 9\text{keV}$). Top panel: ratio between the hard-X ray datasets and the best fit model, once extended up to 0.3keV . A soft excess is clearly visible. Mid panel: best fit of the broadband X-ray spectrum once a black-body component is included. Bottom panel: updated ratio between the datapoints and the model. Data are rebinned for plotting purposes.

component ($zbody$). The previous fitting model (Eq. 7.1) is now modified as:

$$const \cdot TBabs \cdot (zpowerlw + zgauss_{em} + zgauss_{abs} + zbody) \quad (7.2)$$

The spectral fit, shown in Fig. 7.4 (central and bottom panels), returns a value of $\chi^2 = 763.02$ for 410 d.o.f.. We note that this result is affected by the complexity of the soft spectrum, which seems to display emission and absorption features below $1keV$, as discussed also in Kosec et al. (2020). We obtain a power-law index $\Gamma = 1.89 \pm 0.02$ and a blackbody temperature of $kT = 110.8 \pm 0.7 eV$ (see Table 7.3, last column). These values are in agreement with the bulk of the PG sample of radio quiet quasars (see e.g. Piconcelli et al. 2005 for an extensive review). The best fit values of the Gaussian components are consistent with the previous results. We will use the continuum spectrum derived from the broadband fit to describe the ionising continuum in the WINE modelling.

7.3 WINE fit

We fit the hard X-ray band with WINE to investigate in detail the Fe K shell features. We use as incident spectrum and luminosity (S_I, L_{ion} , respectively) the best fit model of the broadband spectrum of PG 1448+273 (Sect. 7.2.2 and Table 7.3, last column). Motivated by the results of the phenomenological fit, we explore the following intervals for the free parameters of the model:

- r_0 : we span the interval $[10, 140] r_S$ with steps of $10 r_S$, where $r_S = 2GM_{BH}/c^2$ is the Schwarzschild radius, and G, M_{BH}, c are the gravitational constant, the SMBH mass and the speed of light, respectively. This interval is consistent with the typical launching radii derived for UFOs (see Sect. 1.3.2 and Sect. 5). We convert from r_S to cm using the black hole mass listed in Tab. 7.2.
- ξ_0 : we span the interval $\log(\xi_0/erg cm s^{-1}) \in [4.0, 6.0]$ with steps of 0.25. This high degree of ionisation is consistent with a large fraction of Fe being in Fe XXV and Fe XXVI state (Kallman et al., 2004), as suggested by the observed absorption and emission lines around 6-7 keV.
- N_H : we span the interval $[5 \cdot 10^{22}, 10^{24}] cm^{-2}$ with steps of $5 \cdot 10^{22} cm^{-2}$. A high resolution radiative transfer is implemented through a sub-slab slicing of the column density, with $\delta N_H = 10^{22} cm^{-2}$ (see Sect. 6.1.4 for further details).
- v_0 : we span the interval $[0.00, 0.45]c$ with steps of $0.05c$.

Moreover, we fix the wind density profile index $\alpha \equiv 1$, so that $n(r) = n_0 (r_0/r)$, as suggested by the absorption measure distribution (AMD; Behar, 2009; Tombesi et al., 2013) and by theoretical models within the MHD framework (e.g. Fukumura et al., 2010). In the case of a momentum-conserving wind, as expected for accretion disc winds (see Sect. 1.4), the velocity profile can be expressed as $v(r) = v_0(r_0/r)^{(\alpha-2)/2} = v_0(r_0/r)^{1/2}$ (see Eqs. 6.1,6.2 in Section 6). We create custom absorption and emission models in XSPEC, $WINE_{abs}$ and $WINE_{em}$ respectively, by uploading the computed spectra as table models, in analogy with what discussed in Sect. 3.2 for the PDS 456 fit.

In the XSPEC language the fitting model can be described as:

$$constant \cdot TBabs \cdot (WINE_{abs} \cdot (zpow + zbody) + WINE_{em}) \quad (7.3)$$

The continuum is described by a power-law and a blackbody component (in agreement with the results of Sect. 7.2.2), which is then absorbed by the wind. We concentrate on the hard spectrum to better model Fe K shell transitions, while leaving the photon index Γ and the parameters of the black body component ($zbody$) fixed to the best values of the broadband fit. We fix i , the inclination of the emission component, to $i = 0$, since it is unconstrained by the fit to the data. In principle, WINE emission and absorption parameters can be treated separately. However, we link all the parameters between these two components, with the only exception of θ_{out} , which belongs only to the emission.

We list the best fit values in Tab. 7.5, along with the derived covering factor of the wind C_f and the mass-averaged wind velocity v_{avg} . The redshift of all the components is fixed to the value in Tab. 7.2. We find that the outflowing material is highly ionised, $\log \xi = 5.53^{+0.04}_{-0.05} \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$, has a large column density, $N_H = 4.5^{+0.8}_{-1.1} \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, is ejected with a maximum velocity $v_0 = 0.24^{+0.08}_{-0.06} c$, and attains an average outflow velocity $v_{avg} = 0.152c$. We successfully constrain the launching radius $r_0 = 77^{+31}_{-19} r_S$. Such constraint is of fundamental importance and represents one of the major novelties of WINE, given that it is often difficult to derive it in a stringent way, as discussed in Sect. 1.3.2, and one can usually provide only a rough estimate (e.g. Boissay-Malaquin et al., 2019) or upper and lower limits (e.g. Tombesi et al., 2012; Gofford et al., 2015). In addition, thanks to WINE we also to derive a lower limit on both the opening angle of the wind ($\theta > 72$) and then on the covering fraction ($C_f > 0.69$). We show in Fig. 7.5 a detail of the best fit with WINE, where it can be seen that there are no residual structures in the Fe K energy band and the emission and absorption features are modelled with high accuracy. Contour plots between r_0 and v_0 , $\log \xi$, N_H are displayed in Fig. 7.6. The fit statistics is $\chi^2/d.o.f. = 285/257$.

We note that our results point towards a slightly higher ionised and more massive outflow than Kosec et al. (2020), where $\log(\xi_0/\text{erg cm s}^{-1}) = 4.0 \pm 0.1$, $N_H = 2.8^{+1.2}_{-0.7} \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$; instead, the

Table 7.5: Best fit values of the WINE model. All errors are at 90% c.l. except for θ_{out} (1σ). Notes: (a) Parameter linked with the corresponding one in the absorption component. (b) Parameter estimated with 1σ error. (c) Derived value.

Component	Value
<i>constant</i>	1, 1.02 ± 0.2
<i>TBabs</i> - N_H (10^{20}cm^{-2})	3.01^a
<i>zpowerlaw</i>	
Γ	1.89^a
norm. (10^{-4})	5.7 ± 0.2
<i>zbody</i>	
T (eV)	110^a
norm. (10^{-5})	5.60^a
<i>wind_{abs}</i>	
r_0 (r_S)	77^{+31}_{-19}
$\log(\xi_0/\text{erg cm s}^{-1})$	$5.53^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$
N_H (10^{23}cm^{-2})	$4.5^{+0.8}_{-1.1}$
ν_0 (c)	$0.24^{+0.08}_{-0.06}$
<i>wind_{em}</i>	
r_0 (r_S)	77^a
$\log(\xi_0/\text{erg cm s}^{-1})$	5.53^a
N_H (10^{23}cm^{-2})	4.5^a
ν_0 (c)	0.24^a
θ_{out} (deg)	$> 72^b$
ν_{avg} (c)	$0.15^{+0.09}_{-0.08}^c$
C_f	$> 0.69^c$
$\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$	285.1/257 (=1.11)

Figure 7.5: WINE spectral fit zoomed on the UFO absorption feature. Data from EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 are shown in black, red and blue, respectively. Ratio between the datapoints and the WINE fit is presented in the bottom panel.

outflow velocity, $0.090 \pm 0.002 c$, is consistent with our v_{avg} within the error bars. The difference in N_H can be easily explained by taking into account the relativistic effects on the wind opacity, which are implemented in WINE but not in the fit of Kosec et al. (2020). Since the outflow is moving with a relativistic v_{out} , its apparent (i.e., observed) column density must be corrected according to v_{out} to obtain the intrinsic N_H (see Sect 4 and Fig. 4.4). Using the values reported in Kosec et al. (2020), we derive an intrinsic $N_H = 3.5^{+1.5}_{-0.9} \cdot 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which is in agreement with the value reported in Tab. 7.5. For what concerns the ionisation degree, we observe an apparent positive correlation in Kosec et al. (2020) between ξ and the velocity dispersion v_σ (see their Fig. 5). Their best fit value for v_σ is $2100 \text{ km s}^{-1} = 0.007c$. In the WINE model, the broadening of the features is primarily governed by the velocity shear along the wind column and we can estimate the velocity dispersion as $v_\sigma \sim |v_0 - v_{avg}| = 0.09 c$. Therefore, we speculate that our ξ , v_σ lie at the upper end of the observed correlation in Kosec et al. (2020). However, their table model ranges only up to maximum values of $\log(\xi_0/\text{erg cm s}^{-1}) = 4.8$, $v_\sigma = 0.03 c$, and hence we cannot draw a firm conclusion on this point.

Figure 7.6: Contour plots of the launching radius vs the outflow velocity (top panel), ionisation parameter (mid panel) and wind column density (bottom panel). Black, red and green lines correspond, respectively, to 68%, 90% and 99% confidence levels.

7.4 Outflow energetics

Using the best fit values of Tab. 7.5 and assuming $C_f = 0.7$, we calculate the mass outflow rate of the UFO by directly integrating the density and velocity profiles:

$$\dot{M}_{out} = 2 \mu m_p \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\theta_{out}} \int_{r_0}^{r_1} n(r) v(r) r \sin(\theta) dr d\theta d\phi \quad (7.4)$$

where μ, m_p are the mean atomic mass per proton (that we set to 1.2, see Gofford et al., 2015) and the proton mass, respectively. We derive n_0 inverting the definition of ξ_0 and we analytically calculate the final radius of the wind r_1 . We multiply the integral by a factor 2 to take into account the contribution from both hemispheres. We obtain $\dot{M}_{out} = 0.65^{+0.44}_{-0.33} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1} = 2.0^{+1.3}_{-1.0} \dot{M}_{acc}$ for a standard radiative efficiency $\eta = 0.1$, as expected for a thin accretion disc (see Sect. 1.2.1). Hereafter, we consider 1σ errors for the wind energetics.

We note that \dot{M}_{out} is a factor of ~ 2 higher than that derived using a first order formula, such as the one in Sect. 3 (see Eq. 1.5), i.e. $\dot{M}_{out}^{CK} = 4\pi r_0 N_H \mu m_p C_f v_0 = 0.25 \pm 0.07 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This latter formula implicitly assumes a constant density outflow with a constant velocity, and it is consistent with those used in several UFO studies reported in the literature (e.g. Tombesi et al. (2012); Gofford et al. (2015); Nardini et al. (2015); Feruglio et al. (2015); Dadina et al. (2018)). It corresponds to Eq. 7.4 in the case of constant density, i.e. $\alpha = 0$, and is characterised by a linear dependence on the wind parameters. Instead, in our work we set $\alpha = 1$ (see Sect. 7.3) and, as a result, the dependence from the parameters is non-linear. This shows that the mean value and errors calculated with \dot{M}_{out}^{CK} may underestimate the real value of the wind energetics if its radial profile deviates from the $\alpha = 0$ case.

Moreover, we note that the main contribution to the uncertainties is given by r_0 . The fractional uncertainty (i.e., the error interval divided by the mean value) for r_0 is the highest among the wind parameters in Tab. 7.5. To assess the impact of the uncertainties of the fit parameters on the error bar derived for \dot{M}_{out} , we calculate the uncertainty associated to \dot{M}_{out} by reducing the errors on each wind parameter, in turn, by a factor 10, while leaving all the others as in Tab. 7.5. While reducing the uncertainties on ξ, N_H, v_0 results in a decrease of less than 2% in the errors of \dot{M}_{out} , reducing the error band on r_0 gives $\dot{M}_{out} = 0.65^{+0.14}_{-0.10}$, i.e. a factor of 4 and 2 decrease for the lower and upper bound, respectively. This result shows the importance of an accurate determination of r_0 . We also note that lower and upper bounds for r_0 are often derived in the literature with even order-of-magnitude differences between them (see e.g. Tombesi et al., 2013; Gofford et al., 2015), and this would result in even higher uncertainties for \dot{M}_{out} .

We calculate the instantaneous kinetic power of the outflow using the special relativity

formula, as in Saez & Chartas (2011):

$$\dot{E}_{out} = (\gamma - 1) \cdot \dot{M}_{out} c^2 \quad (7.5)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor, calculated using v_{avg} , and we subtract the energy at rest, $\dot{M}_{out} c^2$. We obtain $\dot{E}_{out} = 4.4_{-3.6}^{+4.4} \cdot 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1} = 24\% L_{bol} = 18\% L_{Edd}$. We note that this value is slightly higher than the one calculated using the classic formula $\dot{E}^{classic} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{M}_{out} v_{avg}^2$, which gives a value of $4.36 \cdot 10^{44} \text{ erg/s}$. Finally, we find that the outflow momentum rate is $\dot{p}_{out} = 1.9 \cdot 10^{35} \text{ g cm s}^{-2} = 3.1 \dot{p}_{rad}$, where $\dot{p}_{rad} = L_{bol}/c$ is the radiation force. This may possibly suggest that the role of the magnetic field is not negligible in accelerating the wind (see e.g. Fukumura et al., 2015; Kraemer et al., 2018; Fukumura et al., 2018). We also signal that the UFO in PG 1448+273 lies slightly above the region of radiation driven winds in the $v_{out} - \lambda_{Edd}$ plot, shown in Fig. 5.15 (see Sect. 5.5).

The X-ray spectral fit of PG 1448+273 represents the first application of WINE. The accurate determination of the UFO location and energetics confirms the importance of a proper physical modelling of the wind.

8. Conclusions

8.1 Summary

This thesis presents the Wind in the Ionised Nuclear Environment (WINE) model, a new and innovative model for fitting the absorption and emission spectra of UFOs in AGN. The application of WINE to the UFOs detected in two nearby quasars, PDS 456 and PG 1448+273, is also reported. Moreover, we performed a theoretical study of the radiation driving for accretion disc winds including special relativity effects, a major novelty that allowed us to derive new, stringent limits on the maximum wind velocity. Our main findings can be summarised as follows:

- Our Monte Carlo approach, detailed in Sect. 3.1, enables a flexible and accurate modelling of the wind emission profiles. We assume an emitting wind with a conical geometry, which is consistent with the results of most of the simulations of accretion disc winds. This is also in broadly agreement with the galactic-scale outflows observed in AGN host galaxies, which typically exhibit a biconical or spherical-like morphology. We include the effects of special relativity on the gas velocity projection along the observer line of sight, and we also include a radial velocity gradient.

We apply our code to the powerful disc wind observed in the X-ray spectrum of PDS 456 (see Sect. 3.2 - 3.4). This nearby and luminous quasar ($z = 0.184$, $L_{bol} \approx 10^{47} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) hosts a UFO with $v_{out} \simeq 0.25c$ and $\dot{E}_{out} \simeq 20\% L_{bol}$ (Nardini et al., 2015), more than enough to trigger a galactic scale feedback according to theoretical expectations (e.g. Di Matteo et al., 2005). Thanks to our detailed treatment of the geometry of the emitting region, we obtain new constraints on the wind covering factor $C_f = 0.7$, suggesting a wide angle outflow. Moreover, we estimate the wind velocity and its radial extent. These findings allows us to obtain improved values for the UFO energetics: a mass outflow rate $\dot{M}_{out} = 0.23 \pm 0.06 \dot{M}_{Edd}$ and a kinetic power $\dot{E}_{out} \simeq 30 \pm 20\% L_{bol}$. These results have been published in Luminari et al. (2018).

- We demonstrate the importance of special relativity effects on the wind absorption (see Sect. 4). Similarly to what is usually considered for the wind emission, the Doppler shift of the line energies and the beaming of the luminosity deeply affect the wind absorption and the related spectral features. When fitting AGN spectra, wind opacity is usually

considered as a proxy for N_H , independently from v_{out} . However, this is no longer true for relativistic velocities: opacity is reduced by a factor ≈ 2 for $v_{out} = 0.1c$ and by a factor ≥ 10 for $v_{out} \gtrsim 0.8c$. We implement an algorithm to take into account these effects when performing radiative transfer simulations. This algorithm can be coupled to widely used photoionisation codes such as *Cloudy* and *XSTAR*, and it is directly implemented in WINE. We also quantify the impact of relativistic effects on the derived $\dot{M}_{out}, \dot{E}_{out}$ (which linearly depend on N_H) for a sample of UFOs in the literature. For the fastest of them ($v_{out} \geq 0.2c$), the relativistic-corrected values of the energetics are a factor ≈ 2 higher than the reported ones. We also consider that the reduction of the gas opacity for increasing v_{out} may introduce an observational bias, making faster winds more difficult to detect. This work has been published in Luminari et al. (2020).

- We assess the impact of special relativity effects on the wind radiative acceleration (see Sect. 5). The reduced opacity for increasing v_{out} implies a reduction of the radiative pressure exerted on the gas, since the overall interaction rate of the radiation field with the gas follows the opacity drop. We perform a set of radiative driving simulations for a gas launched from a thin accretion disc, with a set of fiducial UFO-like values for N_H, ξ_0, v_{out} . We account for both continuum driving (i.e., Thompson scattering) and line driving, through a novel technique to calculate force multipliers in the UV-to-X-ray energy band. We find that relativistic effects strongly reduce the radiative acceleration imparted on the gas. This leads to typical velocities for UFOs up to 50% less than the classical treatment (i.e., without relativistic corrections): for a typical launching radius $R_0 \geq 50r_G$, we obtain a terminal velocity $v_t = 0.15c$ for an AGN luminosity $\lambda_{Edd} \equiv L_{bol}/L_{Edd} = 1.0$, compared to a classical value of $\approx 0.20c$. We compare the velocities of a broad sample of UFOs from the literature with our theoretical, relativistic-corrected v_t as a function of λ_{Edd} . We find that the reported UFO velocities are systematically higher than our expectations for a pure radiation-driven acceleration, thereby suggesting an additional launching mechanism; in particular, we note that magnetic acceleration could be a promising candidate. See Luminari et al. (2021) for further results.
- The current version of WINE (presented in Sect. 6.1) combines the Monte Carlo modelling of the wind emission with the *XSTAR* radiative transfer code, once corrected for special relativity effects (Sect. 3.1 and 4.2). As a result, the synthetic wind profiles are fully resolved both from a geometric and a kinematic point of view. The WINE model is designed to go beyond the main assumptions of the most popular radiative transfer codes, such as *XSTAR* and *Cloudy*, which are the followings:

- The gas is set to be at rest, in contrast with the mildly relativistic velocities usually observed for disc winds.
- The gas geometry is that of a thin, spherically symmetric shell around the luminosity source, whilst this geometry is not clearly supported both observationally and theoretically.

We outline the detailed working flow of WINE and its free parameters and we discuss the spectral accuracy and all the relevant numerical aspects.

- Thanks to the spectral accuracy of WINE, we determine in Sect. 6.3, 6.4 the UFO parameter space in order to assess the detectability and the observational appearance of P-Cygni profiles, given by the simultaneous presence of wind absorption and emission, primarily in the Fe K energy band around 6-8 keV. We find that emission profiles always have lower equivalent width (EW) with respect to the absorption ones: for a ionisation parameter $\xi_0 = 10^3$ (expressed in units of $erg\ cm\ s^{-1}$), emission EW is a factor ~ 4 lower than the corresponding absorption one, while for $\xi_0 \geq 10^4$ the factor becomes ~ 40 . In addition, the detectability and the strength of the emission due to fast outflowing gas ($v_{out} > 0.10c$) is further complicated by the projection of the lines over a large observed velocity range, i.e. over a large energy interval. For $\xi_0 \geq 10^4$, emission lines can be smeared over an interval of up to some keV, thus requiring an accurate determination of the underlying continuum spectrum to detect them. This task can be especially difficult in the presence of additional spectral components, such as a soft excess or a warm absorber at $E \lesssim 3keV$ and Fe K shell photoionisation edges at $E \gtrsim 9keV$, that could introduce a degeneracy when fitting the continuum spectrum. These findings may be able to explain the limited occurrence of P-Cygni profiles among the observed UFO spectra. We plan to explore our results in a more quantitative way through extensive simulations of UFO spectra, using the resolution of current X-ray CCD detectors as well as of the future microcalorimeters onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*.
- Finally, we analyse the 2017 *XMM-Newton* spectrum of the quasar PG 1448+273 with WINE in Sect. 7. The presence of a UFO is traced by absorption and emission profiles in the 6-8 keV energy band. The outflow is extremely fast and ionised: $v_{out} = 0.24^{+0.008}_{-0.006}c$, $\log(\xi_0/erg\ cm\ s^{-1}) = 5.53^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$. Remarkably, we successfully constrain the launching radius and we derive a lower limit for the covering factor: $r_0 = 77^{+31}_{-19}r_S$, $C_f > 0.69$. This allows us to estimate the energetics of the wind in a self-consistent way, by directly integrating the wind density and velocity profiles and without assuming any quantity *a priori* (with the exception of the density profile index α). The results of this analysis have

been published in Laurenti et al. (2020). We obtain a mass outflow rate $\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.65M_{\odot} = 2.0\dot{M}_{acc}$, where \dot{M}_{acc} is the mass inflow rate onto the accretion disc. This value may suggest that the wind is able to deeply affect the disc, possibly regulating its mass input onto the black hole. Interestingly, the presence of the UFO is simultaneous to the beginning of a drop of the overall X-ray flux. As discussed in Laurenti et al. (2020), the resulting X-ray weakness could be explained thanks to the the wind, which removes a substantial fraction of the accreting matter at the innermost radii. Furthermore, we estimate an outflow kinetic power $\dot{E}_{out} = 4.4 \cdot 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1} = 24\%L_{bol}$. The latter is fairly larger than the values assumed by the most popular model of AGN feedback, usually between 0.5% and 5% L_{bol} (Hopkins & Elvis, 2010; Di Matteo et al., 2005), to provide an effective impact on the host galaxy evolution.

8.2 Future perspectives

8.2.1 Application to observations

The promising results already obtained with WINE suggest the importance of a comprehensive and detailed analysis of spectra of AGN with UFO collected so far. In particular, we plan to apply WINE to powerful and persistent outflows and to study the variability of their observational properties. This would allow a tighter constraint of the wind physical properties, as well as its relation with the X-ray flux and the accretion flow. As an example, the UFO in the X-ray spectrum of the quasar PDS 456 has been observed since the early 2000s (see Sect. 3.2 and Boissay-Malaquin et al., 2019; Reeves et al., 2018). The presence of the wind, as well as its properties and energetics appear to be linked to the intense variability of the X-ray spectrum and luminosity, thus offering a prime opportunity to systematically analyse the relation between the accretion flow and the wind.

Similarly, the high- z , luminous quasar APM 08279+5255 ($z = 3.9$, $\lambda_{Edd} \approx 0.4$) shows a fast UFO over a six-years interval from ~ 2002 to 2008 (Chartas et al., 2009; Saez & Chartas, 2011), with reported $v_{out} \geq 0.35c$. Moreover, even though v_{out} is too high to be explained via radiation driving, as discussed in Sect. 5.6 (see Fig. 5.15), it appears to be somehow correlated with the X-ray luminosity and the powerlaw index Γ , suggesting an interesting link between the wind and the accretion power (Saez & Chartas, 2011; Hagino et al., 2017). Furthermore, strong C IV BAL (Saturni et al., 2018) and significant galaxy-scale molecular outflows (Feruglio et al., 2017) have been observed, possibly hinting at an energy-conserving outflow propagation. The accurate determination of the UFO energetics with WINE may help to shed new light on the wind feedback in APM 08279+5255.

Moreover, multiphase outflows are detected in X-ray spectra through absorption (and emission) features with different N_H, ξ_0, v_{out} between them. They are generally ascribed to different gas layers expanding outward, whose spectral properties are affected by the distance from the luminosity source and the interaction with the ambient medium. Therefore, they represent an interesting probe of the scaling of the wind properties with radius and its evolution during the propagation. An interesting example is given by 1H0707-495 (Kosec et al., 2018), where absorption and emission features show rather different ionisations, i.e. $\log(\xi_0/erg\ cm\ s^{-1}) = 4.3$ and $= 2.4$, respectively. Interestingly, emission is found to be blueshifted, pointing toward a non-spherical emitting region, as indeed expected and modelled within WINE. Serafinelli et al. (2019) detected a three layer structure in the X-ray spectrum of PG 1114+445, composed by a Warm Absorber, an UFO and, finally, a set of absorption features with ξ_0, N_H comparable with the WA ones and with a UFO-like v_{out} . A study of multiphase outflows with WINE may allow to explore in detail the scaling of the observational properties with increasing distance from the black hole, and to assess whether they may represent the same outflow caught at different evolutionary steps.

The large program SUBWAYS targeted 20 quasars at $z \approx 0.1 - 0.4$ to study the presence of outflows with high data quality in a large and representative sample. The *XMM-Newton* observational campaign (PI M. Brusa) has been performed during AO-18 for a total of 1.58 Ms, and the *NuSTAR* one (PI S. Bianchi) has been assigned 610 ks in cycle 6. We are participating in the technical working group *Development of photo-ionisation models* devoted to the production of theoretical templates to fit the X-ray spectra. WINE will be a key part of the analysis toolkit and its results will be interfaced with those from different models, in order to compare and cross-fertilise the different approaches.

Finally, WINE is being employed within a X-ray spectroscopic survey of 14 highly-accreting AGNs observed with *XMM-Newton*. The aim of this work is to explore the evolution of the Comptonising corona at super-Eddington accretion rates, through a detailed assessment of the power-law index Γ , the bolometric correction and the optical/UV SED. In one of these objects WINE constrained the presence of an absorber with intermediate properties between Warm Absorbers and UFOs, possibly suggesting a change in the outflow dynamics at the high Eddington end of the AGN distribution. The results will be published in a forthcoming paper (Luminari et al., *in prep.*).

8.2.2 Simulations and theoretical developments

Starting from the results shown in Sect. 6.3 and 6.4, we are undertaking an extensive simulation campaign to assess in detail the detectability of wind absorption and emission lines and, in

particular, P-Cygni profiles. We are simulating spectra with the resolution of both *XMM-Newton* EPIC CCD and next generation microcalorimeters onboard *XRISM* and *Athena*, for a realistic set of photon fluxes and exposure times. Our aim is to estimate the detectability and the expected EW of the wind features as a function of N_H , ξ_0 , v_{out} , the incident continuum spectrum (particularly the photon index Γ) and the source distance and luminosity.

Moreover, WINE is being used to simulate UFO spectra in distant quasars and estimate their spectroscopic detectability with *Athena*. We are reproducing a set of quasar luminosities, redshifts and exposure times in pointed observations with the X-ray microcalorimeter X-IFU and in survey fields covered by the wide field-of-view detector WFI. This work is coordinated by Dr. L. Zappacosta (INAF - Observatory of Rome) and will be part of the Assessment Study (Red Book) supporting the adoption of *Athena* in the European Space Agency (ESA) Science Program in 2021. As a check, we ran WINE simulations imposing the same conditions adopted in different radiative transfer codes, such as *XSTAR* and *Phase* (Krongold et al., 2003, 2007), obtaining a good overall agreement.

It will also be useful to implement a time-dependent photoionisation in WINE, as done e.g. in Nicastro et al. (1999) and Garcia et al. (2013). This will make possible to accurately relate the evolution of the outflow ionisation status with variations of the continuum luminosity, which are ubiquitous in both AGNs and compact sources, such as ultra-luminous X-ray sources and X-ray binaries. A time-evolving study allows to closely probe the outflow structure, also by breaking the degeneracy between distance and density in determining the ionisation status of the gas, as performed e.g. in Krongold et al. (2007) for NGC4051 (see Sect. 1.3.1). Interestingly, a rapid variation of the outflow ionisation status in response to the intrinsic X-ray variability has been also suggested for the UFO in IRAS 13224-3809 (Parker et al., 2017). A time-dependent modelling would allow to follow the evolution of the observational appearance of the UFO and to properly assess its physical properties. Moreover, we plan to integrate in WINE the improved atomic databases that are being compiled in light of the next *XRISM* and *Athena* missions and to test the coupling of different radiative transfer codes with WINE, such as *Cloudy* or *SPEX* (see Sect. 2.2). We present in Fig. 8.1 a scheme of the main features of current photoionisation codes and of the WINE model, both in its current version and after the developments described above.

Finally, thanks to its modular structure, WINE can be easily applied to emission and absorption features at different scales (e.g. interstellar and intergalactic medium), with the possibility to add additional parameters such as a multi-zone temperature and/or ionisation status, define different density and velocity profiles and modify the geometry of the emitting region.

Figure 8.1: Main features of the current photoionisation codes (left) and of the WINE model, in its actual version (center) and after future developments (right)

9. Acknowledgements

Scientific research is a collective activity, which naturally brings people together to achieve a common goal. During these three years of PhD I had the opportunity to meet and collaborate with several people and all of them helped me to improve my work. I want to thank my thesis supervisors, particularly Prof. Francesco Tombesi and Dr. Enrico Piconcelli, for their guidance and their interesting suggestions, that have been fundamental in shaping my PhD research activity. They carefully followed my work step by step and they trusted me when exploring new ideas, always ready to discuss together and to help me. I am also grateful to the AGN group at the Observatory of Rome (OAR-INAF) for the stimulating and cooperative environment, and particularly to Luca Zappacosta, Fabrizio Nicastro and Nicola Menci (just to name a few), together with Fabrizio Fiore, Manuela Bischetti, Andrea Travascio, who moved from Rome. Thanks to all of them I learned a lot on AGNs and astrophysics in general, and I have been able to put my work within a broader physical perspective, therefore enormously increasing its validity. They also helped me in solving numerical and theoretical problems during the development of the WINE code and in dealing with X-ray observations and simulations in general. I also thank Keigo Fukumura and Demosthenes Kazanas for helping me during my first steps with radiative transfer and for sharing with me a copy of their MHD wind code, from which the first version of WINE was born. I am grateful to Martin Elvis and all the people I collaborated with at the Center for Astrophysics - Harvard & Smithsonian (CfA), where significant part of the work on the radiative acceleration of winds has been carried on. I also thank Massimo Cappi for his careful review of this thesis, which led to several improvements, and for interesting discussions on AGNs and X-ray winds in general. Everything I did would not have been possible without the collective, passionate efforts of all these people.

I also thank all those people who are often "invisible" in the academic life. I refer in particular to the administrative personnel of the universities Sapienza and Tor Vergata, OAR-INAF and CfA, that helped me in several key aspects. In particular, I want to mention Fernanda Lupinacci from Sapienza secretariat for her kind help for the PhD admission exam and for many other topics. At the CfA, Donna Wyatt promptly guided me through all the paperwork and let me start with the right step during my visiting period. Stefano Battaglione from Tor Vergata followed me for the administrative issues regarding meetings, conferences and schools attended abroad.

The extensive WINE code calculations would not have been possible without the servers

made available by Tor Vergata and OAR-INAF. I thank Federico Zani, from the Tor Vergata IT office, and Luca Zappacosta and the CED-SID office at OAR for assisting me on this topic. They always answered to my requests readily, even the most cumbersome ones (and I know there were many!), and developed custom solutions to help me fully exploit the computing power.

My family and my friends have been fundamental during this three years of PhD, which have been exciting, intense and demanding. My parents followed me with intelligence, love and originality during all the time. They helped me to get started with the new challenges and the new perspectives of these years, and I am happy we resisted together to all the difficulties posed by the coronavirus pandemic in the last year. I thank my friends for their support and for making me feel loved: thanks to Alberto, Andrea, Marco, Michele, Valeria and all the others. I also thank Giordano, Gauri and Enzo for their attention toward me and for making me feel at home while I was in Boston. Finally, I thank Laria for being my faithful companion and for believing in me.

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